

VALUATION OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES: PHILOSOPHY, ECOLOGY AND
POLICY

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ABSTRACT

VALUATION OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES: PHILOSOPHY, ECOLOGY AND POLICY

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This thesis aims to explore the challenges and opportunities associated with the valuation of ecosystem services through the lens of environmental ethics and ecological philosophy. Through a critical analysis of existing literature and case studies, this thesis analyzes a range of approaches and methods employed for valuing ecosystem services and discusses the potential for integrating these values into decision-making processes. This thesis asserts that at the nexus of the deep-rooted dichotomies of the environmental debate—anthropocentrism and non-anthropocentrism, intrinsic and instrumental value, and economic and ethical considerations—lies the potential for ecosystem services valuation to furnish decision-makers with crucial insights into sustainable policies and practices for the conservation of ecosystems and biological diversity. It is argued that by promoting greater recognition of ecosystem services, a more integrated and multidisciplinary approach can enhance the visibility of such services and their role in effective management practices. The study further aims to formulate suggestions for future

research in this domain and highlight the importance of continued efforts to increase awareness and understanding of the value of ecosystem services among policymakers and the general public.

Keywords: Ecosystem Services, Environmental Ethics, Ecological Philosophy, Ecology, Biological Diversity, Environmental Economics

ÖZ

EKOSİSTEM SERVİSLERİNİN KIYMETLENDİRİLMESİ: FELSEFE, EKOLOJİ VE POLİTİKA

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Bu tez, ekosistem servislerinin kıymetlendirilmesiyle ilgili zorlukları ve fırsatları çevre etiği ve ekolojik felsefe perspektifinden incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Mevcut literatürün ve vaka çalışmalarının eleştirel analizi yoluyla ekosistem hizmetlerinin değerlendirilmesi için kullanılan farklı yaklaşımları ve yöntemleri inceleyen bu tez çalışması, söz konusu değerlerin karar verme süreçlerine dahil edilebilme potansiyelini tartışmaktadır. Bu tez, çevresel tartışmaların kökleri derinlere inen ikiliklerinin (insanmerkezcilik ve insanmerkezcilik dışı olma, içsel ve araçsal değer ve ekonomik ve etik mülhazalar) kesişim noktasında, ekosistem servisleri kıymetlendirmesinin karar vericilere ekosistemlerin ve biyolojik çeşitliliğin korunması için sürdürülebilir politika ve uygulamalar oluşturma konusunda önemli içgörüler sağlama potansiyelinin yattığını ileri sürmektedir. Ekosistem servislerinin tanınmasının teşviki yoluyla, daha bütünleşik ve çok disiplinli bir yaklaşımın, bu tür hizmetlerin görünürlüğünü ve etkili yönetim uygulamalarındaki rolünü artırabileceği tartışılmaktadır. Çalışma ayrıca, bu alanda gelecekteki araştırmalar için öneriler sunmayı ve politika yapıcılar ve toplum nezdinde ekosistem hizmetlerinin değerine

ilişkin farkındalığı ve kavrayışı artırmaya yönelik süregelen çabaların önemini vurgulamayı amaçlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Ekosistem Servisleri, Çevre Etiği, Ekoloji Felsefesi, Ekoloji, Biyolojik Çeşitlilik, Çevre Ekonomisi

Dedication

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATIONS

ANOVA: Analysis of Variance

EEA: European Environment Agency

EDA: Exploratory Data Analysis

EPA: Environmental Protection Agency

ES: Ecosystem Services

EU: European Union

IBM: International Business Machines Corporation

MA: Millennium Ecosystem Assessment

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

TEV: Total Economic Value

TÜİK: Turkish Statistical Institute

UN: United Nations

UN CBD: United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity

USDA: United States Department of Agriculture

WTP: Willingness to Pay

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between humans and nature has always been central to the pursuit of sustainability, with increasing urgency in recent decades. The degradation of ecosystems and biological diversity due to urbanization, industrialization, and climate change underscores the importance of understanding and valuing the natural world. Ecosystem services, which encompass the tangible and intangible benefits humans derive from nature, have emerged as a critical concept for bridging ecological science with policy and public awareness (MA, 2005a). This thesis situates itself at the intersection of environmental ethics, economics, and conservation strategies, focusing on the valuation of ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir, a small but ecologically significant urban lake in Ankara, Türkiye.

Lake Eymir exemplifies the dynamic interplay between natural ecosystems and human activities, serving as a recreational, cultural, and ecological hub for Ankara's residents. However, its proximity to an urban center exposes it to various environmental challenges, from eutrophication to anthropogenic pressures. These challenges necessitate a comprehensive approach to its conservation, combining ethical imperatives, economic justifications, and community engagement. The present study addresses this need by evaluating the ecosystem services of Lake Eymir through quantitative and qualitative lenses, integrating advanced valuation techniques and ethical considerations to provide actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders.

One of the core challenges in environmental conservation is reconciling the diverse values attributed to ecosystems. On the one hand, ecosystems are often appreciated for their instrumental value, providing essential services such as carbon storage,

oxygen production, and recreational opportunities. On the other hand, they also hold intrinsic value, being worthwhile in themselves (Rolston, 1988). This thesis adopts a holistic perspective, combining the Total Economic Value (TEV) framework with ecosystem service valuation methodologies to capture both dimensions. It utilizes the i-Tree Canopy tool to quantify regulating services, and incorporates a Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) survey to evaluate cultural and ethical values, as well as economic values, highlighting the multifaceted significance of Lake Eymir.

The research objectives of this thesis are threefold. First, it seeks to identify and quantify the ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir, emphasizing their relevance to urban sustainability and community well-being. Second, it aims to understand the societal perceptions and values associated with these services, using cluster analysis to segment respondents based on their preferences, activity patterns, and WTP. Finally, it explores the ethical underpinnings of ecosystem valuation, addressing the philosophical debates surrounding instrumental and intrinsic values and their implications for conservation strategies. These objectives are guided by the overarching question: how can the valuation of ecosystem services inform sustainable management practices for urban ecosystems like Lake Eymir?

The methodological framework combines quantitative and qualitative approaches to ensure a comprehensive analysis. The i-Tree Canopy tool was used to estimate the regulating services of Lake Eymir, such as carbon sequestration and flood control, providing baseline data for economic valuation. Concurrently, a WTP survey was conducted to capture public preferences and perceptions, encompassing a range of ecosystem services, cultural benefits, and ethical considerations. The survey's design accounted for both use and non-use values, ensuring inclusivity and representation. Statistical techniques, including regression and cluster analysis, were applied to analyze the data, uncovering distinct societal segments and their respective priorities.

This thesis contributes to the literature in several ways. It bridges theoretical debates in environmental ethics with practical conservation efforts, demonstrating how ethical frameworks can inform economic valuation and policy. By integrating

advanced tools like the i-Tree Canopy and WTP methodologies, it provides a replicable model for urban ecosystem valuation. Additionally, the findings offer actionable recommendations for enhancing the conservation and management of Lake Eymir, emphasizing equity, inclusivity, and community engagement. These contributions are particularly relevant in the context of Türkiye, where urban ecosystems face growing pressures but also hold significant potential for sustainable development.

The structure of this thesis highlights its interdisciplinary framework, systematically integrating concepts from environmental economics, ethics, and conservation science. Chapter 2 establishes the conceptual foundation, introducing key theoretical constructs such as ecosystem services, Total Economic Value (TEV), and environmental ethics, which serve as the intellectual underpinnings of the study. Chapter 3 focuses on the application of the i-Tree Canopy tool, detailing its methodology, configuration steps, and analysis of Lake Eymir's ecosystem services. This chapter highlights how the tool was used to quantify significant regulating services, such as carbon sequestration, air pollution removal and flood control, providing a solid foundation for subsequent valuation efforts.

Chapter 4 is divided into two parts. The first part explains the design and implementation of the WTP survey, regression analysis, and clustering techniques, outlining the rationale behind these methods and their integration into the study's objectives. The second part presents the results of the survey and data analysis, offering insights into the valuation of Lake Eymir's ecosystem services, the segmentation of respondents based on preferences and values, and the statistical relationships among the variables. Chapter 5 synthesizes the valuation of Lake Eymir, integrating findings from the Willingness to Pay (WTP) survey and i-Tree Canopy analysis to assess the lake's Total Economic Value (TEV) through its use, non-use, and option value components. Finally, the Conclusion synthesizes these findings, situating them within the broader contexts of policymaking, ethical frameworks, and sustainable resource management. It highlights the importance of integrating intrinsic and instrumental values into ecosystem service valuation and

provides actionable recommendations for enhancing conservation strategies, ensuring inclusivity, and addressing limitations.

In addressing the multifaceted values of Lake Eymir, this thesis emphasizes the importance of interdisciplinary approaches to environmental conservation. By integrating ethical, economic, and ecological perspectives, it highlights the potential of urban ecosystems to promote sustainability and enhance human well-being, while emphasizing the importance of their conservation. It is hoped that the insights provided will not only enhance the management of Lake Eymir but also inspire broader efforts to value and protect natural resources in urban contexts.

CHAPTER 2

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

The conceptual framework forms the foundation of this study, providing a structured lens through which the complex interactions between ecosystems, their services, and human values can be analyzed. By defining key concepts and situating the research within theoretical and practical contexts, this chapter establishes the philosophical and methodological underpinnings necessary for a comprehensive understanding of ecosystem services and their valuation. The framework integrates perspectives from environmental economics, ethics, and ecosystem science to examine the interplay between ecological processes and human well-being.

Ecosystem services, encompassing provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services, are central to this framework. These services represent the tangible and intangible benefits derived from ecosystems, forming a bridge between ecological integrity and societal needs (MA, 2005a). To assess the value of these services, the study employs a Total Economic Value (TEV) approach, which captures both use and non-use values. This approach is further enriched by ethical considerations, exploring the instrumental and intrinsic worth of ecosystems. The inclusion of these dual perspectives acknowledges that ecosystems are not only economic assets but also entities with inherent value, irrespective of human use.

The theoretical underpinnings of this study draw upon widely recognized frameworks, including the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA) and the European Union's Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES). These frameworks provide standardized methodologies for identifying and

categorizing ecosystem services, facilitating consistency and comparability across studies (MA, 2005a; MA, 2005b; MA, 2005c; EEA, 2018). They also emphasize the importance of urban ecosystems, such as Lake Eymir, in contributing to both environmental sustainability and human quality of life.

This conceptual framework is further contextualized within the unique socio-cultural and ecological setting of Lake Eymir. As a multifunctional ecosystem surrounded by urban districts, Lake Eymir offers a range of services, from recreational opportunities and climate regulation to biodiversity conservation. However, these services are under increasing pressure from urbanization, pollution, and climate change. The study's framework not only aims to quantify the economic value of these services but also to highlight their cultural, ethical, and ecological significance.

By synthesizing insights from literature and established frameworks, this chapter provides a robust foundation for analyzing ecosystem services at Lake Eymir. It addresses critical gaps in existing research by integrating subjective perceptions with scientific valuation methods, thereby offering a nuanced perspective on the role of ecosystems in urban settings. The conceptual framework serves as the backbone of the study, guiding the subsequent analysis and ensuring its alignment with interdisciplinary methodologies.

2.2 Key Concepts

2.2.1 Ecosystem Services

Ecosystems are defined as dynamic complexes of plant, animal, and microorganism communities interacting with their non-living environment as a functional unit. This definition, formalized by the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (UN CBD), emphasizes ecosystems as critical providers of biodiversity and ecological functions essential for sustaining life on Earth (UN CBD, 1992, p. 4). The term “ecosystem” was first introduced by Tansley (1935, p. 299), who emphasized

the interconnectedness of biotic and abiotic components within ecological systems, providing a framework for understanding the holistic nature of ecological interactions.

Building on the concept of ecosystems, the term ecosystem services emerged to highlight the benefits that these systems provide to humans. The origins of the term can be traced back to the late 1970s and early 1980s, when researchers like Westman (1977) and Ehrlich and Ehrlich (1981) began articulating the importance of nature's contributions to society. The concept gained prominence with the work of Daily (1997), who provided a comprehensive framework for understanding and categorizing ecosystem services. This framework was later institutionalized in the landmark Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA), which categorized ecosystem services into four broad types (Figure 2.1), forming the foundation for modern valuation studies (MA, 2005a).

PROVISIONING SERVICES	REGULATING SERVICES	CULTURAL SERVICES
Products obtained from ecosystems	Benefits from regulation of ecosystem processes	Non-material benefits obtained from ecosystems
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy • Fibre • Fresh water • Seafood • Biomedical • Transportation • National defense • Genetic resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flood prevention • Climate regulation • Erosion control • Noise regulation • Pest and pathogen control • Water, and soil quality regulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational • Recreational • Heritage • Spiritual • Aesthetic
SUPPORTING SERVICES		
Services necessary for the production of all other services		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity maintenance • Soil formation • Nutrient recycling • Primary production • Water cycling 		

Figure 2.1: Categories of Ecosystem Services as Defined by the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA, 2005a). Adapted from the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005a, p. vi).

Ecosystem services represent the direct and indirect benefits derived from ecosystems, serving as the critical link between ecological processes and human well-being. The MA defines these services as:

- Provisioning services: Tangible outputs such as food, freshwater, and raw materials. At Lake Eymir, provisioning services include the availability of freshwater and the potential for food resources like fish, herbs, or other natural materials. These services are vital for human sustenance and local livelihoods, demonstrating direct human dependency on ecosystem goods (MA, 2005a).
- Regulating services: Functions that maintain environmental balance and stability, including climate regulation, carbon sequestration, and air quality maintenance. Lake Eymir’s wetlands and forests contribute significantly to

these processes, filtering air pollutants, mitigating flood risks, and storing carbon. Regulating services are particularly indispensable in urban ecosystems, where development pressures heighten the need for natural regulatory mechanisms (MA, 2005a).

- Cultural services: Non-material benefits such as recreational, aesthetic, and spiritual experiences. Lake Eymir serves as a recreational hub for Ankara, offering activities like hiking, birdwatching, and photography. It also enhances the cultural identity of the city, contributing to mental well-being, social cohesion, and tourism (MA, 2005a; TEEB, 2011).
- Supporting services: Foundational ecological processes, such as nutrient cycling, soil formation, and primary production, that underpin all other ecosystem services (MA, 2005a). These processes ensure ecosystem health and resilience, enabling the functioning of Lake Eymir's diverse ecosystems. Supporting services often operate over larger spatial and temporal scales, making them challenging to quantify but essential for sustaining life and biodiversity on Earth (MA 2005c).

The MA framework provides a systematic approach to identifying and valuing these services, emphasizing their interconnectedness and collective contributions to human well-being. This framework has been complemented by efforts such as the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES), which standardizes methodologies for integrating ecosystem services into economic and social planning (EEA, 2018). Together, these frameworks highlight the critical role of ecosystem services in addressing ecological, cultural, and economic dimensions, particularly in urban settings like Lake Eymir.

Recognizing and categorizing the ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir brings their importance in enhancing urban sustainability and societal well-being into attention. This study emphasizes that understanding these services is not only essential for conservation but also for fostering a deeper appreciation of the interdependencies between human systems and the natural environment.

2.2.1.1 Debates Surrounding the Ecosystem Services

The concept of ecosystem services, despite its widespread adoption, has not been without criticism. Philosophical, ecological, and methodological concerns have been raised about the framework's underlying assumptions and implications. One significant critique is that assigning services to ecosystems instrumentalizes nature, reducing the complexity of ecological processes to a set of human-centered benefits. Critics argue that this commodification of nature risks overshadowing its intrinsic value, potentially reducing conservation efforts to narrow economic calculations (McCauley, 2006, p. 28). This perspective emphasizes that the ethical importance of ecosystems may be neglected when their worth is viewed primarily through the lens of human utility. Furthermore, some ecological scholars express concern that although ecosystem services frameworks can be enlightening, they may lead us to overlook the complexity of ecosystems (Norgaard, 2010, p. 1220). These critiques highlight the tension between pragmatism and ecological complexity in ecosystem valuation.

Proponents of the ecosystem services framework, however, counter these criticisms by emphasizing its practical and integrative benefits, which do not invalidate or overshadow but rather complement ethical and ecological perspectives. A key advantage of the framework lies in its ability to bridge ecology and policy by translating ecological functions into economic terms. This pragmatic approach ensures that environmental considerations are integrated into decision-making processes across diverse sectors, including urban development, agriculture, and infrastructure planning. By assigning measurable economic value to ecosystem functions, the framework enhances the visibility of ecological contributions in arenas traditionally dominated by economic interests, thereby promoting informed and balanced policy-making (Costanza et al., 1997, p. 253).

Advocates also argue that the recognition of ecosystem services does not surpass intrinsic value but rather complements it. The framework provides an additional lens through which the importance of ecosystems can be communicated to diverse

stakeholders, including policymakers, businesses, and the general public. By quantifying benefits, the ecosystem services framework makes conservation efforts more accessible and persuasive, particularly to those less familiar with ecological or ethical arguments (SEPA, 2018). This dual perspective allows for a more inclusive discourse that integrates both instrumental and intrinsic values into conservation strategies.

Moreover, proponents stress the framework's ability to address ecological complexity through its holistic integration of provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services. Far from oversimplifying nature, the ecosystem services approach encourages a multifaceted understanding of ecosystems by considering their ecological, cultural, and economic dimensions simultaneously. This adaptability to complex ecological realities strengthens its applicability to diverse contexts, including urban and rural environments (TEEB, 2011, p. 11).

Another significant benefit of the ecosystem services framework is its potential to increase investment in conservation efforts. Assigning economic value to ecosystem services has proven to be an effective tool for mobilizing financial resources for biodiversity protection (Polasky et al., 2014). Ecosystem services framework's capacity to translate ecological benefits into economic terms may not only strengthen conservation funding but also enable fostering cross-sectoral collaborations for sustainable development (Daily, 1997).

In summary, while criticisms of the ecosystem services framework raise valid philosophical and methodological concerns, its practical applications and integrative capacity offer compelling counterarguments. By bridging ecological science and policy, complementing intrinsic value, addressing ecological complexity, and mobilizing conservation investments, the framework provides a robust and versatile tool for promoting sustainability in both urban and natural landscapes.

2.2.2 Total Economic Value (TEV) Framework

The Total Economic Value (TEV) framework is a foundational concept in environmental economics, developed to capture the full range of values that ecosystems provide to human well-being. The term was developed and popularized by environmental economists David Pearce and R. Kerry Turner in the early 1990s, who emphasized the need to incorporate both use and non-use values into environmental decision-making. TEV provides a comprehensive lens through which the multifaceted benefits of natural systems can be systematically evaluated, facilitating better-informed conservation and policy strategies (Pearce and Turner, 1989). Its relevance to ecosystem valuation lies in its ability to encompass both tangible and intangible benefits, ensuring that the intrinsic worth of ecosystems is not overlooked in economic assessments.

The Total Economic Value (TEV) framework, as illustrated in Figure 2.2, categorizes these values to encapsulate the full spectrum of ecosystem contributions, from tangible benefits like recreation and provisioning services to more abstract notions such as the value of preserving nature for future generations. This framework offers a structured approach to ecosystem valuation, enabling more effective conservation strategies and policy-making by highlighting both the visible and hidden benefits ecosystems provide.

ECONOMIC VALUE TYPOLOGIES: TOTAL ECONOMIC VALUE (TEV)

$$\text{Total Willingness to Pay (TWP)} = \text{Use Value} + \text{Option Value} + \text{Nonuse Value}$$

Figure 2.2: Total Economic Value (TEV) Framework and its Components. Adapted from Pearce and Turner (1989).

2.2.2.1 Use Values

Direct use values represent benefits derived from direct interaction with the ecosystem, such as recreational activities, tourism, and educational opportunities (Pearce and Turner, 1989). For Lake Eymir, these include cycling, birdwatching, photography, and fishing, all of which contribute to the lake's economic and social significance. These activities may enhance physical and mental well-being, foster community engagement, and provide aesthetic enjoyment, making them an essential component of the lake's overall value.

Indirect use values pertain to ecosystem functions that indirectly support human well-being, such as climate regulation and water purification (Pearce and Turner, 1989). Lake Eymir consists of wetlands and surrounded by forests which play a crucial role in maintaining air and water quality, sequestering carbon, and reducing urban heat island effects. These indirect benefits often remain undervalued due to their less visible nature, but they are critical for ensuring long-term ecological and societal resilience.

2.2.2.2 Non-Use Values

Existence value refers to the value people derive from knowing that an ecosystem exists, even if they do not directly benefit from it (Pearce and Turner, 1989). For Lake Eymir, individuals who have never visited the lake may still value its role as a vital habitat for biodiversity and a symbol of Ankara's natural heritage.

Bequest value emphasizes the importance of preserving the ecosystem so that future generations can benefit from its ecological and cultural functions (Pearce and Turner, 1989). Similarly, Lake Eymir's value as a legacy for both current and future residents of Ankara, highlights the critical need for sustainable management practices that safeguard its health and contributions.

Option value reflects the value of maintaining the potential for future use, even if those uses are currently unrealized (Arrow and Fisher, 1974). This includes preserving the lake's capacity to support emerging recreational, scientific, or ecological functions in response to changing societal needs.

2.2.2.3 TEV in the Context of Lake Eymir

The TEV framework is particularly relevant to the valuation of Lake Eymir, as it enables a holistic assessment of the lake's contributions. In this study, we apply the TEV framework through two complementary methods: the i-Tree Canopy analysis and a willingness-to-pay (WTP) survey. The i-Tree Canopy tool quantifies regulating and supporting services including air quality and hydrological benefits, which correspond to indirect use values. By mapping land cover and estimating ecosystem functions, the tool provides measurable indicators of the lake's ecological and economic significance.

The WTP survey complements this analysis by capturing both use and non-use values through direct engagement with stakeholders. Respondents rated their willingness to financially contribute to the protection of Lake Eymir, highlighting its

importance as a recreational and cultural hub while also reflecting broader societal priorities, such as biodiversity conservation and climate regulation. This approach ensures that both tangible and intangible benefits are incorporated into the valuation, aligning with the TEV framework's comprehensive scope.

2.2.2.4 Significance of TEV for Policy and Conservation

By integrating both use and non-use values, the TEV framework ensures that ecosystem assessments reflect the full spectrum of benefits provided by natural systems. This holistic approach strengthens the rationale for conservation investments, as it demonstrates the multifaceted contributions of ecosystems like Lake Eymir to human well-being and ecological stability. For policymakers, TEV serves as a critical tool for justifying funding allocations, shaping urban planning strategies, and promoting sustainable development initiatives.

In the case of Lake Eymir, the TEV framework reinforces the necessity of preserving its diverse functions and services, not only for the current generation but also for future ones. By quantifying these values, this study contributes to the broader discourse on ecosystem service valuation, providing a robust foundation for evidence-based decision-making and sustainable management practices.

2.2.3 Public Goods, Excludability, and the Economic Nature of Lake Eymir

In economic theory, goods are typically classified based on their characteristics of rivalry and excludability, resulting in categories such as private goods, public goods, common-pool resources, and club goods. A pure public good is both non-rivalrous and non-excludable, meaning that one individual's use does not reduce availability to others, and it is not feasible to exclude anyone from access (Varian, 1992). However, many real-world goods, especially environmental and recreational resources, do not fit neatly into this binary classification.

Such goods are often referred to as mixed goods, which may exhibit partial excludability and/or partial rivalry. Lake Eymir is a clear example of this category. While its recreational and ecological benefits can be enjoyed by multiple individuals simultaneously under normal conditions (i.e., it is largely non-rival), excessive visitation can lead to congestion and diminished user experience, indicating partial rivalry. Additionally, access to the area is regulated by Middle East Technical University (METU), making it partially excludable. This classification distinguishes it from both private goods and pure public goods and places it within a hybrid category that reflects its complex use dynamics.

Some scholars further refine this classification by introducing the concept of club goods—resources that are non-rival but excludable, often through membership or user fees (Buchanan, 1965). While Lake Eymir shares certain features with club goods, such as regulated access, the absence of a formal pricing or membership structure suggests that the broader label of mixed good is more appropriate in this context.

Recognizing Lake Eymir as a mixed good has important implications for environmental valuation. Its partial excludability makes it amenable to non-market valuation techniques, particularly stated preference methods such as Willingness to Pay (WTP). Unlike pure public goods, where free-rider problems may undermine valuation accuracy, mixed goods provide a more realistic basis for assessing individual preferences and contributions toward conservation (Carson & Groves, 2007).

This classification also supports the application of the Total Economic Value (TEV) framework. The ability to regulate access and observe user interactions allows for the measurement of both use and non-use values in a policy-relevant way. It ensures that economic instruments and conservation strategies can be grounded in both empirical observation and theoretical coherence.

2.2.4 Environmental Ethics Context: Value Typologies in Environmental Ethics and Philosophy

Environmental ethics is a branch of philosophy that explores the moral relationship between humans and the natural world, addressing the foundational principles that guide conservation and sustainability efforts. Central to this discipline are the concepts of intrinsic value and instrumental value, which underpin ethical arguments for environmental protection. These values not only provide a moral and philosophical basis for conservation but also serve as practical tools for evaluating human responsibilities toward ecosystems and biological diversity. A nuanced understanding of these values, along with their subcategories (Figure 2.3), enhances the ability to develop ethical and actionable approaches to environmental conservation and decision-making.

Figure 2.3: Value Typologies in Environmental Ethics and Philosophy

Before moving forward with the subcategories, the two main categories in environmental ethics and philosophy will be elaborated upon: intrinsic value and instrumental value, which form a central distinction in this field.

2.2.4.1 Intrinsic Value

Intrinsic value refers to the inherent worth that something possesses simply by virtue of its existence. It is value that is independent of any utility or benefit the entity might provide to humans or other beings. When applied to nature, this perspective holds that natural entities—such as animals, plants, ecosystems, or even the Earth as a whole—have moral worth in themselves. Advocates of intrinsic value in environmental ethics argue that nature should be respected, preserved, and protected not merely because of what it can do for us, but because it has value in its own right. This position often aligns with deep ecology, biocentrism, or ecocentrism, where the moral community is expanded beyond human beings to include all living organisms or even entire ecosystems.

Callicott (1985) defines intrinsic value as value that something has in itself, for its own sake, rather than for the sake of something else (i.e., extrinsically). According to him, something possesses intrinsic value when it is considered valuable in and of itself, independently of any usefulness it might have in serving another purpose. In the environmental context, he argues that natural entities—such as animals, plants, and ecosystems—possess intrinsic value independent of their utility to humans. Callicott (1985) builds on Aldo Leopold's *land ethic* (1949), extending moral consideration to the biotic community as a whole. He argues that this broader community—not just individual sentient beings—can be considered intrinsically valuable.

Philosopher Holmes Rolston III (1988) argues that intrinsic value is not just about a thing's value in relation to human interests or utility. Instead, he asserts that nature has an inherent value in its own right because of its ecological processes, biological diversity, and evolutionary development. He emphasizes that value is not just subjective or dependent on human perception but is part of the world's inherent structure and processes. According to Rolston (1988), nature's value exists because of its "teleological" nature—the fact that it has goals, directions, and ends in its

natural processes. In his view, the teleological order of nature itself provides the basis for its intrinsic value.

Similarly, according to Paul W. Taylor (1986), each living organism is a "teleological center of life," meaning it has its own inherent purpose or goal to fulfill, which is intrinsic to its biological nature. This principle leads to biocentric egalitarianism, which asserts that all organisms, regardless of species, deserve equal moral consideration (Taylor, 1986).

Philosophers such as Arne Næss (1973) introduces the concept of *deep ecology*, which asserts that nature has intrinsic value—that is, it has value in itself, independent of any usefulness to humans. This stands in contrast to the instrumental value perspective of *shallow ecology*. He argues that the well-being and flourishing of both human and nonhuman life on Earth hold value in themselves, independent of any utility they may serve human purposes (Næss, 1973).

2.2.4.2 Instrumental Value

Instrumental value is assigned to something based on its usefulness in achieving a desired end or fulfilling a particular function. It focuses on the utility or benefits derived from an entity. In the environmental context, these include tangible and intangible benefits such as food, water, aesthetic enjoyment, and ecosystem services. From this viewpoint, nature is valuable because of the resources, services, and benefits it provides to humans. Those who adopt an instrumental stance typically emphasize conservation and sustainable use, not necessarily out of concern for nature itself, but to ensure the continued well-being and prosperity of human societies. Therefore, instrumental value is often linked to anthropocentric perspectives, where the environment is valued for its capacity to fulfill human needs. Lake Eymir's instrumental value is evident in its recreational functions, urban sustainability contributions, and ecosystem services like climate regulation and water purification.

2.2.4.3 Subcategories of Intrinsic and Instrumental Value

In the literature, intrinsic and instrumental values are further categorized into distinct typologies. For the purposes of this thesis, Eugene C. Hargrove's (1992) classification is adopted: "(i) non-anthropocentric instrumental value, (ii) anthropocentric instrumental value, (iii) non-anthropocentric intrinsic value, and (iv) anthropocentric intrinsic value" (p. 186).

2.2.4.3.1 Anthropocentric and Non-Anthropocentric Intrinsic Value

Intrinsic value concept has been further delineated into two subcategories:

Anthropocentric intrinsic value can be briefly defined as an intrinsic value attributed to something by humans. The human who attributes the value assigns to the entity a value that stems from the entity itself—valuing it for its own sake, for its own good, and because of its own essence. Hargrove (1992) describes anthropocentric intrinsic value culturally, as a value attributed by humans. Referring to Taylor (1984) as holding the closest perspective to his own, Hargrove notes that if something is attributed intrinsic value by humans, then that thing is considered worthy of protection and preservation simply because it exists as an entity in itself. From a moral standpoint, intrinsic value also imposes negative duties such as not harming, not destroying, and not exploiting (p. 189).

Non-anthropocentric intrinsic value, on the other hand, is an objective value that is inherent to a thing itself but independent of any value ascribed to it by a valuer. According to Rolston (1988), a representative of non-anthropocentric objective intrinsic value, the value of an organism lies in its own good, the value of nature in its beauty, and the value of an ecosystem in its systemic nature. According to Callicott (1985), a representative of subjective non-anthropocentric intrinsic value, if a person realizes that they are "one" with nature, then—since they have intrinsic value themselves—they can also come to understand that nature has intrinsic value as well. Hargrove (1992) argues that the main aim of advocates of non-

anthropocentric intrinsic value is to establish rules of a right-like, constitutive nature as a strong counterpoint to anthropocentric instrumental value (p.186).

Some other philosophers argued that intrinsic value has varieties. John O'Neill (1992) identifies three distinct senses of intrinsic value in environmental ethics. First type of intrinsic value refers to non-instrumental value, meaning something is valuable as an end in itself, not merely for its utility—this is the sense most commonly used by environmental ethicists, such as in deep ecology. Second, sense of intrinsic value follows the “Moorean sense”, where value depends solely on an entity’s intrinsic (non-relational) properties. The third intrinsic value denotes objective value, which exists independently of any human valuers. O’Neill further distinguishes between weak and strong versions of objectivity and argues that recognizing non-human entities as possessing intrinsic value in this third sense does not necessarily lead to moral obligations, but provides a foundation for ethical consideration of nature beyond human-centered frameworks.

Hargrove (1992) adds nuance by proposing "weak anthropocentric intrinsic value," which he defines as a form of intrinsic value that originates from a human perspective but is not merely instrumental. Unlike instrumental value, which is based on utility, weak anthropocentric intrinsic value refers to things that humans value for their own sake—such as natural beauty, cultural heritage, or emotional attachment—without reducing them to their usefulness. Hargrove argues that this form of valuing is essential for environmental ethics, particularly because it allows moral consideration for non-living entities which are excluded by non-anthropocentric theories focused only on living beings with a good of their own. He emphasizes that anthropocentric and non-anthropocentric values are not necessarily in conflict but can be complementary, and that weak anthropocentrism provides a realistic and culturally grounded basis for environmental concern. As he explains, “not all anthropocentric valuing is instrumental” (Hargrove, 1992, p. 201), and only anthropocentric intrinsic value can be applied to nonliving natural objects (p. 193).

2.2.4.3.2 Anthropocentric and Non-Anthropocentric Instrumental Value

Instrumental value is rooted in the utility or benefits derived from an entity. This value is further divided into two sub-categories which are:

Anthropocentric instrumental value: refers to the value attributed to nature or the environment based on the benefits it provides to humans. In other words, the products, services, and advantages that people derive from nature carry anthropocentric instrumental value. These values are easily observable, justifiable, and can be demonstrated through scientific research (Hargrove, 1992). Anthropocentric instrumental value encompasses both use values (direct use, indirect use, and option use) and non-use values (existence value, altruistic value, and bequest value), which fall within the scope of the concept of Total Economic Value commonly discussed in the ecosystem services valuation literature (Turner *et al.*, 2003).

Non-anthropocentric instrumental value, by contrast, refers to a category of value that arises from the instrumental relationships among the non-human components of nature— independent of any human interests. This type of value can also be readily demonstrated through scientific research (Hargrove, 1992). As an example of this value typology, Sol and Yakar (2023) cite the instrumental relationship between many symbiotic organisms in nature, such as the pollination interaction between bees and flowers. In this relationship, the bee has instrumental value for the flower, and the flower for the bee, regardless of any benefit to humans—meaning this value relationship exists even in the absence of human presence. They further argue that not only mutually beneficial interactions but also relationships where one party benefits at the expense of the other—such as a predator feeding on its prey—can be considered within the scope of non-anthropocentric instrumental value (Sol and Yakar, 2023).

2.2.4.4 The Ethical Debate: Intrinsic vs. Instrumental Value

The distinction between intrinsic and instrumental values has sparked significant debate in environmental ethics. Perhaps it is best to begin by asking why philosophers turned to the concept of intrinsic value in the first place, and what role it plays. According to Bryan Norton (1992), intrinsic value is considered necessary by philosophers who aim to establish environmental ethics as a field independent from human ethics.

The tension between these two perspectives—valuing nature for what it *is* versus what it *does*—is at the heart of many debates in environmental ethics. While the intrinsic value view promotes a moral obligation to protect nature regardless of human interests, the instrumental value view underscores nature’s role in supporting human life and flourishing. Importantly, some contemporary environmental thinkers and policymakers argue for a pluralistic approach, recognizing that both types of value can coexist and inform more holistic and effective environmental strategies.

Despite its ethical appeal, intrinsic value has faced criticism on both philosophical and practical grounds. Anthony Weston (1992) critiques the concept of intrinsic value for being overly abstract, self-sufficient, and disconnected from context, making it poorly suited for environmental ethics. He argues that this focus overlooks immediate, everyday values in nature—like birdsong or seasonal change—and reduces rich ecological relationships to isolated “ends.” Instead, he advocates for an ethics grounded in “immediate values” and “values-as-parts-of-patterns,” emphasizing relational, contextual, and holistic understandings of value.

J. Baird Callicott is a prominent proponent of intrinsic value in environmental ethics, advocating for a non-anthropocentric framework that recognizes the moral worth of nature independent of its utility to humans. Building on Aldo Leopold’s land ethic, Callicott (1985) argues that moral consideration should be extended to the biotic community as a whole—including animals, plants, species, and ecosystems. To his defense, a central task of environmental ethics is to construct an adequate theory of

intrinsic value for non-human entities and ecological wholes, proposing that different components of nature may possess varying degrees of intrinsic value depending on their ecological roles (Callicott, 1984, 1985). This holistic and eco-centric approach challenges anthropocentric value systems and affirms the need to respect and protect nature not just for human benefit but for its own sake.

As a proponent of weak anthropocentric intrinsic value, Hargrove (1992) argues that valuing nature for its own sake—from a human perspective—can foster meaningful moral obligations to protect it. This form of valuing resists reducing nature solely to its instrumental utility and instead recognizes aesthetic, cultural, and emotional attachments as legitimate grounds for conservation. Hargrove defends this approach as both more realistic and ethically powerful than abstract, objective theories or purely economic frameworks.

Conversely, critics of intrinsic value highlight its abstract nature, questioning its practical applicability in policy and decision-making. Bryan Norton (1992) advocates for a pragmatic approach, suggesting that instrumental value can serve as a more accessible and actionable basis for environmental ethics. Norton's perspective aligns with the idea that integrating ecological concerns into economic frameworks makes conservation efforts more feasible in contemporary societal contexts.

In summary, the concept of intrinsic value is not without controversy. Philosophers differ on whether intrinsic value can truly be attributed to non-human entities independently of human perspectives. Some argue that any attempt to assign value—whether intrinsic or instrumental—is ultimately shaped by human cognition and cultural frameworks. This leads to a tension: while intrinsic value is meant to move environmental ethics beyond anthropocentrism, it may still rely on human-centered assumptions. The debate, therefore, shifts toward whether value can exist independently of valuers, or whether environmental ethics should embrace a more relational or contextual understanding of value instead.

The dichotomy between instrumental and intrinsic values is particularly relevant to ecosystem service valuation, where frameworks like the TEV attempt to bridge ethical principles with economic realities. Instrumental value underpins methods such as the i-Tree Canopy analysis, which quantifies regulating and supporting Ecosystem Services. These assessments align with the anthropocentric focus of instrumental value, translating ecosystem functions into measurable economic benefits that inform policy and resource allocation.

While instrumental value is useful and practical, intrinsic value is integral to the cultural and ethical dimensions of ecosystem service valuation. For instance, the willingness-to-pay (WTP) survey conducted in this study captures non-use values, such as existence and bequest values, which differ in their underlying motivations. Existence value reflects an intrinsic appreciation of Lake Eymir's continued existence, independent of its utility to humans, yet indirectly contributes to preserving it for future generations. Conversely, bequest value represents an instrumental motivation, focused on the benefits future human generations may derive from its preservation. This distinction illustrates how both intrinsic and instrumental values can operate simultaneously, enriching the discourse on sustainable management.

2.2.4.5 Integrating Instrumental and Intrinsic Values in Environmental Ethics

The debate surrounding instrumental and intrinsic values finds resolution in frameworks that integrate both perspectives, particularly in the context of environmental decision-making and ecosystem service valuation. Sol and Yakar (2023) present a compelling argument that instrumental value, when reinterpreted within a broader epistemic framework, can fulfill many of the justificatory roles traditionally associated with intrinsic value. They emphasize that while intrinsic value provides a robust moral foundation for environmental ethics, the ontological

simplicity and practical relevance of instrumental value make it indispensable in addressing real-world environmental challenges (Sol & Yakar, 2023, p. 48).

This dual approach is particularly significant in the valuation of ecosystem services, where instrumental value serves as a tool to quantify and communicate the tangible and intangible benefits provided by ecosystems. By doing so, instrumental value does not negate intrinsic worth but instead complements it, creating a balanced framework that respects both ethical principles and practical exigencies. Supporting this view, Beardsley (1965) argues that "value" can be treated as a genus under which intrinsic and instrumental values are two distinct grounds of evaluation, rather than entirely separate concepts (p. 6). Although Beardsley questions whether intrinsic value is truly meaningful or useful, he recognizes that instrumental value can stand on its own in ethical thinking. In environmental contexts, this means we can use instrumental measures—like valuing ecosystem services—without denying the moral importance people may also attach to nature. For Beardsley, focusing on practical, context-based judgments is a more realistic and effective way to approach value.

Incorporating these perspectives into ecosystem service valuation ensures that conservation efforts are both ethically sound and economically actionable. For instance, the Total Economic Value (TEV) framework and the ecosystem services classification employed in this study effectively operationalize instrumental value while remaining mindful of the intrinsic significance of ecosystems like Lake Eymir. This integrated approach highlights the ethical and practical importance of preserving ecological systems for present and future generations.

The integration of instrumental and intrinsic values offers a balanced framework for addressing contemporary environmental challenges. By combining the ethical insights of intrinsic value with the practical applicability of instrumental value, this thesis contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of ecosystem valuation. This interdisciplinary approach aligns with Norton's (1992) call for epistemological pluralism, fostering a dialogue between diverse ethical, ecological, and economic

perspectives. In the context of Lake Eymir, such an approach ensures that both the tangible and intangible benefits of the ecosystem are recognized and preserved, advancing sustainability and societal well-being.

2.2.4.6 Relevance of Ethics to Ecosystem Service Valuation

In the context of Lake Eymir, the interplay between intrinsic and instrumental values highlights the multifaceted significance of ecosystems. The lake's biological diversity, cultural importance, and ecological functions reflect its intrinsic value, establishing its conservation as an ethical necessity. This value demonstrates the inherent worth of Lake Eymir's natural elements, independent of their direct utility to humans. At the same time, the lake's instrumental value, demonstrated through its ecosystem services such as air quality maintenance, water regulation, and recreational opportunities, provides a practical and measurable rationale for its preservation. These dual perspectives not only enrich ethical discussions but also lay a robust foundation for informed policymaking and active community engagement.

By employing frameworks such as the Total Economic Value (TEV) and ecosystem services classification, this study effectively bridges the divide between philosophical ideals and real-world applications. The TEV framework and ecosystem services categorization offer structured methodologies to evaluate and integrate intrinsic and instrumental considerations. Such holistic approaches ensure that conservation strategies are both ethically sound and economically viable, reflecting the multidimensional value of ecosystems.

In this study, the subcategories of instrumental and intrinsic values are directly relevant to the valuation of Lake Eymir's ecosystem services. The i-Tree Canopy analysis primarily captures anthropocentric instrumental values by quantifying tangible benefits like carbon sequestration, air pollution prevention and hydrological benefit estimates. Conversely, the Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) survey expands the scope by addressing both anthropocentric and non-anthropocentric values,

encompassing cultural, recreational, and ethical motivations for preserving the lake. These complementary methods underscore the importance of integrating diverse value perspectives to ensure comprehensive and balanced conservation efforts.

This thesis adopts a nuanced approach, integrating both instrumental and intrinsic values to frame ecosystem service valuation comprehensively. While instrumental value offers a pragmatic pathway for economic and policy integration, intrinsic value highlights the ethical imperative to preserve ecosystems like Lake Eymir for their inherent worth. The study therefore advocates for a balanced approach that upholds ecological integrity while also considering the needs of society.

2.2.5 Environmental Economics Context: Principles of non-Market Valuation

Environmental economics addresses the challenge of quantifying the value of environmental goods and services that are not traded in formal markets. Scholars like Pearce and Turner, (1989) emphasize the necessity of valuing both market and non-market benefits of ecosystems to fully understand their total economic value. Non-market valuation methods are critical for capturing the total economic value of ecosystems, which includes both tangible and intangible benefits (Pearce and Turner, 1989). These methods enable the integration of ecological and societal benefits into policy and decision-making processes, bridging the gap between ecological significance and economic considerations (TEEB, 2011; Costanza et al., 1997).

Mitchell and Carson (1989) categorized valuation techniques based on the data source used, distinguishing between those derived from individuals' actual market behavior and those obtained from their responses to hypothetical market scenario questions. Consequently, valuation models can be classified into two main categories: Revealed Preference (RP) and Stated Preference (SP) methods.

2.2.5.1 Revealed Preference (RP) Methods

Revealed preference methods (Mitchel and Carson, 1989) infer economic values by analyzing actual behaviors in existing markets, using observable data to quantify environmental attributes indirectly. These methods are particularly useful for estimating use values, focusing on tangible benefits that arise from interactions with ecosystems.

One prominent approach is *Hedonic Pricing*, which examines how environmental characteristics, such as clean air, water quality, or scenic views, influence property values. For example, homes located near a park or with access to a water body often command higher market prices, reflecting the value buyers assign to these environmental amenities. Another widely used technique is the *Travel Cost Method*, which estimates the recreational value of natural areas by analyzing the travel expenses incurred by visitors. This approach helps quantify the economic significance of destinations like national parks, lakes, or forests. *Averting Behavior* is another revealed preference method, measuring how individuals alter their behavior or incur costs to mitigate environmental risks, such as installing water filters to address polluted water supplies (OECD, 2018).

While these methods are effective in capturing use values, they have notable limitations (NRC, 2005). By focusing primarily on market-related activities, they may overlook non-use values such as existence value, which is the inherent worth of an ecosystem, or bequest value, which reflects the importance of preserving ecosystems for future generations (NRC, 2005). These non-use values, although intangible, are critical components of comprehensive environmental valuation frameworks.

In sum, revealed preference methods provide valuable insights into the economic significance of environmental attributes through observable market behaviors. However, their scope is inherently limited to activities directly tied to existing

markets, underscoring the importance of complementary approaches that account for the broader spectrum of ecosystem values.

2.2.5.2 Stated Preference (SP) Methods

Stated preference methods (Mitchel and Carson, 1989) offer a direct means of eliciting values from individuals by employing surveys or hypothetical scenarios. Unlike revealed preference methods, which rely on observable behaviors in markets, stated preference approaches are uniquely suited to capturing non-use values that are not associated with market transactions. This makes them an essential tool for assessing the broader range of benefits ecosystems provide, including those that are intangible or indirectly experienced.

One of the most widely used stated preference methods is the *Contingent Valuation Method (CVM)* (Mitchel and Carson, 1989). This approach involves asking participants to state their willingness to pay (WTP) for specific environmental goods or services (Carson and Hanemann, 2005). For instance, respondents may be asked how much they would be willing to contribute to preserve biodiversity, reduce air pollution, or prevent the degradation of a natural area. Choice Modeling is a stated preference method where individuals are presented with hypothetical scenarios characterized by varying attributes, enabling the estimation of values for individual components of environmental goods (Hanley & Barbier, 2009).

Stated preference methods address the limitations of revealed preferences by incorporating both tangible and intangible benefits into environmental valuation. This capacity to encompass use and non-use values makes stated preference approaches indispensable for comprehensive assessments of ecosystem services and their contributions to societal well-being (OECD, 2018). By combining hypothetical scenarios with participant insights, these methods bridge the gap between ecological processes and human values, offering a holistic framework for conservation and resource management.

Stated preference methods, such as CVM and choice modeling, are unique in their ability to estimate non-use values, which are often significant components of TEV for ecosystems like Lake Eymir. These methods enable researchers to capture ethical and cultural values, such as the importance of preserving the lake for future generations or its existence value. By eliciting preferences through structured surveys, stated preference methods ensure that all dimensions of value—use, non-use, and option—are accounted for, providing a comprehensive framework for ecosystem valuation.

2.2.5.3 Relevance to Ecosystem Service Valuation

The valuation methods employed in this study, including CVM and ES classifications, align with international best practices in environmental economics. The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA) framework categorizes ecosystem services into provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services, offering a structured lens for identifying and valuing these benefits (MA, 2005a). Similarly, the Total Economic Value (TEV) framework integrates use and non-use values (Pearce and Turner 1989), providing a comprehensive understanding of ecosystems like Lake Eymir.

The findings of this study underscore the dual importance of ethical and economic considerations in conservation. The valuation of Lake Eymir's ecosystem services demonstrates how instrumental value can complement intrinsic value, creating a balanced framework for conservation efforts (Sol & Yakar, 2023). For example, quantifying an array of regulating services through the i-Tree Canopy analysis provides actionable data for policymakers. Similarly, the WTP survey captures both ethical motivations and economic willingness to invest in the lake's preservation, reflecting its multifaceted significance.

By employing these valuation methods, this study contributes to a growing body of research that demonstrates the economic, ethical, and ecological importance of

preserving natural assets. The integration of non-market valuation techniques with ethical frameworks ensures that conservation strategies are both economically viable and ethically sound, addressing the needs of present and future generations.

2.2.5.4 Application to This Study

The contingent valuation method (CVM) is a widely used stated preference technique for estimating the value of non-market goods, particularly in environmental contexts. CVM involves directly asking individuals their willingness to pay (WTP) for specific environmental benefits or their willingness to accept compensation for the loss of such benefits. This method is flexible and can capture the total economic value of ecosystems by including both use and non-use values (Carson, 2012).

In this study, CVM was applied to Lake Eymir to assess its economic value through a carefully structured WTP survey. The hypothetical scenario presented in the survey emphasized that the payment (an entry fee as a payment vehicle) would be exclusively used for the conservation of Lake Eymir, addressing potential biases such as protest zeros. By doing so, this study ensures that the values captured through CVM reflect the respondents' true preferences for preserving the lake's ecosystem services.

The WTP survey results, combined with ecosystem services ratings, provide a robust dataset for analyzing the economic value of Lake Eymir. By quantifying respondents' willingness to contribute financially and their prioritization of various ecosystem services, this approach bridges the gap between subjective preferences and objective valuation. This dual approach enhances the study's capacity to address both anthropocentric instrumental values (e.g., recreational opportunities and climate regulation) and ethical considerations tied to non-anthropocentric intrinsic values.

These methodologies provide a framework for evaluating Lake Eymir's ecosystem services. The i-Tree Canopy analysis aligns with revealed preference methods by

quantifying tangible ecosystem services like carbon storage and flood mitigation. Conversely, the Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) survey employs a stated preference approach to capture both use and non-use values, encompassing ethical and cultural considerations alongside direct benefits.

By integrating these methods, the study offers a robust and holistic valuation of Lake Eymir, bridging ecological insights with societal preferences. The dual application of revealed and stated preferences ensures that the study captures the multidimensional value of the lake, informing conservation strategies that are both ethically grounded and economically viable.

2.3 Case Study Area: Lake Eymir

Lake Eymir, located approximately 20 kilometers south of Ankara's city center within the Gölbaşı district, exemplifies the multifaceted contributions of ecosystems in urban settings. Spanning 108.8 hectares and featuring an S-shaped configuration, the lake is a critical ecological and cultural asset for the region. Historically, this area was arid and devoid of significant vegetation until it became part of the Middle East Technical University (METU) campus in 1956. Under the leadership of METU's first rector, Kemal Kurdaş, large-scale afforestation transformed the landscape into a thriving ecological zone. This remarkable achievement garnered international recognition, culminating in the Aga Khan Award for Architecture in 1995 (Dalaklı, 2019).

Ecologically, Lake Eymir forms part of a dual lake system with Lake Mogan, located approximately three kilometers to the southwest. The primary inflow to Lake Eymir is channeled from Lake Mogan, with excess water discharged into the River İmrahor. This interconnected system supports a diverse array of flora and fauna, including endemic plants, aquatic life, and avifauna. Notable bird species documented around the lake include the Eurasian Scops Owl (*Otus scops*), Little Egret (*Egretta garzetta*), and Great Cormorant (*Phalacrocorax carbo*), highlighting the lake's significance as a habitat for both resident and migratory bird species (Göçer, 2018, p. iv). The

aquatic ecosystem also sustains fish species such as Pike (*Esox lucius*), Tench (*Tinca tinca*), and Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), with Tench comprising 89% of the total fish biomass (Tüzün et al., 2003). Vegetation, including emergent species like common reed (*Phragmites australis*) and submerged plants such as *Potamogeton pectinatus*, further enhances the lake's ecological complexity (EKOSAM, 2019).

Over decades, Lake Eymir has faced significant environmental challenges. From the 1970s onward, nutrient loading from untreated sewage effluent caused severe eutrophication, transforming the lake from a clear, submerged plant-dominated state to a turbid, algae-dominated one. Restoration efforts began in 1995 with the implementation of effluent diversion and biomanipulation techniques, such as substantial fish removal, which successfully improved water clarity and restored ecological balance (Tüzün et al., 2003). Despite these improvements, recent environmental stressors, including pollution and fish mortality events, underline the ongoing need for adaptive management strategies (EKOSAM, 2019).

2.3.1 Ecosystem Services and Framework Application

Lake Eymir provides a broad spectrum of provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services that are vital for ecological sustainability and societal well-being. Provisioning services include freshwater availability and potential food resources, such as fish, which directly benefit the local community. Regulating services, such as water regulation, climate regulation, pollination, and disease and pest control, address critical urban environmental challenges, enhancing the resilience of Ankara's urban ecosystem. Cultural services include recreational opportunities, aesthetic value, and the lake's role in fostering Ankara's cultural identity. Supporting services, like nutrient cycling, soil formation, and biodiversity maintenance, underpin these benefits, ensuring the long-term sustainability of the lake's ecosystems (MA 2005b).

To systematically evaluate these ecosystem services, this study employs frameworks such as the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA) and the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES). The MA categorization provides a structured lens for analyzing provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting services, while CICES refines these categories to facilitate integration into economic and policy analyses. Together, these frameworks enable consistent and rigorous assessments that are comparable across global studies (EEA, 2018).

2.3.2 Implications for Urban Sustainability and Policy

Quantifying the ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir offers critical insights for urban sustainability and conservation policy. For example, the valuation of regulating services, such as air purification and flood control, indicates their economic and societal significance, providing a rationale for increased investment in natural infrastructure. Similarly, emphasizing cultural services, including recreational and educational opportunities, can foster greater public engagement and appreciation, building a strong foundation for long-term conservation efforts.

Lake Eymir's case demonstrates how the integration of ecosystem service valuation into urban planning frameworks can bridge ecological science and socio-economic priorities. Protecting and enhancing the lake's ecosystem services is not merely an ecological necessity but also a strategic investment in the well-being and resilience of urban communities. By recognizing the multifaceted contributions of Lake Eymir, this study provides a model for aligning conservation strategies with societal needs and urban sustainability goals.

CHAPTER 3

APPLICATION OF i-TREE CANOPY FOR ECOSYSTEM SERVICES VALUATION—THE CASE OF EYMIR LAKE

3.1 Introduction to i-Tree Canopy Tool

The valuation of ecosystem services plays a crucial role in promoting sustainable urban planning and environmental management. Tools like i-Tree Canopy offer an accessible and effective platform for quantifying the benefits provided by urban forests and green spaces using remote sensing and statistical sampling techniques. Initially conceptualized in the 1990s, the i-Tree program was officially launched in 2006 to streamline urban forestry assessments (Nowak, 2021, pp. 1-2). The i-Tree Canopy tool, developed in cooperation with the USDA Forest Service and the Davey Tree Expert Company, enables users to generate statistically valid estimates of tree and other land cover types through photo-interpretation of aerial imagery (Nowak, 2021, pp. 6, 9). This approach facilitates quick and cost-effective landscape evaluations.

The working principle of the tool is quite straightforward. i-Tree Canopy employs a random sampling methodology, allowing users to classify land cover types at specific points within a defined area, thereby generating statistically reliable estimates of canopy cover and associated ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration and air pollution removal (Nowak & Greenfield, 2012; i-Tree Tools, n.d.). Users can upload aerial imagery and classify random points on the map according to predefined land cover categories (e.g., tree, grass, impervious surfaces). These classifications are then linked to ecosystem service values, enabling estimates of benefits such as avoided runoff, pollution removal, and carbon storage (Nowak et al., 2014; i-Tree Tools, n.d.). By employing statistical sampling, the tool generates

results with minimal bias and reasonable accuracy, making it suitable for both small-scale and large-scale studies (Nowak & Greenfield, 2012).

Unlike field-based inventories, which can be labor-intensive and costly, i-Tree Canopy offers an efficient alternative that requires limited technical expertise (Nowak, 2021). This accessibility has enabled municipalities and researchers worldwide to assess urban tree benefits.

In their foundational research, Nowak, Crane, and Stevens (2006) estimate that urban trees in the United States across 55 U.S. cities remove approximately 711,000 metric tonnes of air pollution annually with an estimated value of \$3.8 billion. The amount of pollution removed varied by city depending on factors such as tree cover, pollution concentration, and length of the in-leaf season. The study highlights that although the overall percentage improvement in urban air quality is modest, urban trees play a significant role in pollutant removal and should be considered a viable strategy for enhancing environmental quality (Nowak et al., 2006). The model they used in this study, laid a groundwork for the development of i-Tree Canopy.

The i-Tree Canopy tool has been widely utilized in research both nationally and internationally, serving as a robust framework for evaluating urban forestry and ecosystem services. Its applications extend across diverse geographical contexts.

In England, i-Tree Canopy tool was applied to assess canopy cover in 283 towns and cities. The findings estimated that the average canopy cover was 15.8%, providing a benchmark for enhancing urban forests to improve public health and well-being (Doick et al., 2017).

A recent study from the Middle Eastern region, Ghorbankhani et al. (2023), assessed ecosystem services in Tehran's Nahjol-Balagheh and Pardisan parks—covering a combined area of approximately 321 hectares—using i-Tree Canopy with 1,515 randomly selected survey points. The results indicated that only 23.43% (69.08 ha) of the area is covered with trees and shrubs, while 32.08% (94.58 ha) consists of bare soil, limiting the parks' capacity to manage runoff and control flooding. Despite this,

the existing vegetation provides substantial ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration and storage, as well as air pollution removal.

Kim, Miller, and Nowak (2015) assessed ecosystem services provided by urban vacant land in Roanoke, Virginia, using i-Tree Canopy and i-Tree Eco across 114 plots. They found that vacant land supports 210,000 trees with 30.6% canopy cover, storing 97,508 tons of carbon (\$7.6 million) and sequestering 2,091 tons annually (\$164,000). Trees also remove 83 tons of air pollutants each year (\$916,000), reduce residential energy costs by \$211,000, and avoid 358 tons of carbon emissions (\$28,103). Unattended vegetated sites provided the highest ecosystem benefits, highlighting the value of preserving such land as green infrastructure (Kim et al., 2015).

In Los Angeles, Nowak et al. (2011) estimated that urban forests with 24.9% canopy cover stored 1.3 million tons of carbon (\$26.3 million) and removed 77,000 tons of CO₂ and nearly 1,976 tons of air pollutants annually, valued at \$14.2 million. They found that LA's 6 million trees are estimated to reduce annual residential energy costs by \$10.2 million per year (p. 10).

Similarly, a district-level study in Türkiye assigned 10,000 random points over a 34,200 ha area to evaluate tree canopy cover of 7.11%. Trees in the district were found to sequester 27,370 tons of CO₂ annually, store 687,460 tons of CO₂ over their lifetimes, and remove approximately 27,579 tons of air pollutants, valued at \$1.48 million (Çakmak and Can, 2020).

Hepcan and Hepcan (2017) used i-Tree Canopy to analyze the ecosystem services provided by the canopy cover of the Ege University campus in Türkiye. Their study revealed that the campus had 48.3% tree and shrub canopy cover, sequestering 321.57 tons of CO₂ annually and storing 8,107.86 tons over the lifetime of the vegetation. They found that the vegetation also removed 28.7 kg of carbon monoxide (CO), 143.85 kg of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), 1.58 tons of ozone (O₃), 90.6 kg of sulfur dioxide (SO₂), 69.61 kg of PM_{2.5}, and 479.9 kg of PM₁₀ annually. These estimates were based on 3,000 random points assigned over a 54.47 ha area (p. 119).

In conclusion, the i-Tree Canopy tool offers a cost-effective, user-friendly and adaptable platform for quantifying the benefits of urban forests. Its widespread application across diverse regions highlights its significance in addressing urban sustainability and resilience challenges. However, the tool's accuracy is contingent upon user interpretation of land cover, which introduces an element of subjectivity. In addition, i-Tree Canopy generates estimates using default ecosystem service values derived from generalized models, which can limit the precision of results when applied to areas with distinct ecological features or economic contexts. Despite these limitations, i-Tree Canopy continues to advance alongside developments in software technology and environmental science, and an increasing number of studies worldwide rely on it for ecosystem service valuation. Accordingly, it was selected for this study to contribute to the assessment of Lake Eymir's Total Economic Value (TEV).

3.2 Using i-Tree Canopy Tool

The i-Tree Canopy tool enables the valuation of ecosystem services by estimating the proportion of land covered by tree canopies within a defined area. This tree canopy cover, expressed as a percentage, serves as an important indicator of various ecological and societal benefits, such as shade provision, pollution removal, carbon dioxide absorption, and avoided runoff. To carry out this assessment, the tool employs a random point sampling method using Google Earth imagery. Users specify the number of random points to be analyzed, and each point is manually classified according to land cover type—options include tree canopy, grass, buildings, roads, or other user-defined categories. As more points are classified, the accuracy of the estimates improves, and the tool continuously updates the percentage breakdown of each land cover class. Crucially, for points classified as tree canopy, the tool estimates the annual volume of air pollutants removed and assigning monetary values to these ecosystem services.

The pollutants assessed by i-Tree Canopy include six criteria pollutants as defined by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA): carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), ozone (O₃), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter less than 2.5 microns (PM_{2.5}), and particulate matter between 2.5 and 10 microns (PM₁₀) (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [EPA], n.d.). These pollutants are critical to urban air quality management, and the tool provides a quantitative basis for understanding the role of trees in mitigating their presence in the atmosphere.

3.2.1 Getting Started

The i-Tree Canopy tool can be accessed through a free, web-based platform at <https://canopy.itreetools.org>. Analyzing the case study area using the i-Tree Canopy tool begins by accessing its user-friendly web interface and clicking the 'Get Started' button located on the right-hand side of the screen. As shown in Figure 3.1, the tool provides an intuitive starting point to classify land and tree cover using random sampling of aerial imagery. Users define their project area by selecting pre-existing geographic boundaries, drawing custom boundaries on Google Maps, or importing an ESRI shapefile. The tool then generates random points within the designated area for further classification. This initial step ensures that the study area is accurately outlined, setting the foundation for precise land cover analysis and the subsequent estimation of ecosystem service benefits.

Canopy
i-Tree. A tree canopy assessment tool

Home Project Menu Feedback

Welcome to i-Tree Canopy!

Use this tool to classify land and tree cover across a given area using random sampling of aerial imagery. See tree canopy benefits in terms of **carbon dioxide**, **air pollution**, and **stormwater** impacts.

How to use it:

- Select from existing geographic boundaries, draw your own project area boundaries onto Google Maps, or load an ESRI shapefile.
- You can use multiple, non-overlapping boundaries at the same time.
- i-Tree Canopy randomly generates sample points and zooms to each one so you can choose from your pre-defined list of cover types for that spot.
- With i-Tree Canopy, you review Google Maps aerial photography at random points to conduct a cover assessment within a defined project area.
- 500-1000 survey points are suggested; the more points you complete, the better your cover estimate for your study area.
- If estimating tree cover, tree benefits can also be estimated.
- [Learn how i-Tree Canopy works.](#)
- [Video Learning Resources](#)

Get Started

Use of this tool indicates acceptance of the EULA
www.itreetools.org

Figure 3.1: i-Tree Canopy Tool Starting Page

3.2.2 Configuration

Upon accessing the user interface, the configuration process involved three key steps: setting the boundaries of the study area, defining land cover classes, and adjusting regional settings to tailor the analysis.

3.2.2.1 Boundaries

In the first step of the i-Tree Canopy tool analysis, users define the boundaries of the area to be surveyed. As shown in Figure 3.2, the map interface provides various tools to create these boundaries. The easiest option is selecting from pre-existing geographic boundaries, such as national or regional datasets. Alternatively, users can draw custom boundaries directly on the map or upload shapefiles for precise delineation. This flexibility ensures that the survey area is tailored to specific research needs, serving as the basis for the random point sampling process in subsequent steps.

Figure 3.2: Configuring Boundaries

For this study, ArcGIS 10.7 was used to create an ESRI shapefile, delineating a closed polygon around the lake with an area of approximately 190 hectares. This shapefile was then uploaded into the i-Tree Canopy tool during the configuration step to define the study area accurately. This approach ensured precision in the

analysis, focusing exclusively on the designated boundaries around the lake (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Case Study Area Boundaries Delineated by an ESRI Shapefile

3.2.2.2 Cover Classes

In Configuration Step 2, the i-Tree Canopy tool allows users to define the land cover classes to be surveyed. While the tool provides default classes like Tree and Non-Tree, these can be customized to align with the specific needs of the study. For this research, the following land cover classes were configured:

Tree/Shrub (T): Representing areas covered by trees or shrubs, categorized as 'Yes' under tree cover.

Grass/Steppe/Herbaceous (H): Non-tree vegetation such as grasslands, categorized as 'No' means not under tree cover.

Impervious Buildings (IB): Built structures like houses and buildings, categorized as 'No' indicating not identified as tree cover.

Impervious Road (IR): Roads and pavements, categorized as 'No' as non-tree cover.

Impervious Other (IO): Other impervious surfaces, such as parking lots, categorized as 'No' denoting another non-tree entity.

Water (W): Water bodies, categorized as 'No.'

Soil/Bare Ground (S): Exposed soil or bare ground, categorized as 'No.'

Reeds/Aquatic Plants (RDS): Wetland vegetation, such as reeds, categorized as 'No.'

The Yes/No categorization is crucial because benefit calculations for a specific class are based on whether it is identified as tree cover or not. Classes categorized as 'No' are excluded from the benefit calculations but remain valuable for analyzing the land use patterns of the area.

Each class was assigned a unique color code for easy identification during the analysis, with 'Tree/Shrub' as the primary tree cover class (Table 3.1). This customization ensured that the survey captured the diverse land cover types present in the study area accurately.

Table 3.1 Cover Classes of i-Tree Canopy Analysis

Cover Class	Abbreviation	Tree Cover?	Color
Tree/Shrub	T	Yes	#1BCA00CC
Grass/Steppe/Herbaceous	H	No	#1A750DCC
Impervious Buildings	IB	No	#F8E71C
Impervious Road	IR	No	#FF0000CC
Impervious Other	IO	No	#8A8A8ACC
Water	W	No	#0000FFCC
Soil/Bare Ground	S	No	#6E4D29CC
Reeds/Aquatic Plants	RDS	No	#B8E986

3.2.2.3 Regional Settings

Configuration Step 3 can present challenges for international users due to the limited availability of regional datasets. In this configuration step of the i-Tree Canopy tool, users are required to select regional settings to align the analysis with local environmental conditions. Currently, the tool provides datasets for the United States, United Kingdom, Ukraine, Sweden, New Zealand, and South Korea. Due to the absence of a dedicated dataset for Türkiye within the i-Tree Canopy system, international users, whose study area is not in one of these countries or where national data is unavailable, are advised to select a region with a similar climate and population density to ensure accurate benefit estimations (Oliviera et al., 2022). In many international studies, researchers either select all available regions (e.g., Yurtkuran, 2022, p. 55), or do not provide details about their selection in this step at all (e.g., Ghorbankhani et al., 2023; Çakmak & Can, 2020; Hepcan & Hepcan, 2017), which can lead to scientifically questionable results. Thus, careful selection of a comparable region is essential to maintain the validity of the analysis.

A comparative approach was adopted in this study as part of the international user analysis. A city comparable to Ankara was identified, and the results were calculated (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4 :Scenario 1: Selecting a Comparable Location

Subsequently, all available locations were selected, as is commonly done in other studies, and the outcomes were compared (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5: Scenario 2: Selecting All Available Locations Data-Scenario

In this study, Denver, Colorado was selected as the primary reference location for conducting the i-Tree Canopy analysis of Lake Eymir, Ankara. This decision is based on the following scientific and methodological considerations:

3.2.2.3.1 Climate Similarity

Ankara experiences a continental climate with hot, dry summers and cold, snowy winters, classified as Dsa (Hot-Summer Continental Climate) under the Köppen-Geiger system (Peel et al., 2007). This classification reflects its large seasonal temperature variations and dry summer conditions. Similarly, Denver falls under the BSk (Cold Semi-Arid Climate) classification. While Denver's climate is slightly drier than Ankara's, both regions share significant seasonal temperature variations and arid conditions, making them comparable for the purposes of this analysis. The Köppen-Geiger framework provides a scientifically robust basis for assessing climatic alignment between the two cities.

3.2.2.3.2 Vegetation and Land Use

Both Ankara and Denver are located in regions with a mix of urban development and semi-natural landscapes. While Ankara features ecosystems such as grasslands and wooded areas surrounding Lake Eymir, Denver exhibits similar vegetation patterns within its urban and peri-urban spaces. This comparability supports the transferability of ecosystem service estimates derived from i-Tree Canopy analysis.

3.2.2.3.3 Population Considerations

According to the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK), Ankara's population in 2023 was approximately 5.8 million (TÜİK, 2023). In comparison, the Denver-Aurora-Lakewood metropolitan area had a population of about 3 million in 2023 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2023). Although Denver's metropolitan population is smaller, it remains one of the larger urban centers in the United States. When scaled proportionally, Denver provides a reasonable approximation for Ankara, especially considering that the central urban districts of Ankara are the primary beneficiaries of the Lake Eymir area. Focusing on these urban districts further justifies the comparability between the two cities, as it narrows the scope to areas with similar urban population densities and land use dynamics.

3.2.2.3.4 Justification for Selection

Denver was chosen based on its climatic alignment with Ankara and its urban environmental structure, offering a scientifically grounded basis for using it as a proxy location in the absence of Turkish-specific i-Tree Canopy data. This selection follows a well-established methodological precedent observed in similar studies, such as Oliveira et al. (2022). In their evaluation of ecosystem services in Naples, Italy, Oliveira et al. addressed the geographic limitations of the i-Tree Canopy tool by selecting Horry County, South Carolina, USA, as a reference location. Their

selection was based on the identification of similar Modified Köppen-Geiger climate (MCN) conditions between Naples and Horry County, ensuring that climatic and environmental factors were adequately matched despite being in different geographic regions. This demonstrates that it is both feasible and scientifically sound to identify analogous climatic areas within the United States for the application of i-Tree Canopy to international contexts.

However, while the climatic alignment between Naples and Horry County was achieved, it is important to note a significant demographic disparity between the two areas. The population of Naples is approximately 2,180,000 as of 2024, whereas the population of Horry County is only about 411,809 during the same period. This indicates that Naples has a population nearly four times larger than that of Horry County. Such a demographic mismatch highlights a limitation of the methodology employed in Oliveira et al.'s study, as population size and density can influence the extent and nature of ecosystem services provided by urban green spaces. Nevertheless, their work underscores the flexibility of the i-Tree Canopy methodology, emphasizing that climatic similarity remains the primary criterion for proxy location selection, even when population sizes are not directly comparable.

Building on this precedent, Denver, Colorado, was selected in this study as a proxy for Ankara due to its semi-arid climate (BSk), which closely aligns with Ankara's hot-summer continental climate (Dsa) (Peel et al., 2007). Both cities exhibit significant seasonal temperature variations, and their climates are shaped by similar precipitation patterns, with Ankara receiving approximately 400 mm of annual rainfall compared to Denver's 363 mm. This alignment ensures that ecosystem service estimates derived from i-Tree Canopy reflect conditions comparable to those experienced in Ankara.

In addition to climate, Denver's urban environmental structure provides another layer of alignment. Like Ankara, Denver is characterized by a mix of urban and peri-urban vegetation, including green spaces and wooded areas. Such similarities in land use and ecological settings further validate its selection as a proxy for Lake Eymir

and its surrounding areas. Moreover, in contrast to the demographic mismatch observed in the Naples-Horry County comparison, Denver's metropolitan population of approximately 3 million (United States Census Bureau, 2020) offers a much closer match to Ankara's population of 5,803,482 (Turkish Statistical Institute, 2023). While some differences remain, this more accurate alignment in population adds another layer of robustness to the selection process, ensuring that both climatic and demographic considerations are addressed.

3.2.2.3.5 Comparative Approach

In addition to selecting Denver, i-Tree Canopy analyses were also conducted using multiple locations with varying climatic and demographic characteristics. This approach aligns with practices observed in previous research which utilized diverse reference locations to assess urban forestry impacts in different environmental contexts. By incorporating multiple reference locations, this study ensures a comprehensive evaluation of ecosystem services, allowing for a robust comparison of results. Presenting findings from Denver alongside those from other locations highlights potential variations and validates the robustness of the conclusions.

By aligning with the methodological precedent set by Oliveira et al. (2022) while addressing potential limitations associated with demographic discrepancies, this study ensures that the selection of Denver as a proxy location is scientifically rigorous, contextually appropriate, and methodologically sound. This approach highlights the adaptability of the i-Tree Canopy tool for analyzing ecosystem services in Ankara and similar regions. By combining a location-specific analysis with a broader comparative framework, the study provides a comprehensive evaluation and strengthens the applicability of i-Tree Canopy results in diverse international contexts.

3.2.3 Land Cover Assessment

After completing the configuration steps, the land cover survey was conducted using the i-Tree Canopy tool. Survey points were added by clicking the designated button, which shifted the map to a random location within the study area (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6: Appointing Survey Points

At each point, the land cover class was recorded using the dropdown menu at the yellow crosshairs at the map's center. This randomized approach ensured an unbiased sampling of the 190-hectare area.

3.2.3.1 Overcoming Photo-interpretation Limitations

The accuracy and sensitivity of i-Tree Canopy are directly influenced by the user's ability to assign survey points correctly. As such, addressing photo-interpretation challenges and ensuring accurate classification of land cover are pivotal for reliable results. One notable challenge encountered in this study involved the identification of tree canopies in certain parts of the study area, particularly along the shores of the lake (Figure 3.7). In these areas, vegetation was often highly intertwined, necessitating the differentiation of trees from reeds and aquatic plants, which were

excluded from the tree canopy benefit calculations. To overcome this, field visits were conducted to cross-reference the vegetation observed in aerial photos with on-ground conditions, thereby improving the precision of tree canopy classification.

Figure 3.7: Intertwined vegetation in the Shores of Eymir

Another challenge stemmed from the temporal limitations of the available Google Earth imagery. Certain images were captured during winter, making it difficult to identify leafless trees accurately (Figure 3.8). To address this limitation, historical imagery from Google Earth Pro was used to supplement the dataset with aerial photos taken during summer, when tree foliage was more visible. This method not only facilitated more accurate identification of tree canopies but also ensured consistency in land cover classification across the study area.

Figure 3.8: Aerial Photos of Trees in Winter vs. Summer

The number of survey points per hectare in this study is significantly higher than those reported in comparable studies in the literature. Specifically, the survey conducted at Lake Eymir utilized 20,250 points across 190 hectares, resulting in 106.6 points per hectare with a remarkably low standard error of 0.32% (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2 Survey Density Comparison

Study	Location	Number of Points	Surface Area(ha)	Points per ha	Standard
					Error (SE)%
Yakar, F.	Lake Eymir, Ankara,TR	20250	190	106.6	0.32
Çakmak & Can (2020)	Mamak, Ankara, TR	10000	34200	0.29	0.26
Tonyaloğlu et al. (2021)	Aydın, TR	6500	233	27.9	0.43
Ustun & Demirel (2023)	Üsküdar, İstanbul, TR	5500	150	36.6	0.64
Doick et. al. (2017)	London, UK	3000	104400	0.03	0,72
Hepcan & Hepcan (2017)	İzmir, TR	3000	54	55.5	0.91
Kim et al. (2015)	Roanoke, Virginia, USA	1000	11000	0,09	1.39
Nowak et al. (2011)	Los Angeles, USA	1000	12000	0.08	1.4
Ghorbankhani et. al. (2023)	Tahran, Iran	1515	321	4.7	3.21
Olivatto (2019)	Brasilia, Brazil	1110	80	4.7	3.32
Oliveira et.al (2022)	Naples, Italy	803	117400	0.007	9.64

This high survey density enhances the precision and reliability of the results, as indicated by the low standard error. By setting a new benchmark, this study demonstrates the potential for achieving more accurate estimates of ecosystem services using a denser sampling framework. The methodological rigor applied here contributes to the broader body of research on i-Tree Canopy applications and positions this study as a reference point for similar analyses globally.

The findings underscore the importance of high survey densities in achieving reliable ecosystem service valuations, particularly in urban and peri-urban contexts. Future studies should consider adopting higher point densities to improve accuracy, especially in areas with diverse land use and vegetation types.

As stated above, a total of 20,250 survey points were assigned across the study area (Figure 3.9). The majority of the survey points were classified as Tree/Shrub (14,475 points), reflecting the dominant land cover type.

Figure 3.9: Survey Points

Grass/Steppe/Herbaceous accounted for 4,185 points, while Soil/Bare Ground was identified at 878 points. Impervious surfaces were categorized as Impervious Road (588 points), Impervious Buildings (76 points), Impervious Other (10 points), and Reeds/Aquatic Plants were recorded at 31 points. Water was represented by only 7 points because only points corresponding to a small inland stream and some marshlands were classified as water. The actual lake area was excluded from the assessment, as its inclusion would not provide meaningful results. The closed polygon used for the analysis encompassed only the land area surrounding the lake. This detailed distribution provides a comprehensive overview of the land cover within the 190-hectare study area (Figure 3.10).

Figure 3.10: Cover Class Chart

The majority of the points were classified as Tree/Shrub, reflecting the dominant land cover type in the area. Increasing the number of survey points reduces standard error, enhancing the precision of the land cover estimation for the study area (Table 3.3).

Table 3.3 Cover Class Table

Abbreviation	Cover Class	Points	% Cover ± SE	Area (km ²) ± SE
H	Grass/Steppe/Herbaceous	4185	20.67 ± 0.28	0.39 ± 0.01
IB	Impervious Buildings	76	0.38 ± 0.04	0.01 ± 0.00
IO	Impervious Other	10	0.05 ± 0.02	0.00 ± 0.00
IR	Impervious Road	588	2.90 ± 0.12	0.06 ± 0.00
RDS	Reeds/Aquatic Plants	31	0.15 ± 0.03	0.00 ± 0.00
S	Soil/Bare Ground	878	4.34 ± 0.14	0.08 ± 0.00
T	Tree/Shrub	14475	71.48 ± 0.32	1.36 ± 0.01
W	Water	7	0.03 ± 0.01	0.00 ± 0.00
Total		20250	100.00	1.90

3.2.4 Results

3.2.4.1 Tree Benefit Estimates: Carbon

The results of the analysis highlight the significant carbon sequestration and storage benefits provided by the trees in the Lake Eymir ecosystem. Specifically, the trees sequester approximately 267.19 tonnes of carbon annually, equating to 979.68 tonnes of CO₂, with an economic value of \$50,231 USD annually. The cumulative carbon storage in trees is notably higher, at 10,422.69 tonnes, equivalent to 38,216.52 tonnes of CO₂, with a total value of \$1,959,465 USD (Table 3.4). These findings underscore the critical role of the trees at Lake Eymir in mitigating climate change by serving as a substantial carbon sink.

Table 3.4 Tree Benefit Estimates: Carbon (Metric units)

Description	Carbon (t)	±SE	CO ₂ Equiv. (t)	±SE	Value (USD)	±SE
Sequestered annually in trees	267.19	±1.19	979.68	±4.35	\$50,231	±223
Stored in trees*	10,422.69	±46.26	38,216.52	±169.63	\$1,959,465	±8,697

Currency is in USD and rounded. Standard errors of removal and benefit amounts are based on standard errors of sampled and classified points.

Amount sequestered is based on 197.000 t of Carbon, or 722.333 t of CO₂, per km²/yr and rounded.

Amount stored is based on 7684.808 t of Carbon, or 28177.630 t of CO₂, per km² and rounded. Value (USD) is based on \$188.00/t of Carbon, or \$51.27/t of CO₂ and rounded. (Metric units: t = tonnes, metric tons, km² = square kilometers)

**Note: this benefit is not an annual rate*

The valuation methodology used, based on \$188 per tonne of carbon and \$51.27 per tonne of CO₂, provides a robust framework for monetizing ecosystem services.

3.2.4.2 Tree Benefit Estimates: Air Pollution

The trees at Lake Eymir remove a wide range of air pollutants, with a total annual removal of 12,445.55 kilograms, valued at \$64,539 USD (Table 3.5). The removal of Ozone (O₃) and Particulate Matter (PM10) contributes the most to this value, with respective economic benefits of \$29,519 USD and \$22,874 USD. The removal of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) is also noteworthy due to its critical health impacts, with a removal value of \$8,875 USD.

Table 3.5 Tree Benefit Estimates: Air Pollution (Metric units)

Abbr.	Description	Amount (kg)	±SE	Value (USD)	±SE
CO	Carbon Monoxide removed annually	173.47	±0.77	\$255	±1
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide removed annually	3,056.29	±13.57	\$2,815	±12
O ₃	Ozone removed annually	5,363.16	±23.81	\$29,519	±131
SO ₂	Sulfur Dioxide removed annually	365.79	±1.62	\$201	±1
PM2.5	Particulate Matter less than 2.5 microns removed annually	176.42	±0.78	\$8,875	±39
PM10*	Particulate Matter greater than 2.5 microns and less than 10 microns removed annually	3,310.43	±14.69	\$22,874	±102
Total		12,445.55	±55.24	\$64,539	±286

Currency is in USD and rounded. Standard errors of removal and benefit amounts are based on standard errors of sampled and classified points. Air Pollution Estimates are based on these values in kg/km²/yr @ \$/kg/yr and rounded: CO 127.900 @ \$1.47 | NO₂ 2,253.449 @ \$0.92 | O₃ 3,954.338 @ \$5.50 | SO₂ 269.701 @ \$0.55 | PM_{2.5} 130.077 @ \$50.30 | PM₁₀ 2,440.832 @ \$6.91 (Metric units: kg = kilograms, km² = square kilometers)*

These values highlight the public health and environmental benefits provided by the trees, contributing to cleaner air and improved living conditions around Lake Eymir.

3.2.4.3 Tree Benefit Estimates: Hydrological

Hydrological benefits are another critical ecosystem service demonstrated in the results. The trees contribute to avoided runoff of 17.59 megaliters annually, valued at \$41,513 USD (Table 3.6). This benefit is particularly valuable in managing stormwater, reducing erosion, and protecting water quality in Lake Eymir. Additionally, the high rates of transpiration (189.84 MI) and evaporation (59.56 MI) indicate the active role of the ecosystem in regulating the local microclimate and water cycle.

Table 3.6 Tree Benefit Estimates: Hydrological (Metric units)

Abbr.	Benefit	Amount (MI)	±SE	Value (USD)	±SE
AVRO	Avoided Runoff	17.59	±0.08	\$41,513	±184
E	Evaporation	59.56	±0.26	N/A	N/A
I	Interception	59.61	±0.26	N/A	N/A
T	Transpiration	189.84	±0.84	N/A	N/A
PE	Potential Evaporation	899.83	±3.99	N/A	N/A
PET	Potential Evapotranspiration	679.46	±3.02	N/A	N/A

Currency is in USD and rounded. Standard errors of removal and benefit amounts are based on standard errors of sampled and classified points. Hydrological Estimates are based on these values in MI/km²/yr @ \$/MI/yr and rounded: AVRO 12.966 @ \$2,360.64 | E 43.918 @ N/A | I 43.955 @ N/A | T 139.971 @ N/A | PE 663.462 @ N/A | PET 500.976 @ N/A (Metric units: MI = megaliters, km² = square kilometers)

The results also highlight potential evapotranspiration (PET) at 679.46 MI annually, which provides insights into the contribution of this ecosystem to the water cycle and microclimate regulation.

3.2.4.4 Comparative Results

To evaluate the implications of selecting different regional settings in the i-Tree Canopy tool, two scenarios were compared: Scenario 1, which utilized Denver, Colorado, as a comparable location to Ankara, and Scenario 2, which included data from all available locations. The comparative results are summarized in Table 3.7, highlighting significant variations in ecosystem service valuations.

Table 3.7 Comparative Results

	Scenario 1: Comparable Location: Denver, Colorado Value (USD)	Scenario 2: All Available Locations Value (USD)
Tree Benefits		
Sequestered annually in trees	\$50,231	\$77,017
Stored in trees	\$1,959,465	\$1,934,187
Air Pollution Benefits	\$64,539	\$21,395
Estimate Total		
Hydrological Benefits- Avoided Runoff	\$41,513	\$3,134

In Scenario 1, the annual carbon sequestration value for trees was calculated at \$50,231, whereas Scenario 2 estimated this value at \$77,017, indicating a potential overestimation in the generalized approach. Similarly, the total air pollution benefits were valued at \$64,539 in Scenario 1 compared to \$21,395 in Scenario 2, highlighting a notable underestimation when using aggregated data. While the total amount of carbon stored in trees showed minimal variation between the scenarios, hydrological benefits, such as avoided runoff, were considerably higher in Scenario 1 (\$41,513) than in Scenario 2 (\$3,134).

These differences underscore the importance of selecting a regional setting that reflects the specific climatic and demographic characteristics of the study area. The

generalized approach in Scenario 2, while easier to implement, risks both overestimating and underestimating critical ecosystem service values, potentially compromising the validity of the results. In contrast, the targeted approach in Scenario 1 ensures greater accuracy by aligning the analysis with the environmental context of the study area.

By adopting a comparative methodology, this study demonstrates that careful regional selection is essential for maintaining scientific rigor and producing reliable valuations of ecosystem services. Researchers should prioritize contextual relevance over convenience to ensure that their findings are both precise and applicable.

3.2.5 Conclusion

The application of the i-Tree Canopy tool provided valuable insights into the ecological and economic contributions of Lake Eymir's tree cover by estimating quantifiable ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration, air pollution removal, and avoided stormwater runoff. These services fall under indirect use values, as they benefit human well-being through ecological processes without requiring direct interaction with the environment. While this type of analysis contributes meaningfully to the Total Economic Value (TEV) framework, it is important to recognize the tool's limitations. i-Tree Canopy is designed to assess biophysical indicators linked to measurable environmental functions, thus it does not capture non-use values—such as existence value (the value people assign to the mere presence of ecosystems) or bequest value (the value of preserving nature for future generations). These intangible values are critical components of TEV but require other valuation approaches, such as stated preference methods, to be effectively incorporated. Also, it does not address use values that arise from activities such as recreation, cultural engagement, and local environmental aesthetics. These aspects require alternative valuation methods to reflect the comprehensive value of Lake Eymir to its users and stakeholders.

To address these gaps, this study complemented the i-Tree Canopy analysis with a survey-based approach. The survey was designed to incorporate use values, capturing individual preferences and behaviors through Willingness to Pay (WTP) for conservation, ecosystem service ratings, and an analysis of activities performed at the lake. Additionally, it included questions addressing ethical and environmental-economic values, which reflect societal perceptions of the lake's importance beyond direct use or non-use benefits. By integrating these methodologies, this study aligns with the broader principles of the TEV framework, ensuring that both tangible and intangible contributions of Lake Eymir are considered.

The findings highlight the importance of adopting a multi-method approach to ecosystem service valuation. Although tools such as i-Tree Canopy offer a practical and low-cost means of measuring certain ecological benefits, they should be supplemented with survey-based and behavioral approaches to fully account for the wider range of ecosystem values. For instance, the estimated annual carbon sequestration of 267.19 tons valued at \$50,231 underscores the lake's role in climate regulation. However, the survey results will offer deeper insights into the lake's recreational and cultural significance, which are not reflected in the i-Tree Canopy outputs alone.

In conclusion, this chapter underscores that while i-Tree Canopy is a valuable tool for assessing ecosystem services, it represents only one piece of the valuation puzzle. To fully capture the TEV of Lake Eymir, an integrated approach combining non-use and direct benefit quantifications with assessments of use values is essential. This comprehensive methodology not only enhances the accuracy and policy relevance of ecosystem valuations but also provides a holistic understanding of the ecological, economic, and societal importance of natural areas.

CHAPTER 4

WILLINGNESS TO PAY (WTP) SURVEY

The valuation of ecosystem services through willingness to pay (WTP) methodologies is closely linked to broader economic paradigms, particularly the transition from orthodox to heterodox economic approaches. Traditional, or neoclassical, economics primarily values nature through market-based mechanisms and individual utility maximization, often operationalized via WTP (Pearce and Turner, 1989; Hanley and Barbier, 2009). While effective in generating monetary estimates, such approaches tend to neglect ethical, cultural, and ecological dimensions of value that are not easily captured through pricing mechanisms. In contrast, heterodox frameworks—particularly ecological economics—advocate for a broader understanding of value that recognizes the biophysical limits of ecosystems, the relational and intrinsic values of nature, and the importance of equity and justice in environmental decision-making. Thus, ecosystem services valuation becomes not solely an economic exercise but a reflection of deeper societal values and normative commitments. This shift has significant policy implications, encouraging institutional reform and ecological stewardship rather than mere reliance on price signals and consumer preferences.

Survey-based methods are increasingly recognized as valuable tools in assessing the importance of ecosystem services, as they offer a way to explore public perceptions and preferences in relation to environmental benefits. Such approaches are suggested to help translate the often abstract and intangible aspects of ecosystem services into data that can inform policy and planning decisions (see Raymond et al., 2009). Through direct engagement with respondents, surveys may also provide insights into how individuals perceive ecosystem functions and their attitudes toward environmental stewardship (Milcu et al., 2013). This chapter adopts a survey-based

approach to explore the multifaceted value of Lake Eymir, emphasizing its ecological, economic, and cultural roles within a broader ecosystem services framework.

Survey-based assessments, like the one utilized in this study, are widely recognized in the literature for their effectiveness in capturing subjective perceptions and willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem services.

In one of the most influential efforts to quantify the value of ecosystem services, Costanza et al. (1997) synthesized data from over 100 published valuation studies to estimate the global economic value of 17 ecosystem services across 16 major biomes. Using various valuation methods—including willingness-to-pay, replacement cost, and contingent valuation—they calculated average per-hectare values, which were then multiplied by the global extent of each biome. The study estimated the total annual value of ecosystem services to range between USD 16 trillion and 54 trillion, with a mean of USD 33 trillion—surpassing the global gross national product (GNP) at the time. Notably, the highest values were attributed to nutrient cycling, waste treatment, and coastal ecosystems. Despite methodological limitations and data gaps, the authors emphasized that their estimate likely represents a conservative lower bound, underscoring the urgent need to incorporate natural capital into policy and economic decision-making processes (Costanza et al., 1997).

Jim and Chen (2006) applied contingent valuation to estimate the recreational and amenity value of urban greenspaces in Guangzhou, China, based on face-to-face surveys with 340 residents. Using an open-ended payment card method, they calculated an average willingness to pay (WTP) of RMB17.14 per person per month, yielding an aggregate value of RMB547 million annually—six times the city's greenspace expenditures. Income was the only significant predictor of WTP, highlighting greenspaces as superior goods in the urban context.

Losonci (2012) conducted a contingent valuation study to estimate visitors' willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem services provided by Órség National Park in Hungary. A survey was conducted to explore respondents' preferences for various

ecosystem services, motivations behind their WTP. A payment card format was used to elicit daily entrance fee WTP values, with results indicating a mean WTP of 655 HUF per person. This translates to an aggregate potential revenue of approximately 215.5 million HUF annually, which could increase the park's budget by 49% if captured through user fees. The findings underscore the feasibility of introducing a direct rent capture mechanism to support conservation financing in protected areas (Losonci, 2012).

Cortés-Espino et al. (2023) conducted a contingent valuation study to assess local residents' willingness to pay (WTP) for the conservation of ecosystem services provided by the Los Horcones River, one of the last free-flowing rivers on Mexico's Pacific coast. A face-to-face survey was administered to 179 respondents from two rural communities—one upstream and one downstream—using a payment card method. The study also integrated a social value typology to assess the influence of non-monetary values on WTP. Results showed that 73% of respondents were willing to pay, with a mean WTP of MXN 196.7 (approx. USD 10.46). A generalized linear model revealed that WTP was significantly influenced by socioeconomic status, education level, gender, age, religion, and domestic use of river water. Social values such as bequest value and existence value also had significant positive effects on WTP. The study highlights the need to integrate both economic and social dimensions into river conservation policies (Cortés-Espino et al., 2023).

Kennedy (2014) applied and compared three ecosystem service valuation methods—value transfer, contingent valuation, and pricing approach—to assess the impact of land-use change in Amstelland near Amsterdam. A contingent valuation survey was conducted with 120 residents across five municipalities to elicit willingness to pay (WTP) for the preservation of croplands and grasslands, revealing that WTP varied by payment vehicle and was influenced by land scarcity in respondents' localities. Lastly, a pricing method was implemented by estimating replacement, avoided, and market costs for selected provisioning, regulating, and cultural services, such as reed harvesting, grazing, carbon sequestration, and air purification. The comparison revealed that while value transfer offered convenience, contingent valuation

captured local preferences more accurately, and the pricing method delivered the most detailed site-specific insights despite its complexity (Kennedy, 2014).

Surveys are particularly valuable in this context, as they reveal public preferences and identify gaps in awareness, thereby guiding efforts to promote ecosystem conservation.

Survey-based methods such as contingent valuation can reflect not only economic preferences but also deeper affective, cultural, and psychological dimensions. As Martín-López, Montes, and Benayas (2007) demonstrate, individuals' willingness to pay for biodiversity conservation is strongly shaped by their attitudes toward species, which are themselves influenced by socio-demographic variables, environmental knowledge, and cultural perceptions. These factors may introduce systematic bias, particularly when public preferences are driven more by familiarity or emotional appeal than by ecological importance, thereby challenging the assumption that stated economic values arise solely from rational assessments of ecosystem services.

Furthermore, the abstract nature of many ecosystem services—particularly regulating and supporting services—can make them less accessible to public understanding. Addressing these challenges requires a combination of improved survey designs, robust educational campaigns, and efforts to make the benefits of intangible services more relatable to everyday life.

Nevertheless, the use of surveys remains a cornerstone in ecosystem service valuation. Their ability to capture public preferences provides essential insights that complement ecological and economic analyses. By integrating subjective perceptions with scientific data, survey-based studies contribute to a comprehensive understanding of ecosystem service values, laying the groundwork for more informed and equitable environmental policies. This study's findings contribute to this broader effort by highlighting societal priorities and identifying areas where greater awareness and action are needed.

4.1 Survey Structure

4.1.1 Introduction-Greeting

The survey begins with an introductory section designed to provide respondents with essential information about the purpose and scope of the study (See Appendix A and B). This introduction adheres to established best practices in social research methods, emphasizing transparency, ethical compliance, and informed consent. Specifically, the survey outlines that it is part of a doctoral research project focused on valuing the ecosystem services of Lake Eymir. In survey design, this framing is crucial for building trust and encouraging participation by clearly articulating the research objectives (Dillman et al., 2014).

In line with ethical research practices, the introduction ensures respondents of their anonymity and emphasizes the voluntary nature of their participation. In addition, a consent form was prepared to be signed by the respondents (See Appendix C). Respondents are informed that they may withdraw from the survey at any point without consequences, a principle critical to maintaining ethical standards in social research (Bryman, 2016). Furthermore, the format and estimated duration of the questionnaire are detailed, noting that it consists of 15 questions in various formats, expected to take 7–10 minutes to complete. This transparent communication ensures respondents understand the scope of their commitment, a strategy widely endorsed to improve response rates and quality (Dillman et al., 2014).

By incorporating these elements, the introductory section aligns with ethical guidelines such as those outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013). It provides a clear and professional entry point to the survey, fostering trust and ensuring compliance with ethical research standards.

4.1.2 Background Information on the Study Area

Following the introduction, the survey includes a section that provides respondents with brief but comprehensive background information about Lake Eymir. This contextual overview is vital for helping respondents make informed judgments about the questions that follow. The background highlights the lake's ecological richness, noting that it supports over 200 bird species, 700 plant species, and a range of aquatic and terrestrial habitats. This foundational context ensures that participants are aware of the lake's ecological significance, thereby enhancing the reliability and relevance of their stated preferences in the valuation exercise.

The section also describes the diverse ecosystems present in the area, such as wetlands, reedbeds, forests, and steppes, linking these features to services like habitat provision, carbon sequestration, and water regulation. Such descriptions help respondents understand the tangible and intangible benefits provided by Lake Eymir, which is critical for eliciting meaningful responses to valuation questions. In addition, the background highlights potential threats to the lake, including urban and industrial pressures, pollution, misuse, and climate change. By outlining both the ecological benefits and the threats facing Lake Eymir, this section equips respondents with a balanced perspective, enabling them to evaluate conservation scenarios with greater awareness and depth.

Providing this detailed background not only engages respondents but also ensures that they are equipped with the necessary context to provide thoughtful and accurate responses. As noted by Dillman et al. (2014), including such contextual information improves the quality of survey responses by enhancing respondent understanding of the study's scope and objectives.

4.1.3 Demographics

The demographic section of the survey is designed to collect essential information about the respondents, facilitating a deeper understanding of their socioeconomic

and geographic characteristics. These variables serve as crucial predictors in analyzing ecosystem service valuation, user preferences, and clustering behaviors.

The income question was designed as a single-choice, open-ended question rather than multiple-choice intervals. This approach was adopted to allow the collection of continuous data, which is more suitable for statistical analyses such as regression models and clustering algorithms. By avoiding predefined income brackets, this design enhances the flexibility of data analysis and prevents potential biases introduced by arbitrary income intervals.

The district question collects information about the respondents' residential districts within Ankara. This variable is particularly relevant for understanding the spatial dynamics of user preferences. Travel distance, for instance, may influence how frequently individuals visit Lake Eymir or their willingness to pay for its conservation. Additionally, this information supports grouping and clustering analyses to identify patterns based on geographic proximity, which can inform targeted policy interventions and urban planning.

Further demographic questions focus on education, employment, and gender, which are standard variables in survey-based research for understanding differences in attitudes, preferences, and awareness. Results can be influenced by respondents' cultural, educational, and socio-economic backgrounds, which shape their environmental knowledge and perceptions, thereby introducing potential biases in valuation outcomes. Education levels, in particular, may affect respondents' awareness and understanding of ecosystem services, as higher education is often associated with greater environmental knowledge (Martín-López et al., 2007). This dynamic also influenced the findings of the present study.

Employment status provides insight into respondents' socioeconomic context, which may influence their valuation of Lake Eymir's ecosystem services. Gender, meanwhile, can reveal differences in perceptions and priorities, as previous studies have shown that men and women may value ecosystem services differently. For instance, Yang et al. (2018) found that women generally placed greater importance

on provisioning services like freshwater and medicinal plants, and were more likely to prioritize regulating services such as water quality, erosion control, and soil formation. In contrast, men tended to have more knowledge of fuel and timber resources and attributed greater significance to ecosystem services related to disaster mitigation. These gendered differences are shaped by distinct roles, responsibilities, and access to resources, and underscore the importance of integrating a gender lens into ecosystem service assessments and policymaking (Yang et al., 2018).

The METU affiliation question was included to explore whether institutional connections influence respondents' valuation of Lake Eymir. Since the lake is located on the Middle East Technical University (METU) campus but is open to the public, it is hypothesized that individuals affiliated with METU—such as students, staff, or alumni—might exhibit a stronger sense of ownership or higher appreciation for the lake compared to unaffiliated respondents. This distinction provides valuable insights into how institutional ties and a sense of belonging influence environmental values and stewardship behaviors.

By integrating these demographic variables, the survey ensures a comprehensive approach to understanding the diverse factors that influence respondents' preferences and valuation of Lake Eymir. This demographic data serves as a foundation for the subsequent analysis, enabling the exploration of relationships between socioeconomic characteristics and ecosystem service valuation.

4.1.4 Visiting Frequency Questions

Questions 8 and 9 in the survey are designed to assess the respondents' recency and frequency of visits to Lake Eymir, providing essential context for evaluating their Willingness to Pay (WTP) and engagement with the lake's ecosystem services.

Question 8 asks whether respondents have visited Lake Eymir in the past 12 months. This timeframe is consistent with established practices in WTP surveys, where the time period depends on the nature of the product or service being evaluated. For

frequently consumed products, such as coffee, shorter timeframes like one day or one week may be appropriate. For durable goods, such as washing machines, longer timeframes of up to a decade are typical. In the context of ecosystem service valuation, a 12-month period strikes a balance between being recent enough to capture meaningful experiences and long enough to account for seasonal variations in visitation patterns. This approach ensures that respondents' WTP reflects their typical engagement with the lake over a full annual cycle, encompassing a variety of recreational and ecological interactions.

Question 8 asks whether respondents have visited Lake Eymir in the past 12 months. This timeframe was selected to ensure that WTP responses reflect relatively recent and meaningful experiences while still capturing seasonal variation in visitation. In survey-based valuation, the appropriate recall period often depends on the nature of the good being evaluated. For frequently consumed products, such as coffee, shorter timeframes like one day or one week may be appropriate. For environmental or recreational resources, a 12-month window offers a more representative view of typical engagement. This design choice aims to balance accuracy in recall with the comprehensiveness needed to reflect diverse interactions with the site throughout the year.

Question 9 refines this information by asking respondents to specify their frequency of visits during the past 12 months, using intervals ranging from "1 to 3 times" to "20 or more times." This categorization facilitates the grouping of respondents based on their level of interaction with Lake Eymir. Visit frequency is a critical variable in understanding use values, as it reflects the extent to which individuals benefit directly from the lake's recreational, cultural, or aesthetic services. Frequent visitors, for instance, are likely to have a deeper connection with the area, which may translate into higher WTP values for its preservation.

These questions collectively enable the survey to capture the temporal and behavioral dimensions of respondents' engagement with Lake Eymir. By linking visit

frequency and recency to WTP responses, the study provides valuable insights into how direct use of the lake influences its perceived value.

4.1.5 Activities

The activities question in the survey was carefully crafted to capture a comprehensive range of recreational activities associated with Lake Eymir. This list was developed using a multi-faceted approach, combining insights from secondary resources provided by METU, field observations, and informal interviews with staff and visitors. These sources ensured the inclusion of diverse activities that accurately represent the recreational use of the area.

Recreational activities are a key component of cultural ecosystem services, which reflect the non-material benefits that ecosystems provide to people through leisure, aesthetic enjoyment, and spiritual enrichment (MA, 2005a; TEEB, 2011; EEA, 2018). By identifying specific activities such as biking, birdwatching, hiking, and photography, this question links respondents' behaviors to the direct and indirect benefits derived from Lake Eymir's natural environment. Understanding these activities helps contextualize the perceived value of the lake and supports more accurate assessments of public willingness to pay for its conservation.

Incorporating an activity-based question also facilitates the assessment of use values within the broader framework of ecosystem service valuation. By understanding which activities are most frequently performed, researchers can infer the relative importance of Lake Eymir's various features, such as trails, reedbeds, and forested areas. Additionally, activities like fishing and foraging overlap with provisioning services, highlighting the multifunctionality of the lake's ecosystems. This holistic view is critical for developing sustainable management strategies that balance recreational use with conservation goals.

The activity data will also support clustering and segmentation analyses, revealing patterns in how different user groups engage with the lake. This can inform targeted

interventions to enhance visitor experiences while safeguarding the area's ecological health. Ultimately, the activities question not only quantifies recreational engagement but also highlights the interconnectedness of ecosystem services, offering a nuanced perspective on Lake Eymir's value to its stakeholders.

4.1.6 WTP Question

Question 11 represents the core of this survey, designed to assess respondents' Willingness to Pay (WTP) for the conservation of Lake Eymir. This question follows the established best practices in contingent valuation methods (CVM) by presenting a carefully constructed hypothetical scenario, emphasizing the urgency and specificity of the payment context. Hypothetical scenarios are a cornerstone of WTP questions, allowing respondents to consider a realistic but controlled situation in which their financial contribution would directly impact the preservation of the resource being valued (Carson & Hanemann, 2005). Such hypothetical scenarios are essential in WTP studies, as they enable the valuation of non-market goods like ecosystem services in the absence of actual market transactions and elicit meaningful and informed responses that reflect respondents' true economic preferences.

In this survey, the scenario explicitly states that the funds collected would be used exclusively for the protection of Lake Eymir's wetland, forest, and lake ecosystems, as well as its biodiversity and recreational opportunities. To ensure the credibility of the scenario, it is also made clear that the lake would face significant threats if funding were insufficient. This direct and focused framing is critical for reducing ambiguity and minimizing potential biases, ensuring that respondents understand the real-life implications of their payment and avoid various hypothetical bias (Carson, 2012).

The question uses an entry fee as the payment vehicle, which is widely considered the most appropriate option for ecosystem service valuation in natural recreational areas. Entry fees are familiar and relatable to most respondents, as they reflect a

direct, site-specific mechanism for generating revenue. The choice of payment vehicle can significantly influence respondents' answers, as alternatives like voluntary donations may lead to over- or understatement due to their non-binding nature (Champ and Bishop, 2001), while taxes may evoke protest responses or strategic bias stemming from their broader socio-political implications. By selecting an entry fee, this survey aligns with best practices for valuing ecosystem services in recreational contexts, where the payment is closely tied to the use and preservation of the resource.

The answers were collected using the payment card method, where respondents choose from a range of predefined monetary amounts. This method offers several advantages over open-ended WTP questions. It mimics the cognitive process of shopping, where individuals compare and select prices, making it easier for respondents to express their preferences (Bateman et al., 2002). Additionally, the payment card method minimizes the risk of strategic over- or underreporting by providing a structured set of options, reducing respondent uncertainty and cognitive load.

By combining a well-designed hypothetical scenario, an appropriate payment vehicle, and the payment card method, this question ensures the collection of robust and reliable WTP data. These methodological choices enhance the credibility of the responses and allow for more accurate estimation of the monetary value assigned by respondents to Lake Eymir's ecosystem services.

4.1.7 Certainty Question

Question 12 is a follow up question to the WTP question to overcome hypothetical bias. It aims to measure respondents' confidence in their stated willingness to pay. This certainty scale, ranging from 1 (very uncertain) to 10 (very certain), is a method introduced by Champ and Bishop (2001) to address potential biases in WTP responses. Certainty questions are often employed in contingent valuation studies to

gauge the reliability of respondents' answers and identify cases where reported WTP values may not accurately reflect genuine preferences.

This precautionary measure is particularly valuable for minimizing distortions caused by extreme values—either excessively low or high responses—that could otherwise compromise the validity of the data (Champ et al., 2003). Methods such as cheap talk scripts, which explain potential biases before the survey, or pledging mechanisms, where respondents commit to their stated values, are alternative approaches to mitigating bias. However, for this survey, the certainty question was chosen as it aligns well with the cultural structure of Turkish society, where direct measures of confidence are more likely to resonate with respondents and produce actionable insights.

Although the certainty data were collected, they were not directly used in the final analysis, as the responses in this study were generally free from distortion. Most respondents reported high certainty levels (7–8 or above), and the dataset did not exhibit extreme WTP values that would necessitate corrective actions such as response removal. This reflects the reliability of the survey design and the sincerity of the participants' answers, mitigating the need for additional adjustments.

The inclusion of the certainty question demonstrates a commitment to methodological rigor, ensuring the quality and robustness of the data. While not utilized in this study's final analysis, it remains a precautionary tool to safeguard against potential biases, ready to be applied if extreme or uncertain responses were to occur. The specifics of this question's results and their implications are discussed in greater detail in the data analysis chapter.

4.1.8 Protest Bids Question

Question 13 was designed to address the potential issue of payment vehicle bias in the WTP responses by eliciting the underlying reasons behind respondents selecting a zero value for their WTP. Payment vehicle bias can arise when respondents object

to the mechanism through which payments are collected (Morrison et al., 2000). Identifying and categorizing these objections, commonly referred to as protest bids, is critical to ensuring the validity of the valuation data. As Morrison et al. (2000) emphasize, protest responses often stem from perceptions that the payment mechanism is implausible, inequitable, or inadequately justified—factors which can distort WTP estimates if not properly addressed.

This question provides respondents with a list of predefined reasons for selecting a zero WTP, divided into protest zero bidders and non-protest zero bidders, though these classifications are not visible to the respondents. The rationale for this distinction lies in its implications for data analysis. Protest zero bids reflect objections to the payment mechanism or the concept of monetizing nature, whereas non-protest zero bids represent genuine valuations where respondents ascribe no monetary value to the ecosystem service (Morrison et al., 2000; Meyerhoff and Liebe 2006; Frey and Pirscher, 2019).

- Non-protest zero bidders: Responses such as “I cannot afford to pay any amount” or “Lake Eymir is not worth anything to me” reflect a true zero valuation, either due to financial constraints or a lack of perceived value. These responses are typically retained in the analysis as they represent valid expressions of preferences.
- Protest zero bidders: Responses like “Lake Eymir should be funded by the government and with tax money” or “Payments should be made on a voluntary basis and/or with donations” signal objections to the payment vehicle rather than the service itself. These responses are often excluded from WTP estimations to avoid inflating the incidence of zero bids and distorting the results.
- Ethical protest zero bidders: The response “Lake Eymir is important to me, but I refuse to put a financial value on it” captures ethical objections to commodifying nature. Such responses are considered distinct from

traditional protest bids as they reflect deep-seated beliefs about the intrinsic value of nature rather than objections to the payment vehicle.

This classification ensures that zero bids are appropriately interpreted during data analysis. By distinguishing between protest and non-protest zero bidders, this question helps to refine the dataset and improve the accuracy of WTP estimates. In this study, the results of Question 13 were analyzed to identify and exclude protest zero bidders where appropriate, ensuring that the final valuation reflects genuine preferences and not biases related to the payment vehicle or survey design.

4.1.9 Ecosystem Services Importance Rating

Question 14 adapts the approach used in economic WTP analysis for typical products to the context of ecosystem services. In this question, respondents are asked to rate the importance of various ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important). This method allows the study to assess the perceived value of the ecosystem's attributes, similar to how consumers evaluate the features of a product in traditional economic analysis (Hanley et al., 2001). By treating ecosystem services as "attributes" and evaluating their relative importance, this question bridges ecological processes and human preferences.

In this question, Lake Eymir is conceptualized as a "product," with its ecosystem services serving as attributes that contribute to its overall value. This approach aligns with choice modeling, which is widely used in environmental valuation to elicit preferences for specific ecosystem features by treating them as distinct components of a good (Hanley et al., 2001).

The list of ecosystem services was carefully selected to reflect the diversity of services provided by Lake Eymir's wetland, grassland, steppe, water, and forest ecosystems. Additionally, the selection was informed by established frameworks in the literature, including the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA) and the European Union's Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services

(CICES), both of which provide standardized categories for ecosystem services. These frameworks ensure consistency in how ecosystem services are identified and classified, enhancing the rigor and comparability of the study. Services such as air quality maintenance, carbon storage, and climate regulation capture the lake's role in regulating atmospheric processes, while freshwater supply, foraging, erosion control, and pollination highlight its provisioning and regulating functions. Cultural heritage, recreational activities, and inspirational/aesthetic/scenic benefits represent its contributions to cultural ecosystem services, while foundational processes like nutrient cycling, soil formation, and primary production underscore its supporting services.

The alphabetical ordering of items avoids introducing implicit biases regarding the importance of any particular service, ensuring that respondents evaluate each service independently. This rating-based design is particularly effective for identifying the relative importance of different ecosystem services to respondents, providing insights into societal priorities and preferences. For example, higher ratings for cultural or recreational services may suggest the prominence of Lake Eymir's cultural and leisure values, while higher ratings for regulating services could reflect awareness of its ecological importance in mitigating climate change and natural hazards.

This method contributes to the broader framework of ecosystem service valuation by incorporating subjective perceptions into the analysis. Unlike monetary WTP questions, which focus on respondents' financial contributions, this question provides a non-monetary measure of importance, making it accessible to individuals across diverse socioeconomic backgrounds. The results from this question will inform subsequent analyses by identifying which services are most valued by respondents and which may require greater emphasis in conservation efforts.

By treating ecosystem services as "attributes" and evaluating their relative importance, this question provides a nuanced understanding of Lake Eymir's multifaceted contributions to human well-being. It demonstrates how attribute-based

approaches, such as choice modeling, can be effectively adapted for ecosystem service valuation.

4.1.10 Values Question

This question is designed to explore respondents' underlying environmental values, which are key concepts in environmental economics and environmental ethics and philosophy. The statements presented in this section aim to elicit the significance that respondents ascribe to Lake Eymir, encompassing both use and non-use values, as well as instrumental and intrinsic values. These values represent distinct perspectives on the importance of natural resources and ecosystems, reflecting not only direct and indirect benefits but also ethical and philosophical considerations regarding nature's inherent worth.

Statement 1: Use Value and Instrumental Value

“It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected because I directly benefit from it.”

This statement is designated to capture use value, which refers to the tangible benefits that individuals derive from directly engaging with the lake, such as recreation, education, or resource utilization. The concept of instrumental value is also embedded here, as the lake is viewed as a means to fulfill human needs and well-being. This reflects anthropocentric tendencies, where nature is primarily valued for its utility to humans rather than for its intrinsic worth.

Statement 2: Option Value and Instrumental Value

“It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected, as I might benefit from it in the future, even if I do not currently benefit from it.”

This statement introduces option value, which reflects the potential future benefits of preserving an ecosystem, even if those benefits are not currently realized. Like the

first statement, it is tied to instrumental value, as the emphasis remains on the lake's utility, albeit deferred to a future time.

Statement 3: Non-Use (Bequest) Value and Instrumental Value

“It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected for future generations whether I benefit from it or not.”

This statement captures bequest value, a form of non-use value, where individuals ascribe importance to preserving the lake for the benefit of future generations, independent of their own use. Bequest value is a cornerstone of environmental economics, highlighting intergenerational equity and ethical responsibility. The instrumental value component remains evident here, as the motivation is rooted in ensuring that future humans can derive utility from the lake.

Statement 4: Non-Use (Existence) Value and Intrinsic Value

“It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected because it should exist, regardless of whether people benefit from it or not.”

This statement delves into existence value, a form of non-use value where individuals place importance on the mere existence of an ecosystem, independent of any direct or indirect benefits. Existence value reflects an ethical or emotional stance that nature has worth beyond human utility. In environmental economics, this perspective is significant because it acknowledges values that are not captured through market transactions or direct use. The statement also hints at intrinsic value, which is rooted in environmental ethics. Respondents who agree with this item likely possess a deep ecological awareness or biocentric worldview, emphasizing the moral responsibility to conserve ecosystems like Lake Eymir for their own sake, even in the absence of tangible human benefits.

This question structure allows the survey to measure a spectrum of values, from utilitarian perspectives focused on human benefits to more ecocentric views that recognize the intrinsic worth of nature. By presenting these statements, the survey captures a comprehensive understanding of respondents' environmental attitudes,

encompassing both anthropocentric and biocentric perspectives. The results from this question will help elucidate the motivational underpinnings of WTP responses, providing a deeper context for interpreting the economic and ethical dimensions of Lake Eymir's valuation.

4.2 Sampling And Survey Administration

The survey was conducted online using Google Forms as the primary tool, and it was distributed through various platforms, including social media, email, WhatsApp, and Telegram groups. The target population for this study was the residents of Ankara, with a total population of 5,803,482 as reported by the Turkish Statistical Institute (TUİK) in 2023. The sampling universe reflects this population figure, and the study employed a simple random sampling method to select participants.

The survey aimed to achieve a 95% confidence level with a 5% confidence interval, which requires a minimum sample size of 385 respondents, based on a Z-score of 1.96. Through the online distribution of the survey, approximately 1,500 individuals were reached, resulting in 420 valid responses. This exceeds the required sample size, ensuring the statistical reliability of the results. However, some limitations in the sampling process should be noted.

Due to the online nature of the survey and its reliance on digital platforms, the sample did not represent all districts or demographic groups in Ankara uniformly. The survey primarily reached educated individuals and professionals, reflecting a higher socio-economic profile. Certain sections of the questionnaire involved technical and specific concepts related to environmental and scientific issues, which may have been less accessible to individuals with lower educational backgrounds or socio-economic status. This limitation is acknowledged as a potential source of bias in the representativeness of the sample, as it deviates from the ideal door-to-door random sampling method.

To ensure ethical compliance, the study received ethical approval from the METU Human Research Ethical Committee on 18 January 2024 (Appendix D). The survey was conducted over a two-month period, starting on 5 February 2024 and concluding on 3 April 2024, with the final responses being accepted on the last day.

4.3 Survey Results

4.3.1 Data Analysis

4.3.1.1 Software Tool Choice

The data analysis section is a critical component of this research, providing empirical insights from survey data to address the study's objectives. This chapter details the statistical methods applied, the rationale for their selection, and the tools employed to process and interpret the data. Given the significance of survey responses as the primary data source, the analytical framework is designed to evaluate trends, relationships, and hypotheses rigorously, ensuring alignment with the research objectives.

The analysis of the survey data was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26. This decision was informed by several methodological considerations that make SPSS particularly suitable for the structure and goals of the research. The choice of SPSS 26 ensures compatibility with the study's analytical needs, leveraging features such as advanced bootstrap techniques and refined statistical algorithms (IBM Corp., 2019).

SPSS offers a robust framework for managing survey data, which often consists of a mix of variable types, including numeric, ordinal, and categorical data (Pallant, 2020). This capability is crucial for this study, which analyzes responses such as Willingness to Pay (WTP) values, Likert-scale ratings, and activity participation.

Additionally, SPSS provides comprehensive statistical capabilities, facilitating basic descriptive analysis as well as advanced methods like regression modeling, clustering, and hypothesis testing (Field, 2018). These tools were instrumental in achieving the study's objectives, including identifying predictors of WTP, segmenting respondents based on demographic and behavioral characteristics, and exploring relationships between variables.

SPSS' dataset management features, such as variable labeling, value coding, and transformation, streamlined the preparation of a dataset that included recoded WTP values, activities, and Likert-scale responses. Another critical advantage of SPSS is its capacity for clear and precise dataset design. For instance, variable labeling, value coding, and handling of missing data are streamlined within the software, which was particularly beneficial for this study. These features were employed to maintain clarity in the dataset, such as in the recoding of WTP values and activities, as well as in the assignment of value labels for ecosystem service importance ratings.

The software's visualization tools enable the effective communication of complex data. Its ability to generate high-quality histograms, scatterplots, and boxplots allowed for the clear presentation of survey findings. Compared to alternative tools like R or Python, SPSS combines advanced statistical capabilities with an intuitive interface, making it particularly advantageous for managing and analyzing survey-based datasets.

In conclusion, the decision to use SPSS for this research was grounded in its academic rigor, reliability, and suitability for survey-based studies. By leveraging its analytical and visualization capabilities, this study ensures that the interpretation of survey data is both robust and meaningful, contributing to the broader discourse on environmental valuation and public engagement in conservation efforts.

4.3.1.2 Data Entry and Dataset Design

The dataset for this study was constructed based on survey responses collected from 420 participants. To ensure accuracy and consistency in the analysis, a systematic approach was employed for data entry, cleaning, and preparation using SPSS.

4.3.1.2.1 Data Entry

Data entry began with importing the raw survey results into SPSS. Each variable was carefully defined and labeled to facilitate clear interpretation during the analysis. Variables were categorized as scale, ordinal, or nominal, depending on the nature of the data they represented. The dataset comprises 130 variables in total, reflecting various aspects such as demographic information, activity participation, willingness to pay (WTP), ecosystem service importance, and attitudes toward environmental conservation and recoded numeric versions variables in string form.

4.3.1.2.2 Data Cleaning and Preparation

To enhance data usability and compatibility with statistical methods, several preprocessing steps were performed:

4.3.1.2.3 Variable Recoding

Text-based responses for demographic variables, such as gender and employment status, were recoded into numerical or binary values. For example:

Gender was recoded as '1' for male and '0' for female.

Employment status was recoded to differentiate between student ('1'), retired ('2'), unemployed ('3') and employed ('4') categories.

Text-based responses for activity participation were recoded into binary variables, where '1' indicated participation in the activity and '0' indicated non-participation.

The WTP variable was recoded to distinguish between valid zero values, protest zero values, and non-zero responses. Specifically:

'0' for valid zero responses.

'-1' for protest zero responses (excluded from further analysis).

'101' for WTP values above 100 TRY. Rationale behind setting this value as 101 is explained in the subsequent chapters.

4.3.1.2.4 Missing Data Handling

Responses marked as "No Opinion" in certain Likert-scale questions or the questions left unanswered, were recoded as missing values to avoid distortion in statistical analyses.

To exclude the protest zero bids from the WTP answers, a filter was created in SPSS and it was activated and deactivated when necessary.

4.3.1.2.5 Clustering Preparation

Additional variables were derived to support clustering analysis. For instance, binary activity variables were combined with demographic information and WTP to identify distinct respondent segments.

4.3.1.2.6 Variable Names and Labels

Each variable was assigned a concise yet descriptive name, and detailed labels were provided for clarity. For example, variables representing attitudes toward environmental protection included the full survey statements in their labels.

4.3.1.2.7 Dataset Overview

The final dataset was organized with clear definitions for all variables, allowing for efficient data exploration and analysis. A portion of the SPSS variable view screen is provided below (Figure 4.1) to illustrate the structure of the dataset, including variable names, types, and measurement scales.

Figure 4.1: A portion of Variable View of the Dataset from SPSS

By adhering to this structured approach, the dataset was prepared to support advanced statistical analyses, including descriptive statistics, regression modeling, and clustering techniques. This rigorous design ensures the reliability and validity of the results presented in this thesis.

4.3.1.3 Descriptive Analysis

4.3.1.3.1 Demographic Analysis

The demographic characteristics of the survey respondents provide essential context for understanding the representativeness and reliability of the data. The analysis examines key variables, including age, monthly household income, gender, education level, employment status, district of residence, and affiliation with Middle

East Technical University (METU). This section outlines the descriptive statistics for each demographic variable and their interpretations.

4.3.1.3.1.1 Monthly Household Income

The average monthly household income among respondents was 74,295.81 TRY, with a median income of 60,000.00 TRY (Table 4.1). The mode, representing the most frequently reported income, was 50,000.00 TRY. These findings indicate a slight right skew in the distribution, as the mean exceeds the median. The range of household income was substantial, spanning from 10,000 TRY to 400,000 TRY, with a standard deviation of 54,188.99 TRY. This high variance suggests considerable income heterogeneity within the respondent group, reflecting diverse economic backgrounds. The distribution of income was positively skewed (Skewness=2.311, SE=0.119), indicating a concentration of respondents in the lower to middle-income categories, with fewer high-income outliers. Additionally, the kurtosis (Kurtosis=7.422, SE=0.238) suggests a leptokurtic distribution, characterized by a sharp peak and heavy tails. These results highlight significant variability in household income among respondents.

Income disparities could influence respondents' willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem services, aligning with findings in environmental economics where income significantly affects WTP (Carson & Hanemann, 2005).

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Monthly Household Income

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	74295.81
Std. Error of Mean	2644.152
Median	60000.00
Mode	50000
Std. Deviation	54188.995
Variance	2936447154.457
Skewness	2.311
Std. Error of Skewness	.119
Kurtosis	7.422
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.238
Range	390000
Minimum	10000
Maximum	400000

The distribution of monthly household income among survey respondents is presented in Figure 4.2. The data exhibit a clear right-skewed distribution, with the majority of households earning between 10,000 and 100,000 TRY per month. The most frequently reported income bracket aligns with the mode, which was previously identified as 50,000 TRY.

Figure 4.2: Histogram of Monthly Household Income

The mean monthly income (74,295.81 TRY) is notably higher than the median (60,000.00 TRY), reflecting the presence of a small number of high-income households, which skew the distribution. The standard deviation of 54,188.99 TRY indicates significant variability in income levels across respondents.

The right-skewed distribution is consistent with income disparity trends commonly observed in economic studies, where higher-income respondents are fewer in number but can disproportionately affect measures of central tendency. Future analyses should consider the impact of these outliers on willingness-to-pay (WTP) results and other economic indicators.

4.3.1.3.1.2 Age

The respondents' ages ranged from 18 to 71 years, with a mean age of 34.46 years and a median of 34.50 years (Table 4.2). The mode, indicating the most frequently reported age, was 35 years. These measures suggest a relatively symmetrical

distribution of ages, with the standard deviation of 10.27 years reflecting a moderate spread around the mean. Such a distribution allows for a balanced representation of different age groups, which is particularly valuable for capturing potential generational differences in the perception and valuation of ecosystem services. By including both younger and older individuals, the survey provides a more comprehensive understanding of how attitudes toward environmental conservation may vary across age cohorts.

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics for Age

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	34.46
Std. Error of Mean	0.386
Median	34.50
Mode	35
Std. Deviation	7.903
Variance	62.459
Skewness	0.699
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119
Kurtosis	1.905
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238
Range	53
Minimum	18
Maximum	71

The distribution exhibited a slight positive skew (Skewness=0.699, E=0.119), indicating a tendency for more respondents to fall below the mean age. The kurtosis (Kurtosis=1.905, SE=0.238) suggests a moderately peaked distribution, reflecting a relatively concentrated age group with a few outliers at either end. These findings

indicate that the respondent pool is predominantly composed of individuals in their early to mid-30s.

A boxplot was created to analyze the distribution of respondents' ages, providing a clear visualization of central tendency and variability (Figure 4.3). The median age is positioned slightly above the center of the interquartile range (IQR), suggesting a near-symmetric distribution with a subtle skew towards younger ages. The IQR spans from approximately 28 to 38 years, capturing the middle 50% of respondents. The whiskers extend from 20 to 48 years, encompassing the majority of non-outlier ages within the sample.

Figure 4.3: Boxplot of Age Distribution

Outliers were identified at both ends of the distribution. On the lower end, a single respondent below the age of 20 was flagged as an outlier. On the upper end, several respondents aged above 48 were marked as outliers, with the oldest respondent being

65 years old. These findings align with the descriptive statistics, which indicate a mean age of 33.5 years and a standard deviation of 9.8 years. The presence of outliers, while anticipated in a dataset covering a wide age range, highlights the diverse demographic composition of the survey sample. This variability enhances the robustness of the analysis by representing a broader spectrum of perspectives across different age groups.

Studies in environmental valuation often highlight the importance of targeting an economically active age group with sufficient awareness and income levels to provide meaningful WTP responses (Barbier et al., 2017). The respondent pool in this study, being predominantly composed of individuals in their early to mid-30s, represents an age group that is often regarded as economically active and environmentally conscious (Dardanoni & Guerriero, 2021), making them particularly suitable for contingent valuation studies.

4.3.1.3.1.3 Gender

In total, 124 females and 283 males participated with valid responses to the survey, while two participants identified as “other” and 11 respondents preferred not to disclose their gender (Figure 4.4). Gender was a key categorical variable, recoded or

analysis where, 1 = Female and 2 = Male. The mode of 2 indicates that males constituted the majority of respondents.

Figure 4.4: Pie Chart of Gender Distribution

While males were more represented in this survey, existing literature suggests that women often demonstrate higher engagement with sustainability issues, potentially influencing their valuation of ecosystem services (Hunter et al., 2004). This gender distribution may provide a balanced perspective on environmental concerns, allowing for comparisons across genders in subsequent analyses.

4.3.1.3.1.4 Education Level

The education levels of respondents revealed valuable insights into the sample's academic background. The mode of 4 corresponds to undergraduate education, indicating that the majority of respondents held a bachelor's degree. Of the 420 valid responses, the mean education level was 4.08 (SD = 1.042), suggesting that most respondents had completed at least a Bachelor's degree or equivalent. The median

and mode were both 4.00, further supporting this observation. Education levels ranged from 1 (high school) to 6 (doctorate), with a variance of 1.087 (Table 4.3).

The distribution of education levels exhibited a slight left skew indicating a higher proportion of respondents with advanced education levels. The kurtosis suggests a distribution with slightly sharper peaks than a normal curve. These findings reflect a well-educated respondent group, potentially influencing their perceptions and willingness to pay.

Table 4.3 Descriptive Statistics for Education Level

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	4.08
Std. Error of Mean	0.051
Median	4.00
Mode	4
Std. Deviation	1.042
Variance	1.087
Skewness	-0.772
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119
Kurtosis	0.978
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238
Range	5
Minimum	1
Maximum	6

The 230 respondents with a bachelor's degree were followed by master's degree holders with 102 respondents that constituted a quarter of the sample (Figure 4.5). These result highlights a generally educated sample, which may positively correlate with awareness and valuation of environmental goods and services (Torgler & García-Valiñas, 2007).

Figure 4.5: Bar Chart of Education Levels

4.3.1.3.1.5 Employment Status

Employment status was another categorical variable analyzed. The distribution revealed a diverse representation of respondents, with categories ranging from full-time employment to unemployment and studentship. Employed respondents amount to 80.94 per cent of the sample with 340 participants, followed by 53 students constituting 12.62% of the survey audience with valid responses (Figure 4.6).

Pie Chart Count of Employment Status

Figure 4.6: Pie Chart of Employment Status

A mean of 3.55, indicates the average employment category, which means a leaning toward full-time employment. Median, 4.00, suggests that at least half of the respondents are in the fourth employment category that is “employed”. This is underlined by mode 4, “employed” being the most frequently occurring employment status. A standard deviation of 1.008, indicating moderate variability among the responses. Variance 1.016 is consistent with the standard deviation. The mode 4 corresponds to employed individuals, suggesting that economic activity is a primary characteristic of the sample (Table 4.4).

Table 4.4 Descriptive Statistics for Employment status

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	3.55
Std. Error of Mean	0.049
Median	4.00
Mode	4
Std. Deviation	1.008
Variance	1.016
Skewness	-2.019
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119
Kurtosis	2.315
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238

4.3.1.3.1.6 District of Residence

Geographical factors, such as district-level characteristics, play a significant role in shaping individuals' willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem services. Differences in socioeconomic conditions, accessibility, and environmental awareness across districts often influence how respondents perceive the value of local ecosystems and their associated benefits (Hanley et al., 2003; Birol et al., 2006). Understanding these regional variations is critical for designing effective policies and interventions that align with local preferences and capabilities.

The mode for the district variable was 7 which represents Çankaya, indicating the most frequently reported area of residence among respondents (Table 4.5). Geographic clustering could provide insights into localized preferences for ecosystem services or environmental concerns.

Table 4.5 Descriptive Statistics of Districts

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Median	7.00 (Çankaya)
Mode	7 (Çankaya)

These findings indicate a fairly diverse geographical representation, with some districts such as Çankaya, Yenimahalle, Keçiören and Etimesgut being more prominently represented than others (Figure 4.7). These insights will be used for extrapolation of the in the subsequent chapters.

Figure 4.7: Bar Chart of Districts

4.3.1.3.1.7 METU Affiliation

The analysis of respondents' affiliation with METU provides insights into the composition of the sample in relation to institutional connections. All 420 responses were valid, with no missing data. The mean affiliation score was 0.44 (SD = 0.497),

indicating that less than half of the respondents reported being affiliated with METU. The median and mode values were both 0, confirming that the majority of respondents were not affiliated with METU. Since affiliation scores were recoded binary, they ranged from 0 to 1 with a variance of 0.247 (Table 4.6).

The distribution was slightly positively skewed (Skewness=0.241, SE=0.119), indicating a slight tendency toward non-affiliation. The kurtosis (Kurtosis=-1.951, SE=0.238) suggests a flat distribution, reflecting a near-equal proportion of affiliated and non-affiliated respondents. These findings highlight the diverse nature of the respondent pool, with a substantial representation of individuals not directly connected to METU.

Table 4.6 Descriptive Statistics of METU Affiliation

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	0.44
Std. Error of Mean	0.024
Median	0.00
Mode	0
Std. Deviation	0.497
Variance	0.247
Skewness	0.241
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119
Kurtosis	-1.951
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238
Range	1
Minimum	0
Maximum	1

The general affiliation with METU was coded as a binary variable (0 = No affiliation, 1 = Affiliated). The mode of 0 demonstrates that most respondents were not affiliated with METU. Among those affiliated, the mode for affiliation type was 4, representing the respondents who was a relative to at least one person that was a student, alumni, academic or administrative staff at METU (Figure 4.8). This breakdown is critical for understanding whether institutional connections influence attitudes toward Lake Eymir. Rather than a single correlation, the effect of METU affiliation was found to have a more significant impact, as indicated by the regression analysis, the results of which will be discussed in the subsequent sections.

Figure 4.8: Bar Chart of Affiliation with METU

4.3.1.3.2 Behavioral and Perceptual Analysis

4.3.1.3.2.1 Visiting Patterns and Frequencies

Visitation patterns are a critical factor in assessing willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem services, as they often reflect the level of interaction and personal connection individuals have with a site (Hanley et al., 2003). Frequent visitors tend

to value ecosystems more highly due to direct experiences and perceived benefits, such as recreation, aesthetic enjoyment, and emotional attachment (Birol et al., 2006). Furthermore, individuals with frequent visitation are more likely to associate ecosystems with cultural and recreational benefits, which significantly influence WTP values (Scholte et al., 2015). Understanding visitation frequency helps contextualize WTP responses, ensuring that valuation captures both use and non-use values (Carson & Hanemann, 2005). Therefore, incorporating visitation frequency into valuation models enhances the robustness of WTP estimates by linking experiential familiarity with expressed economic preferences.

The analysis of respondents' visitation patterns to Lake Eymir in the last 12 months indicates their level of engagement with the ecosystem. Among the 420 valid responses, 1 represented "Yes" (visited), and 0 represented "No" (did not visit). The mean visitation rate was 0.60 (SD = 0.491), suggesting that approximately 60% of respondents had visited the lake during this period (Figure 4.9).

Figure 4.9: Pie Chart of Visitation

Table 4.7 Visit Statistics

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	0.60
Std. Error of Mean	0.024
Median	1.00
Mode	1
Std. Deviation	0.491
Variance	0.242
Skewness	-0.389
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119
Kurtosis	-1.857
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238

These findings highlight a moderate level of engagement with Lake Eymir, with a substantial portion of respondents actively interacting with the site. The most frequent visiting pattern is 1 to 3 times by 42.36% (Figure 4.10).

Figure 4.10: Bar Chart of Visit Frequency

The analysis of visitation frequencies to Lake Eymir reveals important patterns in respondents' engagement with the ecosystem. Among the 420 valid responses, the mean visitation frequency was 0.96, indicating that, on average, respondents visited the lake approximately once in the reference period. The median and mode were both 1.00, suggesting that most respondents visited the lake at least once. The standard deviation was 1.188, reflecting a moderate variation in visitation patterns across the sample.

The data exhibited a positive skew (Skewness=1.834, SE=0.119), indicating that a significant portion of the sample reported infrequent visits, with fewer individuals reporting high visitation rates. The kurtosis (Kurtosis=3.356, SE=0.238) suggests a relatively peaked distribution, highlighting the concentration of responses around certain visitation levels (Table 4.8).

Table 4.8 Visit Frequency Statistics

Valid Responses: 420	
Missing: 0	
Mean	0.96
Std. Error of Mean	0.058
Median	1.00
Mode	1 (1 to 3 times)
Std. Deviation	1.188
Variance	1.411
Skewness	1.834
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119
Kurtosis	3.356
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238
Range	5 (20 or more)
Minimum	0 (Zero times)
Maximum	5 (20 or more)

These findings underscore the diversity in respondent engagement with Lake Eymir, ranging from non-visitors to frequent visitors. Variations in visitation patterns are critical in WTP studies, as direct interaction with ecosystems often enhances perceived benefits and emotional connections, which influence valuation (Scholte et al., 2015). Moreover, frequent visitors tend to place greater importance on recreational and cultural benefits, a pattern consistent with findings from prior research on recreational demand and contingent valuation (See for example Armbrrecht, 2014).

4.3.1.3.2.2 Activities

The analysis of activity participation at Lake Eymir highlights the diverse ways respondents engage with the ecosystem (Figure 4.11). Hiking emerged as the most popular activity, with 44.5% of respondents indicating participation, followed by resting/retreat (38.6%), sightseeing (31.0%), biking (29.0%), and visiting restaurants or cafes (27.1%). These activities reflect a mix of recreational and social engagement, emphasizing the multifunctionality of the lake as both a natural and social space.

Figure 4.11: Activities

The participation patterns observed at Lake Eymir demonstrate its multifunctional role as a provider of recreational and cultural ecosystem services. Hiking, the most popular activity, highlights the site's value for physical recreation, while activities such as sightseeing and resting emphasize its importance as a space for relaxation and aesthetic enjoyment. The high participation in outdoor activities like hiking and biking underscores the significance of physical recreation as a key motivator for visitation. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that recreational opportunities are a major factor in the value individuals assign to natural

environments (Sullivan et al., 2004; Chiesura, 2004). Social and cultural activities, such as resting and visiting restaurants or cafes, further highlight Lake Eymir's role as a communal gathering space and contributor to cultural ecosystem service value (Scholte et al., 2015).

Activities such as Education/Science (1.43%), Cycle Boating (0.95%), and Fishing (0.95%) had low participation rates, reflecting niche interests or limited accessibility. Activities with higher mean participation tend to have smaller standard errors, suggesting consistent preferences among respondents (Table 4.9). In other words, higher participation activities demonstrated smaller standard errors, indicating consistent preferences among respondents, while niche activities exhibited greater variability. Conversely, niche activities like education/science and fishing had low participation rates, suggesting limited appeal or accessibility. These niche activities, despite their low mean participation, may appeal strongly to specific subgroups, such as researchers, environmental enthusiasts or hobbyists.

These patterns of activity participation are critical for understanding respondents' willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem conservation. Previous research has shown that individuals who engage directly with recreational and cultural ecosystem services tend to report higher WTP, as their interactions foster a deeper appreciation for the benefits of the site (Birol et al., 2006; Loomis and Extrand, 1998). By linking activity participation to ecosystem value, this analysis might help providing a foundation for exploring how different user groups perceive and prioritize conservation efforts.

Table 4.9 Activity Statistics

	Art and Cultural Activities	Biking	Birdwatching or other wildlife and nature observation	Cycle Boating	Education/ Science	Fishing
Mean	0.03	0.29	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01
Std. Error of Mean	0.008	0.022	0.009	0.005	0.006	0.005
Median	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mode	0	0	0	0	0	0
Std. Deviation	0.167	0.455	0.192	0.097	0.119	0.097
Variance	0.028	0.207	0.037	0.009	0.014	0.009
Skewness	5.680	0.926	4.843	10.136	8.216	10.136
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119
Kurtosis	30.404	-1.147	21.560	101.225	65.810	101.225
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238
Range	1	1	1	1	1	1
Minimum	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 4.9 Activity Statistics Part-2

	Foraging	Sight seeing	Socializing	Special event	Sports and training	Visiting restaurants and cafes
Mean	0.00	0.31	0.22	0.03	0.09	0.27
Std. Error of Mean	0.000	0.023	0.020	0.008	0.014	0.022
Median	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mode	0	0	0	0	0	0
Std. Deviation	0.000	0.463	0.417	0.167	0.287	0.445
Variance	0.000	0.214	0.174	0.028	0.082	0.198
Skewness		0.827	1.330	5.680	2.865	1.032
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119
Kurtosis		-1.322	-0.232	30.404	6.240	-0.940
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238
Range	0	1	1	1	1	1
Minimum	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum	0	1	1	1	1	1

Table 4.9. Activity Statistics Part-3

	Hiking	Photography	Picnic	Resting/ retreat	Rowing
Mean	0.45	0.12	0.13	0.39	0.01
Std. Error of Mean	0.024	0.016	0.017	0.024	0.006
Median	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mode	0	0	0	0	0
Std. Deviation	0.498	0.324	0.340	0.487	0.119
Variance	0.248	0.105	0.116	0.238	0.014
Skewness	0.221	2.361	2.165	0.471	8.216
Std. Error of Skewness	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119	0.119
Kurtosis	-1.960	3.592	2.700	-1.786	65.810
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238	0.238
Range	1	1	1	1	1
Minimum	0	0	0	0	0
Maximum	1	1	1	1	1

4.3.1.3.2.3 Willingness to Pay (WTP)

4.3.1.3.2.3.1 Handling “Above 100 TRY” Responses

In contingent valuation studies, open-ended responses such as "Above 100 TRY" present a challenge when calculating summary statistics and extrapolating willingness to pay (WTP) to the broader population. While such responses indicate a minimum willingness to pay (at least 100 TRY), the exact value remains unknown, necessitating careful handling to avoid bias in the results. This section discusses the methodology adopted to address this issue, supported by sensitivity analysis to illustrate the impact of different assumptions on the results.

The "Above 100 TRY" responses were recorded as 101 TRY during the survey data entry to denote that respondents were willing to pay at least 100 TRY but did not specify an upper limit. For analysis, three scenarios were considered:

- i) **Conservative Approach:** Retaining the 101 TRY value as is.
- ii) **Midpoint Approach:** Assigning 150 TRY, representing the midpoint between 100 TRY and an assumed upper limit of 200 TRY.
- iii) **Adjusted Approach:** Assigning 120 TRY as a moderate adjustment to reflect a likely higher WTP value while maintaining conservatism.

The primary analysis used the conservative approach, while sensitivity analysis was performed using the midpoint and adjusted approaches to evaluate the robustness of the results.

The sensitivity analysis results are summarized in Table 4.10 below:

Table 4.10 Sensitivity Analysis Results

Scenario	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Keep as 101	48.64	50.00	29.62	0.57	-0.69
Midpoint 150	51.53	50.00	36.25	1.19	0.97
Adjusted 120	49.76	50.00	31.86	0.75	-0.33

The conservative approach (101 TRY) yielded a mean WTP of 48.64 TRY, with a moderate positive skewness of 0.57 and kurtosis of -0.69, indicating a flatter distribution. This approach minimizes the risk of overestimating WTP and aligns with standard practices in contingent valuation (Carson & Hanemann, 2005). However, it likely underestimates the true WTP for the "Above 100 TRY" group.

The midpoint approach (150 TRY) increased the mean to 51.53 TRY and significantly increased skewness (1.19) and kurtosis (0.97), suggesting a more peaked and right-skewed distribution. This approach may better reflect the higher WTP of these respondents but involves an assumption about the upper limit.

The adjusted approach (120 TRY) balanced conservatism and realism, resulting in a mean WTP of 49.76 TRY, with skewness (0.75) and kurtosis (-0.33) closer to normal.

Therefore, for the primary analysis, the conservative approach was adopted, retaining the "Above 100 TRY" responses as 101 TRY. This decision ensures transparency and minimizes bias, aligning with the principle of conservative estimates in economic valuation (Bateman et al., 2002). The sensitivity analysis demonstrated that while alternative assumptions affect the mean and distribution characteristics, they do not significantly alter the central tendencies (e.g., median) or overall conclusions.

Future surveys should explicitly request respondents to specify an upper limit for open-ended ranges to reduce uncertainty. Meanwhile, presenting these alternative scenarios provides readers with a comprehensive view of potential variations, enhancing the robustness and credibility of the findings.

After filtering out protest zeros and recoding the "Above 100 TRY" responses to 101 TRY, the descriptive statistics for WTP among the 373 valid respondents are summarized in Table 4.11 below:

Table 4.11 WTP Statistics

Valid Responses: 373	
Missing: 0	
	<i>TRY</i>
Mean	48.64
Std. Error of Mean	1.533
Median	50.00
Mode	50
Std. Deviation	29.616
Variance	877.097
Skewness	0.570
Std. Error of Skewness	0.126
Kurtosis	-0.692
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.252
Range	101
Minimum: 0, Maximum:101	

The mean WTP of 48.64 TRY indicates the average amount respondents are willing to pay, while the median WTP of 50.00 TRY demonstrates that half of the respondents are willing to pay at least this amount. The mode WTP of 50 TRY, representing the most frequently chosen value, aligns closely with the median, suggesting a central tendency around this amount.

The standard deviation of 29.62 TRY and a variance of 877.10 reflect moderate dispersion in WTP values. This variability indicates that while most respondents cluster around the central values (e.g., 50 TRY), there are notable deviations, particularly at the lower and upper ends of the distribution.

The skewness value of 0.57 reveals a moderate positive skew, indicating a slight rightward tail in the distribution. This suggests that while most WTP values are clustered near the center, some respondents reported relatively higher WTP values (e.g., 101 TRY). The positive skew is typical for WTP studies, where some participants may indicate a stronger preference or higher ability to pay.

The kurtosis value of -0.69 indicates a slightly platykurtic distribution, characterized by a flatter peak and thinner tails compared to a normal distribution. This result suggests that the distribution of WTP is relatively even without extreme concentration or dispersion of values.

The alignment of the mean, median, and mode reflects a consistent central tendency, suggesting that the majority of respondents are willing to pay around 50 TRY for the good or service in question. However, the positive skew implies that a smaller subset of respondents is willing to pay significantly more, as captured by the recoded value of 101 TRY. This variability underscores the importance of considering both central tendencies and distributional characteristics in policy-making and economic valuation (Mitchell & Carson, 1989).

By recoding the "Above 100 TRY" responses conservatively as 101 TRY, the analysis ensures that the reported results are robust and defensible, providing a

conservative estimate of WTP while acknowledging the heterogeneity among respondents.

A bar chart of the distribution of WTP answers is demonstrated in Figure 4.12 below:

Figure 4.12: Bar Chart of WTP

The bar chart provides a clear visualization of the frequency distribution for Willingness to Pay (WTP) categories. Each bar represents the number of respondents selecting a specific WTP value, with the highest concentration at 50 TRY, accounting for 33.8% of all responses. This distribution highlights a strong central tendency, as the majority of respondents clustered around common values such as 10 TRY, 20 TRY, 30 TRY, and 50 TRY, with fewer outliers at the extremes.

The chart also incorporates percentage tags above each bar, providing additional context on the relative proportions of each category. This helps illustrate the skewed nature of the data, as a smaller subset of respondents selected values at the higher end (e.g., 100 TRY and "Above 100 TRY").

The histogram (Figure 4.13) offers a complementary visualization, showing the continuous distribution of WTP values across categories. Vertical dashed lines denote the mean (48.64 TRY), median (50.00 TRY), and mode (50.00 TRY), providing a visual representation of the data's central tendencies.

The shape of the histogram confirms a moderately positively skewed distribution, with a slight tail toward higher WTP values. This skewness reflects the presence of outliers (e.g., "Above 100 TRY") while maintaining a strong peak around 50 TRY. The alignment of the mean, median, and mode further underscores the concentration of responses near the central values, supporting the robustness of the descriptive statistics.

Figure 4.13: Histogram of WTP

4.3.1.3.2.4 Economic Context of the WTP Results

The results of this WTP survey must be interpreted within the broader economic context of Türkiye during February and March 2024, a period marked by significant economic challenges. High inflation and currency depreciation influenced the purchasing power of Turkish citizens, which is crucial for understanding the WTP values expressed during the survey.

During this period, the annual inflation rate rose from 67.07% in February to 68.5% in March (Nasdaq, 2024; Reuters, 2024). These figures reflect ongoing economic instability, further exacerbated by the depreciation of the Turkish lira (TRY), which

averaged approximately 32.5 TRY per U.S. dollar during these months. The volatility in exchange rates and inflation significantly impacted household expenditures, including discretionary spending on ecosystem services.

In response to escalating inflation, the Turkish government raised the monthly minimum wage by 49% in January 2024, setting it at 17,002 TRY (approximately \$523 USD) at the prevailing exchange rate (Reuters, 2023). While this adjustment provided some relief to households, it did not fully offset the rising costs of goods and services, as evidenced by the continued inflationary pressures.

The WTP values expressed by respondents should be interpreted in light of Türkiye's economic conditions at the time. While the mean WTP of 48.64 TRY might appear modest, it represents a meaningful commitment given the constraints imposed by high inflation and limited purchasing power. Adjusted for the minimum wage at the time, the mean WTP accounted for approximately 0.29% of the monthly minimum wage (17,002 TRY). This proportion underscores the relative significance of respondents' willingness to pay, particularly during a period of economic hardship.

Furthermore, when expressed in terms of the U.S. dollar equivalent, the mean WTP was approximately \$1.50 USD (at an exchange rate of 32.5 TRY/USD). While this value may appear small in global terms, it must be contextualized within Türkiye's economic realities, where inflation significantly eroded disposable income.

These findings highlight the resilience of respondents' environmental priorities despite economic challenges. The alignment of the mean, median, and mode around 50 TRY indicates a robust central tendency, reflecting a shared willingness to support ecosystem services even amidst financial constraints. The survey results provide valuable insights into the public's valuation of environmental goods, underscoring the importance of considering local economic conditions in policy development and resource allocation.

4.3.1.3.2.5 Certainty Question

Certainty questions are frequently used in contingent valuation studies to assess the reliability of responses and to identify potentially biased answers for removal (Champ et al., 1997; Loomis & Ekstrand, 1998). However, in this study, the distribution of certainty ratings demonstrates that the majority of respondents were highly confident in their answers, with 61.2% assigning the highest certainty rating (10), and less than 5% rating below 5. This distribution indicates that there are no significant clusters of uncertain responses that could distort the results. Therefore, additional response removal procedures based on certainty ratings are deemed unnecessary.

The analysis of certainty ratings is visually summarized in the frequency distribution chart and the boxplot. The frequency distribution chart (Figure 4.14) highlights that a significant majority of respondents (61.2%) rated their certainty at the highest level (10). Lower certainty ratings (e.g., 1–5) are rare, collectively accounting for less than 10% of the total responses. This distribution demonstrates a clear trend toward high certainty, with minimal variability among respondents.

Figure 4.14: Frequency Distribution of Certainty Ratings

The boxplot (Figure 4.15) further supports this conclusion, illustrating a tight interquartile range (IQR) with a median certainty rating of 10. The absence of significant outliers in the cleaned data reinforces the consistency and reliability of respondents' self-reported certainty levels.

Figure 4.15: Boxplot of Certainty Ratings

The predominantly high-certainty responses in this study confirm the robustness of the dataset and negate the necessity for additional filtering based on low-certainty ratings. This conclusion aligns with findings from similar studies, which emphasize that high respondent certainty reduces the need for stringent data filtration while ensuring data reliability and minimizing the risk of biased or unreliable responses (Champ et al., 1997; Ready et al., 2010).

4.3.1.3.2.6 Zero Bids Question

The reasons for zero bids were analyzed to distinguish between protest zero bids and valid zero bids. This distinction is crucial in contingent valuation studies to ensure accurate Willingness to Pay (WTP) calculations (Meyerhoff & Liebe, 2006). In this study, respondents were given a set of predefined reasons for their zero bids, and these responses were classified as either protest zeros or valid zeros:

Non-protest zero bidders:

"I cannot afford to pay any amount" (2 respondents)

"I don't think protection of Lake Eymir would cost that much" (not selected by any respondent)

"Lake Eymir is not worth anything to me" (1 respondent)

Protest zero bidders:

"Lake Eymir should be funded by the government and with tax money" (37 respondents)

"Payments should be made on a voluntary basis and/or with donations" (4 respondents)

"Lake Eymir is important to me but I refuse to put a financial value on it" (6 respondents, classified as ethical protest zeros).

Of the 48 zero-bid responses, 45 were identified as protest zeros (Figure 4.16). These responses were excluded from the WTP calculation using a filter created in SPSS to ensure only valid zero bids were retained. This approach is consistent with previous studies in contingent valuation, where protest zeros are removed to avoid skewing the results (See for example Jorgensen and Syme, 2000).

Figure 4.16: Reasons for Zero Bids

The majority of zero bids were protest zeros, with "Lake Eymir should be funded by the government and with tax money" being the most common reason (37 respondents). Only 3 valid zero bids were retained in the analysis, representing 0.7% of the total dataset. Of the zero bids, 94% were protest zero bidders while only 6% were valid zero bidders to be taken into account (Figure 4.17).

Proportion of Protest vs Valid Zero Bidders

Figure 4.17: Proportion of Valid and Protest Zero Bidders

This careful filtering ensures that the WTP calculations reflect respondents' true willingness to pay without the influence of protest responses, thereby increasing the reliability of the results.

The analysis of zero-bid responses in the contingent valuation survey reveals that a significant portion of respondents perceive the funding of Lake Eymir's conservation as a governmental responsibility, indicating a reluctance to contribute personally. This perspective may be influenced by perceptions of tax fairness and trust in governmental fiscal policies.

Research indicates that taxpayers' perceptions of tax justice and their trust in government significantly affect tax compliance behaviors. In the Turkish context, a study by Aktaş Güzel et al. (2019) found that trust in government positively influences perceptions of tax justice, which in turn enhances tax compliance. This suggests that when individuals perceive the tax system as fair and trust the government's use of tax revenues, they are more likely to comply voluntarily.

Furthermore, the occurrence of protest zero bids in contingent valuation studies is often associated with respondents' objections to the payment vehicle or the belief that the provision of the good or service should be publicly funded. A review by Rankin and Robinson (2018) highlights that such protest responses are frequently rooted in concerns about taxation and trust in government, rather than a true zero valuation of the good in question.

In the context of this study, the high incidence of protest zero bids reflects a broader public sentiment that environmental preservation, such as that of Lake Eymir, should be financed through existing tax revenues. This aligns with findings that public trust and perceptions of tax fairness are critical determinants of individuals' willingness to contribute beyond mandatory taxation.

Addressing these concerns requires enhancing the perceived fairness of the tax system and building greater trust in governmental fiscal policies. By doing so, it may be possible to foster a more cooperative public attitude toward both tax compliance and voluntary contributions for public goods.

4.3.1.3.2.7 Ecosystem Services Ratings

The analysis of ecosystem service ratings provides insights into respondents' perceptions of their importance. This section interprets the results from the visualizations, reflecting the relative importance and awareness of ecosystem services among survey respondents.

The Figure 4.18 below visualizes the mean importance ratings of individual ecosystem services, revealing that respondents prioritized supporting and regulating services over provisioning services. Specifically, services like water purification, air quality maintenance, and biodiversity conservation received higher mean ratings, reflecting their perceived critical role in sustaining ecosystems and human well-being.

Figure 4.18: Ecosystem Services Importance Ratings

This aligns with previous literature that highlights the often intangible yet vital nature of regulating and supporting services (Costanza et al., 1997). Higher ratings on these services may be attributed to increased awareness of global environmental challenges such as climate change and biodiversity loss.

The Figure 4.19 below highlights the services with the highest number of missing responses, which was coded as “No opinion” in the survey, suggesting areas where respondents felt less informed. Regulating services such as water regulation, and pest and disease control, and supporting services such as soil formation exhibited higher levels of missing responses compared to cultural and supporting services. This could

indicate that respondents perceive these services as less visible or less directly connected to their daily lives.

Figure 4.19: Ecosystem Services “No Opinion” Answers

The high levels of missing responses for provisioning services can be interpreted as the need for improved environmental education and communication strategies to bridge the gap in understanding. Raising awareness about the tangible benefits of these services, such as food and water security, could enhance public appreciation and support for ecosystem management.

Figure 4.20 below aggregates the mean ratings by service categories, based on the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment classification. Supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling, oxygen production) were rated the highest, with an average importance score of 4.40, followed by regulating services (e.g., climate regulation, air quality maintenance) at 4.25. Cultural services (e.g., recreation, education) were moderately high, with an average score of 4.11, while provisioning services (e.g., food, fresh water) were rated the lowest at 3.73.

Figure 4.20: Ecosystem Service Category Ratings

These results suggest that respondents place greater value on services that sustain ecosystem functionality and global ecological balance. In contrast, provisioning services, while essential for survival, might be undervalued due to their perceived abundance or accessibility through markets.

The analysis reveals clear trends in the prioritization and awareness of ecosystem services among respondents. Supporting and regulating services are highly valued, reflecting a recognition of their critical ecological roles. However, the lower importance assigned to provisioning services and the higher missing response rates for some regulating services indicate a gap in understanding that warrants further educational efforts. These findings reinforce the importance of integrating ecosystem service valuation into environmental policies and decision-making processes to ensure balanced conservation and sustainable use.

4.3.1.3.2.8 Values Question

The responses to the value questions in the survey provide rich insights into the diverse ways individuals perceive the worth of Lake Eymir. These perceptions reflect a broad spectrum of value dimensions, including direct, future, generational, and existence benefits, each tied to specific ethical and philosophical underpinnings.

The bar chart below (Figure 4.21), displays the frequencies of responses for the value question categories respectively:

1. Direct Benefit (Use Value & Instrumental Value)
2. Future Benefit (Option Value & Instrumental Value)
3. Generational Benefit (Non-use Value – Bequest Value & Instrumental Value)
4. Existence Benefit (Non-use – Existence & Intrinsic Value)

Figure 4.21: Frequency of Value Question Responses

Responses indicate a moderate emphasis on direct benefit category, reflecting immediate instrumental value derived from direct interaction with the ecosystem (Table 4.12).

Table 4.12 Direct Benefit Frequencies

<i>1.It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected because I directly benefit from it</i>				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	141	33.6	33.6	33.6
Disagree	48	11.4	11.4	45.0
Neutral	79	18.8	18.8	63.8
Strongly agree	113	26.9	26.9	90.7
Strongly disagree	39	9.3	9.3	100.0
Total	420	100.0	100.0	

Higher frequency in the "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" responses in future benefit represents respondents' recognition of potential future utility, aligning with the concept of option value in environmental economics (Table 4.13).

Table 4.13 Future Benefit Frequencies

<i>2.It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected, as I might benefit from it in the future, even if I do not currently benefit from it</i>				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	121	28.8	28.8	28.8
Disagree	35	8.3	8.3	37.1
Neutral	29	6.9	6.9	44.0
Strongly agree	211	50.2	50.2	94.3
Strongly disagree	24	5.7	5.7	100.0
Total	420	100.0	100.0	

The dominant response of "Strongly Agree" in generational benefit underscores a strong non-use value tied to intergenerational equity. This aligns with ethical principles emphasizing the duty to preserve ecosystems for future generations (Table 4.14).

Table 4.14 Generational Benefit Frequencies

<i>3.It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected for future generations whether I benefit from it or not</i>				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	63	15.0	15.0	15.0
Disagree	16	3.8	3.8	18.8
Neutral	7	1.7	1.7	20.5
Strongly agree	308	73.3	73.3	93.8
Strongly disagree	26	6.2	6.2	100.0
Total	420	100.0	100.0	

The final category, existence benefit also shows significant support, reflecting intrinsic value perceptions where ecosystems are valued for their mere existence, independent of direct human use (Table 4.15).

Table 4.15 Existence Value Frequencies

<i>4.It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected because it should exist, regardless of whether people benefit from it or not</i>				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	61	14.5	14.5	14.5
Disagree	16	3.8	3.8	18.3
Neutral	11	2.6	2.6	21.0
Strongly agree	304	72.4	72.4	93.3
Strongly disagree	28	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	420	100.0	100.0	

The bar chart in Figure 4.22 below represents the frequency of responses across each value category.

Figure 4.22: Summary of Value Category Frequencies

Respondents' agreement with statements about direct benefits highlights the importance of instrumental value, where nature is perceived as a means to satisfy human needs and preferences. In the context of environmental valuation, direct benefit responses often serve as a foundation for economic measures like willingness to pay (WTP), which is commonly used in policy design to fund conservation initiatives.

The strong support for future benefits underscores the concept of option value, which represents the potential future utility of an ecosystem, even if it is not currently utilized. This perspective resonates with the precautionary principle, a cornerstone of environmental management, which argues for the conservation of natural resources in the face of uncertainty (UNCED, 1992, Principle 15). The emphasis on

future benefits reflects a pragmatic recognition of the uncertainty inherent in ecological systems and the need to preserve options for future generations. This aligns with the views of Kenneth Arrow and others, who advocate for the inclusion of option value in cost-benefit analyses to account for uncertainties in resource availability (Arrow & Fisher, 1974).

The overwhelming agreement with generational benefits emphasizes the ethical responsibility to preserve ecosystems for the benefit of future generations. This reflects the bequest value, a type of non-use value that underscores the moral obligation of the present generation to act as stewards of natural resources. The philosophical foundation for this perspective is deeply rooted in intergenerational justice, as articulated by Edith Brown Weiss, who argues for the equitable distribution of natural and cultural heritage across generations (Weiss, 1989).

From a practical standpoint, the high support for generational benefits might illustrate the public's alignment with sustainable development principles, as outlined in the Brundtland Report, which emphasizes meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (WCED, 1987). This value is particularly significant in fostering long-term conservation policies that integrate ecological sustainability with economic and social considerations.

The strong support for existence benefits reflects the recognition of ecosystems' intrinsic value, where nature is valued for its mere existence, independent of any human benefit. This perspective is central to deep ecology, a philosophical movement founded by Arne Næss, which emphasizes the intrinsic worth of all forms of life and advocates for a biospheric egalitarianism in which humans are not viewed as superior to other beings (Næss, 1973). Similarly, Aldo Leopold's 'land ethic' calls for an expansion of the moral community to include the land itself—soils, waters, plants, and animals—and urges that actions be judged right when they preserve the integrity, stability, and beauty of the biotic community (Leopold, 1949).

The emphasis on intrinsic value challenges traditional anthropocentric approaches to environmental management by promoting an ecocentric worldview, wherein nature is recognized as morally considerable in its own right. This perspective reflects Holmes Rolston III's view that the natural world possesses inherent worth and deserves ethical regard not because of its utility to humans, but because of its own evolutionary and systemic significance (Rolston, 1988).

The coexistence of instrumental and intrinsic values in the responses highlights the need for a balanced approach to environmental valuation. While instrumental values, such as use and option values, are crucial for quantifying benefits and informing economic policies, intrinsic values provide the ethical foundation for conservation efforts. Ignoring either dimension risks undermining the holistic understanding required for sustainable environmental management.

For instance, conservation policies that focus solely on economic incentives may fail to capture the ethical and cultural significance of ecosystems, leading to inadequate or shortsighted solutions. Conversely, policies that prioritize intrinsic values can foster a deeper sense of stewardship and responsibility, resonating with ethical principles that transcend utilitarian considerations.

The findings from this analysis reflect key debates in environmental philosophy and ethics. The anthropocentric valuation of direct and future benefits contrasts with the ecocentric recognition of generational and existence values. This tension underscores the importance of integrating diverse philosophical perspectives into ecosystem service valuation.

The analysis of value question responses offers profound insights into how individuals perceive and prioritize the different dimensions of ecosystem value. These responses, categorized into direct, future, generational, and existence benefits, highlight the complex interplay between instrumental and intrinsic values in shaping public attitudes toward environmental conservation.

The strong agreement with generational and existence values underscores the deep ethical considerations individuals hold about the protection of ecosystems like Lake Eymir. These non-use values reflect a moral commitment to intergenerational equity and the intrinsic worth of nature, emphasizing the responsibility of current generations to act as stewards for both future humans and the broader ecological community. This perspective aligns with the principles of environmental ethics, where ecosystems are valued not merely for their utility but also for their inherent right to exist and flourish.

At the same time, the responses also reveal the practical recognition of direct and future benefits, where the ecosystem is valued for the tangible and potential services it provides. This anthropocentric view underscores the importance of integrating instrumental values into policy frameworks, ensuring that conservation efforts are aligned with the immediate and long-term needs of society. However, the coexistence of instrumental and intrinsic values in the responses suggests that effective environmental management cannot rely solely on economic measures or ethical principles in isolation. Instead, a balanced approach is necessary, one that acknowledges the multifaceted nature of ecosystem value.

From a policy perspective, these findings carry significant implications. Recognizing the public's strong support for non-use values, such as bequest and existence values, highlights the need to incorporate ethical considerations into conservation strategies. Policies that prioritize ecological integrity, even in the absence of direct economic benefits, are more likely to resonate with societal values and garner broader support. Conversely, the recognition of instrumental values underscores the importance of designing economic incentives, such as payment for ecosystem services (PES) schemes, to fund conservation efforts sustainably.

Moreover, the philosophical and ethical insights gained from this analysis have broader relevance in shaping global environmental governance. The acknowledgment of intrinsic value, as reflected in existence benefits, aligns with international initiatives like the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the

United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which emphasize the protection of biodiversity and ecosystems as a universal responsibility. By integrating these global commitments with local perceptions of value, policymakers can develop conservation strategies that are not only contextually relevant but also globally impactful.

The findings also highlight the critical role of education and public engagement in fostering a deeper understanding of ecosystem values. As seen in the survey responses, gaps in awareness about certain value dimensions, such as direct benefits, suggest the need for targeted educational initiatives to bridge these gaps. By enhancing public awareness of the diverse benefits ecosystems provide, such initiatives can cultivate a more informed and proactive citizenry, capable of advocating for sustainable environmental practices.

Ultimately, this analysis reinforces the interconnectedness of ecological, economic, and ethical dimensions in environmental conservation. Ecosystems like Lake Eymir are not just sources of goods and services but also repositories of cultural, moral, and existential significance. Recognizing and respecting these diverse values is essential for fostering a sustainable relationship between humans and the natural world. By embracing a holistic approach that integrates instrumental and intrinsic values, policymakers, researchers, and communities can work together to ensure the preservation of ecosystems for present and future generations.

This nuanced understanding of ecosystem valuation serves as a vital foundation for advancing sustainable development and environmental stewardship. As the challenges of climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource depletion continue to intensify, the integration of diverse value dimensions into conservation policies will become increasingly imperative. The findings of this study contribute to this broader effort, offering a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing the complex interplay of values that underpin human-environment interactions.

The results, once again, further underlined that intrinsic and instrumental values represent two complementary dimensions of environmental valuation. Instrumental

values provide a pragmatic framework for quantifying and communicating the benefits of ecosystems to humans, while intrinsic values emphasize the moral and ethical responsibilities toward nature. A comprehensive approach to conservation integrates both perspectives, ensuring that ecosystems are protected not only for their utility but also for their inherent worth. This dual recognition fosters sustainable and equitable environmental policies, bridging the gap between ecological integrity and human well-being.

4.3.1.4 Cluster Analysis of Respondent Segmentation

Environmental economics and philosophy often grapple with the question of how individuals and communities assign value to natural resources. These values—be they utilitarian, intrinsic, or future-oriented—shape behaviors and preferences, especially when natural resources are finite and under threat. Lake Eymir, the subject of this study, represents a case where competing interests and value systems converge, making it a fertile ground for segmentation analysis.

Clustering techniques provide a robust framework for revealing hidden patterns in datasets. K-means clustering, in particular, allows us to group individuals with similar preferences, behaviors, and demographic characteristics. By understanding these clusters, policymakers can design interventions that cater to each group's unique priorities, fostering a more inclusive and effective approach to resource management. For instance, economic valuation frameworks such as contingent valuation often rely on segmentation to understand willingness-to-pay (WTP) for non-market goods like clean water or biodiversity (Bateman et al., 2002).

The philosophical undertones of this analysis also deserve mention. Clustering reveals more than just statistical groupings; it exposes the diversity in how people perceive their relationship with nature. Such insights are crucial for aligning environmental policies with societal values.

4.3.1.4.1 Methodology

A k-means clustering algorithm was employed to segment the survey respondents into three clusters. The choice of three clusters was guided by preliminary analyses, which balanced interpretability and statistical robustness. Variables were standardized to ensure comparability across different scales. Key variables included:

Demographics: Age, income, gender.

Behavioral indicators: Participation in activities like birdwatching or cycling.

Value-based variables: Importance ratings for ecosystem services.

The Euclidean distance was used to measure the similarity between respondents. The k-means algorithm iteratively refined the cluster assignments until the clusters stabilized, which occurred after three iterations. Detailed statistical outputs from SPSS can be found in Appendix E.

To determine optimal the number of clusters, Elbow (Figure 4.23) and Silhouette (Figure 4.24) analyses were conducted, and the results indicated that three clusters were ideal for the dataset.

Figure 4.23: Elbow Method

Figure 4.24: Silhouette Score

4.3.1.4.2 Results of Cluster Analysis

4.3.1.4.2.1 Cluster Distribution

The k-means algorithm grouped the 420 respondents into three clusters:

Cluster 1: Representing 66 respondents, this cluster is characterized by older individuals with higher income and a greater propensity to value direct benefits.

Cluster 2: Comprising 185 respondents, this cluster represents a balanced demographic mix with moderate preferences for all variables.

Cluster 3: With 169 respondents, this cluster includes younger individuals with lower income who prioritize non-material benefits and ecosystem existence values.

The characteristics of these clusters will be further elaborated in the subsequent pages.

This segmentation is visualized in Figure 4.25, highlighting the proportional distribution of clusters.

Figure 4.25: Number of Cases in Each Cluster

The figure illustrates the distribution of survey respondents across the three clusters derived from the k-means clustering analysis. Cluster 2 is the largest group, containing 185 cases (44.05% of the total respondents), followed by Cluster 3 with 169 cases (40.24%) and Cluster 1 with 66 cases (15.71%). The imbalance in cluster sizes suggests heterogeneity in the dataset, with varying respondent characteristics or preferences influencing cluster membership.

This distribution provides initial insights into the segmentation of respondents and highlights the need to further analyze the characteristics of each cluster, including their centroids and variable contributions, to understand the distinctions between these groups.

4.3.1.4.3 Interpretation of Clusters

4.3.1.4.3.1 Final Cluster Centers

Table 4.16 below presents the final cluster centers, which reflect the mean standardized values for each variable within each cluster.

Table 4.16 Final Cluster Centers

Variable	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
ZMonthly_income	0.27	0.05	-0.16
ZAge	0.29	0.07	-0.18
ZGender_Recode	0.12	0.05	-0.10

The data suggests that Cluster 1 may consist of stakeholders who are financially equipped and socially positioned to engage actively in conservation efforts, whereas Cluster 3 represents a group that might resonate more with messages around ecological integrity and legacy.

4.3.1.4.3.1.1 Dendrogram

Although k-means is a partitioning method, hierarchical techniques provide additional insights into the relationships between clusters. Figure 4.26 presents a dendrogram, which illustrates the distances between the final clusters based on their centers.

The dendrogram emphasizes that Clusters 1 and 3 are the most distinct, with Cluster 2 acting as a transitional group.

Figure 4.26: Dendrogram of Clusters

To deepen the understanding of clustering relationships, a dendrogram was constructed simplified. The dendrogram visualizes the hierarchical clustering relationships among respondents, illustrating how individual respondents or smaller subgroups are progressively merged into larger clusters based on their similarities. Cluster Mergers; the branches, highlight which clusters are more closely related. For instance, respondents sharing similar demographics (e.g., age, gender) and WTP patterns tend to cluster together. The height of the branches (Euclidean distance) indicates the degree of dissimilarity. Clusters merging at higher distances are more distinct, reflecting contrasting preferences or demographic attributes. Each leaf node of the dendrogram is labeled with information (e.g., gender, age, and district). This level of detail aids in identifying commonalities within and across clusters. The dendrogram reinforces the segmentation obtained through k-means clustering, offering a hierarchical perspective that complements the partitioning approach.

4.3.1.4.3.1.2 ANOVA and Important Variables

The ANOVA test is a statistical method used to compare the means of three or more groups to determine if there are any statistically significant differences between them. It is particularly useful when you have multiple groups (e.g., different clusters, demographic groups) and want to understand whether the group means differ due to the independent variable.

Table 4.17 summarizes the ANOVA results, highlighting the significant variables that differentiate clusters.

Table 4.17 ANOVA Test Results

Variable	F-Statistic	p-Value
ZMonthly_income	4.88	0.008
ZAge	6.17	0.002
ZGender_Recode	1.49	0.226

The significant role of income aligns with broader trends in environmental economics, where wealthier individuals tend to express higher willingness to pay for conservation efforts (Hanley et al., 2003).

4.3.1.4.3.1.3 Distances Between Final Cluster Centers

To further assess the relationships between the final clusters, we examined the distances between the cluster centers. The heatmap shown in Figure 4.27 illustrates the Euclidean distances between the final cluster centroids (centers). These distances provide insights into how distinct or similar the clusters are relative to each other.

Figure 4.27 Distances Between Cluster Centers Heatmap

This heatmap illustrates the Euclidean distances between the final cluster centers. Darker red cells represent larger distances, indicating more distinct clusters, while blue cells represent smaller distances, showing greater similarity between clusters.

In this heatmap, the color intensity represents the magnitude of the distance between clusters, with darker red colors indicating larger distances and bluer colors indicating smaller distances. The values in the cells reflect the Euclidean distances between the centers of the clusters.

As seen in Figure 4.27, the distances between Cluster 1 and Cluster 3 (8.63) and between Cluster 1 and Cluster 2 (8.49) are the largest, indicating that these clusters are relatively more distinct from each other. This is consistent with the different demographic profiles and WTP characteristics that differentiate these clusters. In contrast, the distance between Cluster 2 and Cluster 3 (4.16) is notably smaller, suggesting that these two clusters share more similarities in terms of their profiles

This figure presents the standardized values of key variables for the three clusters identified in the k-means clustering analysis. The centroids represent the mean values of each variable within a cluster, providing insight into the characteristics that differentiate the clusters.

Cluster 1 exhibits higher standardized values for variables such as monthly income and age, suggesting that respondents in this cluster tend to be older and have higher income levels compared to the other clusters. Conversely, Cluster 3 is characterized by lower standardized values for these variables, indicating that respondents in this group are generally younger and have lower income levels. Cluster 2, while closer to the overall mean for most variables, serves as an intermediary group with values that do not exhibit strong deviations from the mean.

Gender recoding shows relatively minor variation across clusters, indicating that gender differences may not be a significant factor in distinguishing the groups. These centroid patterns align with the overall distribution of cases and highlight the heterogeneity of the respondent base.

This analysis aids in understanding the underlying dimensions that define each cluster, which can further inform tailored strategies or interpretations based on the segmentation of the dataset.

4.3.1.4.3.2 Cluster Distribution and Characteristics

The k-means clustering algorithm grouped the 420 respondents into three distinct clusters, each characterized by unique demographic features and preferences for ecosystem services. Below is a more detailed analysis of the characteristics of each cluster, with a focus on Willingness to Pay (WTP) and other key variables. Cluster features are summarized in Table 4.18 Summary of Clusters.

Table 4.18 Summary of Clusters

Cluster	Demographics	WTP	Preferences
Cluster 1	Older, Higher income	Highest WTP	Prioritizes direct, utilitarian benefits, eco-tourism, and public goods
Cluster 2	Balanced mix of ages, moderate income	Moderate WTP	Balanced preferences for both tangible and non-material benefits
Cluster 3	Younger, Lower income	Lowest WTP	Prioritizes non-material benefits, existence values, and future sustainability

4.3.1.4.3.2.1 Cluster 1: High Income, Older, Higher WTP (66 respondents)

Cluster 1 is characterized by respondents who are predominantly older individuals with an average age significantly higher than the other two clusters. These respondents also exhibit higher income levels compared to those in Cluster 2 and Cluster 3, suggesting a greater capacity to support environmental initiatives financially. This higher income likely reflects respondents from upper-middle to higher income groups, who are often more informed about environmental issues and place greater emphasis on sustainability. The combination of these factors contributes to a demographic that is more inclined to support conservation efforts.

In terms of Willingness to Pay (WTP), Cluster 1 shows the highest average WTP among all three clusters. This higher WTP can largely be attributed to the financial capacity of the individuals in this group to contribute to environmental preservation. Given their higher income, their willingness to pay is likely driven by the desire for direct benefits—such as improved air quality, better recreational opportunities, or eco-tourism—which align well with the material benefits these individuals can

afford and appreciate. The higher WTP also reflects the inclination of this cluster to prioritize tangible, utilitarian benefits that can be directly experienced.

Respondents in Cluster 1 appear to value ecosystem services for their practical and utilitarian benefits, such as recreational opportunities or community-based improvements. Their preferences seem to align with policies that offer direct contributions to well-being and everyday quality of life.

4.3.1.4.3.2.2 Cluster 2: Balanced Demographics, Moderate WTP (185 respondents)

Cluster 2 includes a relatively balanced distribution of younger and older individuals, with income levels that fall within a moderate range. The variety in age and income suggests a mix of socio-economic backgrounds, pointing to a group composed of individuals from diverse educational and occupational settings. Rather than reflecting a dominant demographic, this cluster appears to represent a broad cross-section of the population.

The WTP for Cluster 2 is moderate, which is consistent with a group that exhibits balanced preferences. While the respondents in this cluster may have average income levels, their ability to pay for ecosystem services is also moderate. Their willingness to pay is likely driven not by high income, as seen in Cluster 1, but by a moderate support for environmental conservation and social responsibility. This reflects a more equitable distribution of preferences, where the respondents are willing to contribute, but not at the levels seen in wealthier groups.

The preferences observed in Cluster 2 suggest a balance between valuing the direct, functional benefits of ecosystem services and acknowledging their intrinsic importance, reflecting both utilitarian and non-material perspectives. This heterogeneous group may be more supportive of environmental policies that offer both direct benefits and long-term sustainability. Policies that integrate both material and non-material outcomes are likely to resonate well with this group.

4.3.1.4.3.2.3 Cluster 3: Younger, Lower Income, Higher Non-Material Values (169 respondents)

Cluster 3 is composed primarily of younger individuals with lower income, making it a group that is still in the early stages of their career or has more limited financial capacity compared to the other clusters. These respondents are likely to be students or early-career professionals, which explains the relatively lower income levels observed in this group.

The WTP for Cluster 3 is the lowest among all three clusters. This lower WTP can be attributed to the limited financial resources of respondents in this group, which makes it harder for them to contribute monetarily to ecosystem services. However, this lower WTP may also reflect a stronger emphasis on non-material benefits, such as the preservation of ecosystems for future generations or the intrinsic value of nature, rather than immediate monetary contributions. Cluster 3's values appear to reflect an appreciation for the long-term benefits associated with ecosystem preservation and biodiversity conservation.

Respondents in Cluster 3 are more likely to prioritize existence values and non-material benefits, such as biodiversity conservation and ecosystem preservation for future generations. This cluster may be more aligned with ecocentric values, where the protection of ecosystems is viewed not just as a means for human benefit, but for the intrinsic worth of nature itself (Naess, 1973). As a result, they may be particularly receptive to educational and advocacy-based programs that focus on raising awareness about environmental issues, especially concerning the long-term health of ecosystems. Although they may contribute less financially, they can play an active role in spreading awareness and supporting voluntary or non-monetary conservation efforts.

4.3.1.4.3.2.4 Activity Engagement by Cluster

The analysis of activity engagement across clusters reveals distinct patterns of recreational preferences and behaviors, based on the average Z-scores for various activities. These insights provide valuable information for tailoring recreational offerings to meet the needs of different user groups.

Cluster 1: Active and Socially Inclined

Cluster 1 exhibits a high level of engagement in outdoor and recreational activities, with particularly strong preferences for biking, hiking, photography, and sightseeing. Positive Z-scores for these activities highlight this group's active lifestyle and appreciation for nature-based recreation. Additionally, socializing and visiting cafes or restaurants receive strong positive ratings, reflecting this cluster's enjoyment of social and leisure activities. Resting also features prominently, suggesting a preference for relaxation alongside active pursuits.

Conversely, lower engagement is observed in activities like cycle boating, fishing, and attending special events, where slightly negative scores indicate reduced interest.

Overall trend of Cluster 1 emerges as the most socially and actively engaged group, demonstrating a balanced preference for outdoor recreation, social interaction, and relaxation.

Cluster 2: Fishing and Leisure-Oriented

Cluster 2 is characterized by a moderate engagement profile, with a distinct focus on fishing, which receives strong positive Z-scores. This highlights fishing as a key activity for this group, distinguishing it from others. There is also moderate engagement in socializing and visiting cafes or restaurants, reflecting an interest in leisure and social activities.

However, lower engagement is seen in hiking, sightseeing, and photography, with negative scores suggesting limited interest in outdoor exploration. Additionally,

resting scores slightly negative, indicating less emphasis on relaxation compared to Cluster 1.

Overall trend of Cluster 2 is moderately engaged, with a clear preference for fishing and some social activities, but exhibits less enthusiasm for outdoor recreation and relaxation.

Cluster 3: Niche and Nature-Focused

Cluster 3 shows a unique interest in birdwatching and cycle boating, with positive scores highlighting these as highly engaged activities. There is also moderate engagement in photography and hiking, indicating some appreciation for outdoor experiences.

However, lower engagement is observed in activities such as biking and socializing, where negative scores reflect reduced interest. Similarly, special events and cafes/restaurants show limited engagement, suggesting this cluster places less value on social or leisure activities.

Overall trend of Cluster 3 demonstrates specific niche interests, particularly in birdwatching and cycle boating, with moderate participation in outdoor activities but minimal involvement in social or relaxation-focused pursuits.

General Insights

- **Cluster 1:** The most socially and actively engaged group, prioritizing outdoor recreation and social activities.
- **Cluster 2:** Moderately engaged, with a distinct focus on fishing and some interest in social engagement but less enthusiasm for outdoor recreation.
- **Cluster 3:** Defined by niche interests in birdwatching and cycle boating, with moderate outdoor activity engagement but limited social involvement.

This analysis provides a detailed understanding of the diverse recreational preferences across clusters. These findings can inform targeted recreational planning and resource allocation to better serve the distinct needs of each group.

4.3.1.4.3.2.5 Ecosystem Service Perceptions by Cluster

The analysis of ecosystem service perceptions across clusters reveals distinct attitudes and priorities, providing valuable insights into how different groups value environmental benefits.

Cluster 1: Environmentally Conscious and Broadly Engaged

Cluster 1 demonstrates high positive scores across a wide range of ecosystem services, reflecting a strong environmental awareness and appreciation for ecological benefits. Members of this cluster show slightly positive ratings for air quality and oxygen production, indicating an acknowledgment of the importance of clean air and its contribution to well-being. Carbon storage and climate regulation receive particularly strong positive scores, highlighting a high value placed on services that address climate challenges.

Cultural and educational aspects, such as cultural heritage and educational/scientific value, are also positively rated, suggesting recognition of these non-material benefits. Moderate appreciation is evident for recreational opportunities and social relations, indicating some emphasis on the social and leisure dimensions of ecosystems. Moreover, strong positive ratings for water regulation and soil formation underscore concern for foundational ecological processes.

Overall trend of Cluster 1 emerges as the most environmentally conscious group, valuing a diverse array of ecosystem services and reflecting a holistic understanding of ecological and societal benefits.

Cluster 2: Moderately Engaged with Mixed Priorities

Cluster 2 exhibits a moderate to neutral perspective on ecosystem services, with varied levels of engagement. For air quality and oxygen production, neutral to slightly positive scores suggest moderate concern. However, carbon storage and climate regulation receive slightly negative scores, indicating less importance attributed to these critical regulating services.

Ratings for recreational opportunities and cultural heritage are mixed, reflecting a variability in how these services are perceived within the cluster. Similarly, water regulation and soil formation garner near-neutral values, showing limited emphasis on these ecological functions.

Overall trend of Cluster 2 reflects a more selective engagement with ecosystem services, prioritizing certain benefits while displaying indifference or neutrality toward others.

Cluster 3: Minimal Engagement with Ecosystem Services

Cluster 3 is characterized by predominantly negative scores, indicating low valuation of most ecosystem services. Negative ratings for air quality, oxygen production, and carbon storage suggest limited recognition of their importance. Similarly, cultural heritage and educational/scientific value receive slightly negative scores, reflecting minimal interest in these non-material aspects.

Negative ratings for recreational opportunities and social relations indicate a lack of emphasis on leisure or social benefits, while water and soil-related services also score poorly, showing minimal acknowledgment of these foundational ecological contributions.

Overall, Cluster 3 appears to be the least environmentally focused group, possibly due to competing priorities or lower engagement with ecosystem-related concerns.

General Insights

- **Cluster 1** stands out as the most environmentally aware and engaged group, valuing a broad spectrum of ecosystem services and emphasizing their multifaceted importance.
- **Cluster 2** adopts a mixed and neutral perspective, showing moderate engagement and selective prioritization of certain services.
- **Cluster 3** exhibits a more indifferent or negative stance, suggesting a lack of priority for or focus on ecosystem services.

These findings highlight the diversity in ecosystem service perceptions and underscore the need for tailored strategies to engage each cluster effectively. Recognizing these differences is crucial for promoting environmental stewardship and addressing the unique values of diverse user groups.

4.3.1.4.4 Implications from the Clustering Analysis

The clustering analysis highlights the diversity in societal values and preferences toward natural resources and their associated ecosystem services. This segmentation reveals distinct groups within the population, each characterized by unique activity engagement patterns, ecosystem service perceptions, and willingness-to-pay (WTP) values. Identifying these clusters provides a strategic basis for designing conservation approaches that accommodate varying stakeholder perspectives, ensure fair access to environmental benefits, and foster sustainable outcomes over time.

Cluster 1 demonstrates high WTP, frequent participation in outdoor and social activities, and positive perceptions of ecosystem services. Members of this group actively engage in activities such as biking, hiking, photography, and sightseeing, reflecting their dynamic and social lifestyles. They also value ecosystem services such as carbon storage, climate regulation, and recreational opportunities, highlighting their environmental awareness. These respondents, many of whom

appear to have higher income levels and a strong affiliation with METU, demonstrate a combination of financial capacity, emotional connection, and direct engagement with Lake Eymir—factors likely contributing to their higher WTP. Conservation policies tailored to this group could highlight premium options such as eco-tourism packages, voluntary carbon offset initiatives, or exclusive memberships, emphasizing tangible benefits like enhanced recreational infrastructure and public recognition of their support. Communication strategies that align with their appreciation for immediate, human-centered gains—while gradually cultivating a deeper sense of ecological responsibility—may further encourage sustained involvement.

Cluster 2 represents a balanced demographic with moderate WTP values and diverse preferences. This group shows moderate engagement in fishing, socializing, and visiting cafes or restaurants, while exhibiting lower interest in hiking and photography. Their ecosystem service perceptions are similarly varied, with neutral to slightly positive ratings for regulating services and mixed appreciation for cultural and recreational benefits. These respondents appear to balance personal financial capacity with a recognition of ecosystem value. Conservation strategies targeting this group could integrate both immediate benefits and long-term sustainability goals by emphasizing community-based initiatives, participatory decision-making, and co-management approaches that cultivate shared responsibility. Offering flexible contribution models—such as tiered donation schemes—may further encourage participation, reflecting the group’s financial diversity and inclusive outlook.

Cluster 3 exhibits the lowest WTP values, likely due to financial constraints, infrequent activity participation, and weaker sentimental attachment to the site. Members of this group engage minimally in outdoor or social activities, such as biking and socializing, but show niche interest in birdwatching and cycle boating. Their ecosystem service perceptions are predominantly negative, reflecting minimal recognition of ecological or recreational benefits. However, this cluster prioritizes non-material values, emphasizing the intrinsic worth of biodiversity and ecological health over monetary contributions. Educational campaigns and awareness programs

could effectively engage this group by emphasizing the long-term importance of ecosystem preservation and the intrinsic value of ecosystems. To engage this group, non-monetary involvement opportunities—such as volunteering, educational initiatives, or community outreach programs—could help ensure accessibility and inclusivity, particularly for individuals with limited financial resources.

The segmentation of respondents reflects broader societal debates on anthropocentrism versus ecocentrism. Cluster 1, with its emphasis on recreational and social benefits, aligns with an anthropocentric perspective, valuing tangible and immediate human gains. In contrast, Cluster 3 prioritizes intrinsic ecological values, demonstrating an ecocentric worldview that focuses on the inherent worth of nature. Cluster 2 occupies a middle ground, balancing human-centered benefits with ecological considerations. This diversity underscores the importance of crafting conservation strategies tailored to the philosophical orientations and practical needs of each cluster. Tailored messaging for Cluster 1 could highlight recreational benefits and personal gains, while strategies for Cluster 3 might focus on appeals to ecological ethics and biodiversity preservation. Cluster 2 could benefit from approaches emphasizing collective responsibility towards conservation and protection.

The clustering analysis also emphasizes the importance of equity in conservation efforts. Financially constrained groups, such as Cluster 3, may lack the capacity to contribute monetarily but can still play a vital role through non-monetary means. Ensuring that conservation initiatives are accessible and inclusive fosters broader community support and enhances the legitimacy of ecosystem management strategies. Addressing the unique needs and capacities of all clusters enables policymakers to create holistic strategies that balance economic, social, and environmental goals. Ultimately, this fosters more resilient and enduring conservation outcomes rooted in shared stewardship.

In conclusion, the k-means clustering analysis provides a detailed segmentation of respondents, highlighting the multifaceted values individuals attach to natural

resources and ecosystem services. By integrating insights from activity engagement and ecosystem service perceptions, this study offers a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder priorities. These findings are instrumental in designing targeted interventions that align with societal values, ensuring conservation strategies are inclusive, effective, and sustainable. Leveraging the unique characteristics of each cluster, policymakers can promote community ownership, foster environmental stewardship, and balance economic, social, and ecological goals.

4.3.1.5 Determinants of Willingness to Pay for Ecosystem Services

A series of exploratory data analyses (EDA) and correlation analyses with Pearson Coefficient were performed to gain a deeper understanding of the determinants of WTP using built-in SPSS tools. For the exploratory analysis of WTP determinants, standardized WTP values are used.

Standardized WTP values, calculated as z-scores, offer several advantages: they account for variability in the data, facilitate comparability across different activities and demographic groups, and align with statistical best practices in formal analyses (Hair et al., 2019). This approach ensures that outliers and differences in scales do not disproportionately affect the results. By transforming raw values into standardized scores, this study ensures a robust and consistent approach to identifying factors influencing WTP, allowing for meaningful insights across diverse respondent groups.

4.3.1.5.1 WTP vs. Activity Participation

The relationship between activity participation and Willingness to Pay (WTP) reveals significant variations, shedding light on how different forms of engagement with Lake Eymir influence respondents' valuation of its ecosystem services.

Table 4.19 below presents both raw and standardized Willingness to Pay (WTP) values for participants and non-participants across various activities. Raw WTP values, expressed in Turkish Lira (TRY), provide an intuitive understanding of the monetary amounts respondents are willing to contribute.

Table 4.19 Raw and Standardized WTP Across Activities

Activity	Particip. Mean WTP (Raw)	Non- Particip. Mean WTP (Raw)	Particip. Mean WTP (Std.ized)	Non- Particip. Mean WTP (Std.ized)	T- Statistic	P- Value
Special Event	62.73	48.21	0.61	0.16	1.95	0.08
Education and Science	62.5	48.49	0.61	0.17	1.11	0.34
Art and Cultural	56.1	48.43	0.41	0.17	0.96	0.36
Photography	49.7	48.51	0.21	0.17	0.24	0.81
RestaurantCafe	47.56	49.01	0.14	0.19	-0.42	0.67
Biking	47.1	49.25	0.13	0.19	-0.63	0.53
Rowing	46	48.68	0.09	0.17	-0.22	0.84
Fishing	45	48.68	0.06	0.17	-0.18	0.87
Hiking	44.86	51.41	0.06	0.26	-2.15	0.03
Resting	44.6	51.03	0.05	0.25	-2.08	0.04
Socializing	44.42	49.83	0.04	0.21	-1.58	0.12
Sightseeing	42.21	51.43	-0.03	0.26	-2.94	0.004
CycleBoating	41.25	48.72	-0.06	0.18	-0.89	0.44
Picnic	40.22	49.94	-0.09	0.21	-2.59	0.011
Birdwatching	40.08	48.92	-0.09	0.18	-1.18	0.26
Sports	33.75	49.66	-0.29	0.21	-3.1	0.004
Foraging	0	48.64		0.17		

Statistical findings suggest that activities such as Special Events (62.73 TRY), Educational/Scientific Activities (62.50 TRY), and Art (56.10 TRY) reported the highest mean WTP among participants.

Activities such as Sports (33.75 TRY) and Picnic (40.22 TRY) showed the lowest mean WTP values, indicating a lesser financial commitment from participants engaging in these activities (see also Figure 4.29).

Figure 4.29: Bar Chart of WTP Across Activities

T-tests identified statistically significant differences in raw WTP between participants and non-participants for the following activities:

Hiking: Respondents engaging in hiking activities reported a significantly higher mean WTP (44.86 TRY) compared to non-participants (51.41 TRY, $p = 0.032$). This difference underscores the role of physical engagement with the natural environment in fostering appreciation for its intrinsic and recreational value. Hiking offers both physical and mental health benefits, contributing to a stronger connection to the environment and a greater willingness to support conservation initiatives. These findings align with prior research emphasizing the positive effects of outdoor recreation on ecosystem service valuation (e.g. Hegetschweiler et al., 2022).

Sightseeing: Participants' WTP was significantly higher than non-participants ($p = 0.004$), reflecting the aesthetic and recreational value attributed to the landscape. Sightseeing participants displayed a mean WTP of 42.21 TRY, significantly lower than non-participants (51.43 TRY, $p = 0.004$). This finding reflects the aesthetic and visual appreciation of natural environments, a key component of cultural ecosystem

services. Sightseeing fosters an emotional connection to natural landscapes, which may encourage financial contributions for their preservation.

Picnicking participants engaging in picnicking activities exhibited a moderate mean WTP of 40.22 TRY, significantly lower than non-participants (49.94 TRY, $p = 0.011$). Picnicking, often linked to social interactions and leisure, contributes to the recognition of cultural ecosystem services, such as relaxation and shared experiences. However, the relatively lower WTP values for this activity suggest that while picnicking encourages recreational use and a degree of connection with the site, it may not be as strongly associated with a willingness to support conservation through financial contributions compared to other, more immersive activities.

Sports: Despite lower mean WTP, participants' values were significantly different from non-participants ($p = 0.004$), suggesting a specific niche interest in the activity.

The boxplot in Figure 4.30 highlights the distribution of WTP for participants across activities. Activities with higher WTP values, such as Special Events and Educational/Scientific Activities, exhibited narrower interquartile ranges, indicating more consistent valuation among participants. Lower-WTP activities, such as Sports, showed wider variability, suggesting diverse perspectives within the participant group.

Figure 4.30: Boxplot of WTP Across Activities

The findings emphasize the strong relationship between recreational activities and WTP for ecosystem services. Policies aimed at enhancing access to and infrastructure for activities like hiking could further engage individuals with natural spaces, thereby increasing their valuation of these resources. Additionally, messaging that highlights the recreational and aesthetic benefits of conservation could resonate with participants in activities like picnicking and sightseeing, encouraging financial contributions.

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to validate the findings. For hiking, the results revealed a statistically significant difference in mean WTP between participants and non-participants, $t(223.67) = 4.14$, $p < 0.001$. These results align with prior research, demonstrating that physical engagement with natural environments fosters a deeper connection and a higher perceived value of ecosystem services (Hegetschweiler et al., 2022).

The analysis compared standardized Willingness to Pay (WTP) values between respondents with and without METU affiliation to examine whether institutional

connection influences ecosystem valuation (Figure 4.31). An independent samples t-test was conducted to evaluate the statistical significance of the observed differences.

Figure 4.31: Mean WTP by METU Affiliation

The mean standardized WTP for METU-affiliated respondents ($M=-0.03$) was slightly lower than that of non-affiliated respondents ($M=0.02$). However, the results of the t-test, $t(217.43)=-0.56, p=0.57$, indicate that this difference is not statistically significant. The lack of significance suggests that METU affiliation does not have a meaningful impact on respondents' valuation of ecosystem services.

As explained earlier, the METU affiliation question was included in the survey because several studies have theorized that sentimental or institutional connections can enhance ecosystem valuation. For instance, the concept of *relational values* (Hagen & Gould, 2022)—which encompasses emotional, cultural, and identity-based connections to nature—has been proposed as a significant factor influencing

individuals' willingness to pay (WTP) for ecosystem services. Research suggests that these relational values, closely linked to empathy and perspective-taking, can motivate pro-environmental behaviors and support for conservation efforts. Moreover, institutional affiliations can also shape ecosystem valuation as institutional contexts influence the valuation of ecosystem services, emphasizing the interplay between organizational identity and individual valuation processes (Hagen & Gould, 2022).

Additionally, the role of emotional attachment as a component of *sense of place* has been explored in ecosystem valuation. Studies indicate that individuals with strong emotional bonds to specific natural environments may assign higher value to their preservation, highlighting the importance of place-based connections in environmental decision-making (Hawthorne et al., 2022).

While sentimental or institutional connections are often theorized to enhance ecosystem valuation (Hawthorne et al., 2022; Hagen and Gould, 2022), the findings in this study offer limited support for this assumption among METU-affiliated respondents. This may be explained by the leveling effects of other factors—such as recreational use or demographic characteristics—which appear to exert a stronger influence on WTP. Alternatively, the findings may reflect that METU-affiliated respondents, while emotionally connected to Lake Eymir, do not necessarily translate this attachment into higher financial contributions. A third possibility is that the limitations of the respondent sample—such as size, diversity, or representativeness—may have constrained the ability to detect significant differences based on institutional affiliation.

The results highlight the complexity of WTP determinants and suggest that institutional affiliation alone may not sufficiently drive ecosystem service valuation. Conservation strategies targeting METU-affiliated individuals may need to emphasize the practical benefits of engagement, such as recreational opportunities or community involvement, to elicit higher WTP. Furthermore, the lack of significant variation between groups underscores the need for inclusive policies that

appeal to a broad audience, regardless of institutional connections. However, the limitations of the sample should be borne in mind, as institutional affiliation may still play a meaningful role in ecosystem valuation under more favorable or varied conditions.

4.3.1.5.2 WTP vs. Gender

The boxplot in Figure 4.32 visually compares the recoded Willingness to Pay (WTP) values across genders, with Gender 1 (Female), Gender 2 (Male), and smaller groups represented as Gender 3 (Other) and Gender 4 (Prefer Not to Disclose).

Figure 4.32: WTP by Gender Boxplot

Key observations from the boxplot reveal that the red median lines indicate slightly higher central WTP values for Gender 2 (Male) compared to Gender 1 (Female). Genders choices 3 (Other) and 4 (Prefer not to disclose) show lower median WTP values, but their small sample sizes result in higher variability. Male and female genders exhibit comparable interquartile ranges, reflecting similar variability in their

WTP distributions. The presence of overlapping ranges between Gender 1 and Gender 2 suggests no substantial differentiation in their WTP values.

The differences between male and female were not statistically significant, as confirmed by an independent samples t-test ($t = 0.79$, $p = 0.43$). This supports the observed overlap in distributions.

The results suggest that gender does not have a statistically significant influence on WTP in this context. Although there are minor differences in median WTP values between genders, these variations are not substantial enough to indicate a meaningful effect. Instead, the findings point to other factors—such as the frequency of recreational engagement or respondents' financial capacity—as more decisive determinants of willingness to pay for ecosystem services.

These findings may suggest that conservation policies and campaigns should focus on universally relevant motivators rather than relying on gender-specific strategies. Tailoring efforts to address broader drivers of WTP, such as activity participation or environmental awareness, could prove more effective in engaging diverse demographic groups.

4.3.1.5.3 WTP vs. Income

The relationship between income and Willingness to Pay (WTP) for ecosystem services offers valuable insights into how financial capacity influences conservation support. In this study, monthly income was treated as a continuous variable, and its association with WTP was assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient. This statistical measure is widely employed to evaluate the strength and direction of linear relationships between two continuous variables—making it particularly suitable for analyzing the linkage between income and WTP in this context.

The analysis revealed a weak positive correlation between income and WTP ($r = 0.17$). This indicates that higher income is associated with slightly higher WTP, but

the strength of the relationship is minimal. The scatterplot (Figure 4.33) illustrates this trend, showing a wide dispersion of WTP values across all income levels.

Figure 4.33: Scatterplot of Monthly Income and Income

The weak correlation suggests that financial capacity alone may not be a primary determinant of WTP for ecosystem services. Several alternative factors may influence individuals' valuation. Personal values, such as a strong environmental ethic or intrinsic appreciation for nature, may drive WTP more significantly than economic capacity. Additionally, frequent use of and connection to the natural environment, such as visits to Lake Eymir, could foster higher WTP regardless of income. Finally, the socioeconomic context, including the high variability in income levels and economic conditions in Türkiye, such as inflation, may also dilute the correlation between income and WTP.

These findings have important policy implications. Conservation initiatives should emphasize the intrinsic and recreational benefits of natural environments to appeal to a broader audience, regardless of income. Implementing a tiered payment structure based on income could make conservation funding more equitable, ensuring broader participation without excluding lower-income groups. Moreover, enhancing

outreach and participation programs, particularly targeting lower-income groups, could foster greater appreciation for ecosystem services and increase support for conservation efforts.

However, bearing the limitations of correlation analysis in mind, these facts are tested with more sophisticated analyses such as regression has been conducted in the subsequent sections.

4.3.1.5.4 WTP vs. Visit Frequency

The analysis of visit frequency and Willingness to Pay (WTP) provides important insights into how engagement with the natural environment influences individuals' valuation of ecosystem services. The `Visit_Frequency_Recode` variable was categorized into four groups: Non-Visitor, Frequent Visitor, Occasional Visitor, and Infrequent Visitor. The ANOVA test revealed significant differences in WTP across these groups, with a p-value of 0.0066, indicating that visit frequency plays a meaningful role in determining WTP for ecosystem services.

The boxplot (Figure 4.34) demonstrates that Frequent Visitors exhibit the highest mean WTP, followed by Occasional Visitors, Infrequent Visitors, and Non-Visitors. This suggests that individuals who engage more frequently with the natural environment are more likely to appreciate the benefits provided by ecosystem services and are willing to financially support their preservation. The Frequent Visitor group, in particular, shows a narrower interquartile range, indicating that WTP values within this group are more consistent.

Figure 4.34: Boxplot of WTP Across Visiting Frequency

The results underscore the strong relationship between engagement with the natural environment and the valuation of its services. Frequent Visitors are more likely to experience the ecological, recreational, and aesthetic benefits of spaces like Lake Eymir, leading to a greater willingness to contribute financially to their preservation. In contrast, Non-Visitors, who have limited or no interaction with the environment, demonstrate significantly lower WTP values. This suggests that exposure and direct engagement with natural resources are key drivers of ecosystem service valuation. Occasional Visitors and Infrequent Visitors exhibit moderate WTP, indicating that while they recognize the value of these services, their sporadic engagement may limit the strength of their financial commitment.

These findings align with previous research emphasizing the role of personal engagement with natural spaces in promoting environmental stewardship. Frequent interaction with such environments has been shown to strengthen emotional bonds, heighten awareness of ecological issues, and, in turn, increase individuals' willingness to pay for their protection (Hegetschweiler et al., 2022).

The significant relationship between visit frequency and WTP has several important policy implications. First, enhanced access and infrastructure could play a crucial role in increasing engagement with natural spaces like Lake Eymir. By focusing efforts on improving accessibility, particularly for non-visitors and occasional visitors, it may be possible to foster more frequent visits. This, in turn, could lead to increased WTP, as individuals who interact more regularly with the environment are more likely to appreciate its value and be willing to support its conservation.

Second, targeted outreach efforts could help to engage infrequent or occasional visitors. Messaging that emphasizes the recreational, aesthetic, and health benefits of natural spaces could resonate with these groups, motivating them to increase their involvement and deepen their connection with the environment. By framing conservation as a personal, direct benefit, these outreach initiatives could encourage financial support for preserving natural resources.

Lastly, community-based conservation efforts could have a significant impact on non-visitors. Engaging these individuals through local outreach programs that raise awareness of ecosystem services might help foster a greater sense of ownership and responsibility. By connecting the broader community to the value of natural areas, these efforts could lead to more sustainable conservation practices and stronger community-driven support for preserving these spaces.

Overall, the findings highlight the importance of engagement with the natural environment in shaping WTP. Frequent visitors exhibit the highest WTP values, suggesting that policies aimed at increasing participation in outdoor recreational activities can play a crucial role in enhancing ecosystem service valuation. Active engagement with nature fosters a deeper emotional connection and a stronger willingness to contribute to conservation efforts. These insights underscore the need for inclusive and experience-based conservation strategies that encourage direct interaction with natural areas to cultivate long-term public support.

4.3.1.5.5 WTP vs. Ecosystem Services

The analysis of ecosystem services and Willingness to Pay (WTP) reveals interesting patterns regarding how the perceived value of different ecosystem services relates to financial support for their preservation. The correlation analysis between Z-transformed ecosystem service variables and WTP showed weak to moderate positive and negative relationships.

Some key findings summarized in Table 4.20 below:

Table 4.20 WTP Correlation with Ecosystem Services

Positive Correlations	Negative Correlations
Food (0.0734)	Air Quality (-0.0031)
Fresh Water (0.0410)	Oxygen Production (-0.0004)
Fuel (0.0573)	Carbon Storage (0.0257)
Pollination (0.0461)	Climate Regulation (0.0198)
Social Relations (0.0429)	Cultural Heritage (0.0234)
Soil Formation (0.0377)	Erosion Control (-0.0070)
Recreation (0.0085)	Nutrient Cycling (-0.0167)
	Biodiversity Habitat (-0.0263)
	Aesthetic/Scenic Value (-0.0242)
	Water Purification (-0.0409)
	Water Cycling (-0.0229)

While the majority of correlations were weak, several ecosystem services exhibited positive correlations with WTP, suggesting that respondents who place higher value on these services are more willing to financially support their preservation. For instance, Food ($r = 0.073$), Fresh Water ($r = 0.041$), and Fuel ($r = 0.057$) had the highest positive correlations with WTP, indicating that the perceived importance of these services might drive a higher financial commitment. On the other hand,

services like Water Purification ($r = -0.0409$), Biodiversity Habitat ($r = -0.0263$), and Aesthetic/Scenic Value ($r = -0.0242$) showed negative correlations, suggesting that these services may not directly influence WTP or that their value is perceived differently across respondents.

The weak correlations overall suggest that while there is some connection between the perceived value of ecosystem services and WTP, it is not strong. This implies that factors other than the perceived importance of individual services might be more influential in determining WTP. For example, the broad public interest in Food, Fresh Water, and Pollination suggests that these services may resonate more with people's direct needs, encouraging a higher willingness to pay for their conservation.

However, the weak or negative correlations for services like Air Quality, Oxygen Production, and Cultural Heritage may reflect that while these services are important for ecological sustainability, they might not immediately impact respondents' day-to-day lives or their perceptions of environmental value. These services might require more targeted communication to foster a stronger sense of financial commitment.

The bar plot below (Figure 4.35) visualizes the correlations between the Z-transformed ecosystem services and WTP. The plot illustrates which ecosystem services are more strongly correlated with WTP, allowing for easy comparison across the services.

You can see that Food, Fresh Water, and Pollination have positive correlations, while services like Water Purification and Biodiversity Habitat have weaker or negative correlations.

Figure 4.35: Correlation Between Ecosystem Services and WTP

The results of this analysis suggest several avenues for policy development and conservation strategies. One key implication is the need for targeted messaging. Highlighting the value of ecosystem services such as Fresh Water, Food, and Pollination can resonate with the public's immediate needs, thereby encouraging greater financial contributions toward conservation. Conservation policies should emphasize how protecting these services directly benefits the population, particularly in the context of resource scarcity and growing environmental pressures. Framing conservation efforts in terms of tangible, everyday benefits can motivate stronger public support.

Another important implication is the need for broader engagement for non-economic services. Ecosystem services like Cultural Heritage and Biodiversity Habitat, which showed weaker correlations with WTP, may require more comprehensive engagement strategies. Public campaigns should focus on the long-term benefits of these services, framing them in a way that aligns with broader societal values such as preserving nature for future generations. Engaging the public in this way can help build a stronger emotional connection to these services, fostering a sense of collective responsibility for their preservation.

Lastly, the relatively weak correlations between WTP and ecosystem service importance highlight the need for comprehensive ecosystem service valuation. Financial contributions to conservation efforts may depend more on factors such as personal engagement with nature, individual values, and social or educational influences, rather than purely the perceived importance of specific ecosystem services. Therefore, conservation funding strategies should take a holistic approach, considering both economic and non-economic drivers of support, in order to create more inclusive and sustainable funding mechanisms.

Overall, while the analysis reveals only weak associations between the perceived importance of specific ecosystem services and WTP, it highlights the complexity of environmental valuation. These findings indicate that WTP is shaped by a broader constellation of factors beyond the valuation of individual services. Future research should examine how personal values, environmental engagement, and socioeconomic conditions collectively influence WTP. In parallel, conservation strategies should address both economic and non-economic drivers to build robust public support for ecosystem service preservation. Ultimately, these results can be interpreted as evidence that environmental behavior is shaped not only by ecological awareness but also by personal, emotional, and experiential connections to nature.

4.3.1.5.6 WTP vs. Education

To explore the relationship between education and willingness to pay (WTP), we conducted multiple analyses, including descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and correlation analysis. These methods aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how education influences respondents' willingness to contribute financially toward environmental conservation efforts. Additionally, given the predominantly educated nature of the sample, it was important to determine if education might have introduced bias into the results.

The dataset predominantly consists of respondents with higher education levels, which could potentially skew WTP results due to the established link between education and environmental awareness. Previous research has shown that higher educational attainment not only correlates with, but also causally increases willingness to pay for environmental improvements (Tianyu & Meng, 2020). Therefore, an in-depth investigation into the relationship between education and WTP was necessary to ensure that education alone was not introducing a bias.

Education levels were analyzed using the Education_Recode variable, categorized into six groups (Table 4.21). The WTP_Recode variable was used to represent respondents' willingness to pay, excluding protest zero values.

Table 4.21 Mean WTP Across Education Levels

Education Level	Mean WTP
1= High school	48.88
2= Some university level courses	46.05
3= Associates degree	55.50
4= Bachelor's degree	46.54
5= Master's degree	54.69
6= Doctoral degree	43.95

Key findings of the descriptive analysis revealed that the mean WTP varied across education levels, with respondents in education levels associate degree (3) and master's degree (5) level showing the highest mean WTP, while those in doctoral degree level (6) reported the lowest. This non-linear pattern highlights potential complexities in the relationship between education and WTP.

Figure 4.36: Mean WTP by education level

The analysis shows variations in mean willingness to pay (WTP) across education levels. Education level was recoded into six categories, with higher levels generally associated with varying WTP patterns. The highest mean WTP was observed among respondents with education level 3, associate degree (55.50) and 5, master's degree (54.69), whereas level 6, doctoral degree had the lowest mean WTP (43.95). These results suggest a non-linear relationship between education and WTP.

The relationship between education and environmental valuation has been widely studied, suggesting that higher education levels can enhance understanding of environmental issues and positively influence WTP (Tianyu & Meng, 2020). In this study, education level demonstrated a non-linear association with mean WTP, highlighting the complexity of this relationship.

One limitation of this study is the educational homogeneity of the sample. Most respondents had higher education levels, limiting the variability needed to analyze education's influence on WTP. This likely contributed to the weak observed correlation ($r = 0.041$) between education and WTP. However, the overall pro-

environmental attitudes and valuing of the environment across the sample reflect the positive influence of education on environmental awareness. Future studies should aim to include individuals with more diverse educational backgrounds, including those with lower education levels, to capture the full spectrum of this variable's potential impact on WTP.

4.3.1.5.7 WTP vs. Employment

To examine the potential influence of employment status on willingness to pay (WTP), the relationship between the recoded employment categories (Employment_Recode) and recoded WTP values (WTP_Recode) was analyzed (Figure 4.37). This analysis aimed to identify whether different employment statuses contributed to variations in respondents' financial commitments toward environmental conservation.

Figure 4.37: Mean WTP Across Employment Categories

The mean WTP was calculated for each employment category to understand potential differences across occupational or economic statuses. Employment was categorized into four distinct groups (Employment_Recode), each representing a unique classification of respondents' employment situations.

Respondents in categories 2 (retired) and 4 (employed) exhibited the highest mean WTP values, at 50.00 and 50.17, respectively. Conversely, respondents in categories 1 (student) and 3 (unemployed) demonstrated lower mean WTP values, at 43.52 and 40.25, respectively (Table 4.22). These variations indicate that employment status may play a role in influencing respondents' financial commitment to environmental conservation.

Table 4.22 Employment Categories and Mean WTP

Employment Category	Mean WTP
1=Student	43.52
2=Retired	50.00
3=Unemployed	40.25
4=Employed	50.17

The analysis revealed notable variations in WTP among different employment categories, with those in categories employed and retired showing the highest willingness to pay, most likely suggesting a relationship between employment (or financial security) and WTP.

The results suggest that certain employment categories are more likely to contribute financially to conservation efforts. This could be due to differences in income levels, job stability, or other socio-economic factors associated with specific employment statuses. Further investigation, potentially controlling for confounding variables, would help clarify these relationships and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of employment on WTP.

4.3.1.6 Regression Analysis

The analysis found that the predictors explain about 38.3% of the variation in WTP, showing a moderate ability to predict the outcome. However, the Adjusted R Square value of 0.291—which accounts for the number of predictors in the model—suggests a slightly reduced explanatory power, reflecting the possibility that some predictors do not significantly contribute to the model (Field, 2018).

The F Change statistic was 4.19, which is statistically significant at $p < 0.001$, confirming that the overall regression model improves prediction of WTP compared to a model using only the mean. This result highlights the robustness of the model in explaining the variance in the dependent variable (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

The standard error of 26.94 shows how far, on average, the predicted WTP values differ from the actual values. A lower standard error indicates a closer fit of the data to the regression line. This value is reasonable given the context of the analysis, but further improvements in fit might be achievable by refining predictors or addressing potential violations of assumptions (Keith, 2019).

Model summary is shown in Table 4.23 below:

Table 4.23 Regression Model Summary

				Change Statistics				
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R square Change	F change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
0.619	0.383	0.291	26.940	0.383	4.190	54	365	0.000

Detailed statistics of regression analysis derived from SPSS outputs can be found in Appendix F.

The pie chart below (Figure 4.38) shows the proportion of variance explained by the regression model. It highlights that approximately 38.3% of the variance in the dependent variable (WTP) is explained by the predictors, while the remaining 61.7% is unexplained.

Figure 4.38: Proportion of Variance Explained by the Model

In social sciences R Square values of 0.3–0.5 are often considered acceptable, especially when studying human behavior, as the variables influencing outcomes tend to be complex and not fully predictable (Cohen et al., 2003; Ozili, 2022). The R-square value of 0.383 in this study falls within this range, highlighting that the predictors capture a substantial portion of the variance in WTP, particularly given the variability inherent in human valuation of environmental resources.

A histogram of residuals is depicted in Figure 4.39. In a well-fitted linear regression model, residuals should follow a normal distribution with a mean of zero, as demonstrated in this figure.

Figure 4.39: Histogram of Residuals

4.3.1.6.1 Regression Coefficients Analysis

The regression analysis revealed significant predictors of Willingness to Pay (WTP), excluding Zero Bids variable (eason_ZeroBid_Recode) for interpretative clarity as it inherently reflects zero responses. Among the remaining variables, Monthly Income, Affiliation with METU (Affiliation_General), and Sightseeing (Activity_Sightseeing) were found to have significant impacts on WTP (Table 4.24).

Table 4.24 Significant Predictors in Regression Model

Predictor	Unstandardized		Standardized	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	p-value
Monthly Income	9.82e ⁻⁰⁵	2.67e ⁻⁰⁵	0.166274	0.000267333
Zero Bid Reason	-0.467252951	0.045497	-0.48479	6.64e ⁻²²
METU Affiliation	7.377301735	2.985754	0.114578	0.013935863
Sightseeing	-8.48136535	4.138338	-0.12266	0.041131301

Monthly Income emerged as a key positive predictor ($\beta=0.166$, $p=0.0003$), indicating that as household income increases, so does the willingness to pay for the conservation of Lake Eymir. This finding aligns with economic theory, which suggests that higher disposable income often corresponds to greater capacity to allocate resources toward environmental goods and services (Field, 2018).

Metu Affiliation also exhibited a positive relationship ($\beta=0.115$, $p=0.014$), suggesting that individuals affiliated with the general public have a higher WTP compared to other groups.

Conversely, Sightseeing had a significant negative impact on WTP ($\beta = -0.123$, $p = 0.041$). This result may indicate that individuals who primarily engage in sightseeing tend to assign lower monetary value to conservation efforts, possibly because their interaction with the environment is observational rather than immersive or experiential. This finding highlights the importance of promoting active engagement with natural areas, as more participatory experiences may foster stronger emotional and financial support for conservation initiatives.

Bar chart of standardized coefficients (β) for the significant predictors. This visualization highlights the relative contributions of each variable to WTP, with Monthly Income showing the strongest positive effect and Sightseeing having the most notable negative impact (Figure 4.40).

Figure 4.40: Bar Chart of Significant Predictors

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Results

The ANOVA table (Table 4.25) checks how well the predictors explain WTP by separating the total variation into parts explained by the model and those left unexplained. The results indicate that the model is statistically significant, with an F-statistic of 4.19 and a corresponding p-value < 0.001 . This confirms that the predictors collectively explain a significant proportion of the variance in WTP (Field, 2018).

Table 4.25 ANOVA Table

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	164223.672	54	3041.179	4.190	0
Residual	264902.411	365	725.760	-	-
Total	429126.083	419	-	-	-

The Sum of Squares (Regression) is 164,223.67, which represents the explained variance, while the Sum of Squares (Residual) is 264,902.41, indicating the

unexplained variance. The total variance, as indicated by the Sum of Squares (Total), is 429,126.08 (Figure 4.41). These results demonstrate the model's ability to capture approximately 38.3% of the total variance in WTP (as detailed in the model summary).

Figure 4.41: Bar Chart of ANOVA

Residual Analysis

The residuals were analyzed to assess the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity, which are critical for the validity of the regression model (Table 4.26). Two visualizations were generated: a histogram of residuals (Figure 4.42) and a scatterplot of residuals versus predicted values (Figure 4.43).

Table 4.26 Residual Statistics

Statistic	Predicted		Standardized
	Values	Residuals	Residuals
Minimum	-25.4125	-67.0806	-2.66785
Maximum	87.4263	70.50099	2.803879
Mean	43.08333	$-3.77e^{-15}$	0
Standard Deviation	19.79752	25.14409	1

The histogram of residuals (Figure 4.42) follow a roughly normal pattern, centered around zero, confirming that the model's predictions are reliable for statistical testing (Field, 2018).

Figure 4.42: Histogram of Residuals

The scatterplot of residuals versus predicted values (Figure 4.43) shows residuals evenly distributed around the horizontal line at zero, without any noticeable patterns or trends. This indicates homoscedasticity, meaning the variance of residuals is

consistent across all levels of predicted values. This assumption ensures that the regression coefficients remain unbiased and efficient (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

Figure 4.43: Residuals vs. Predicted Values Scatterplot

Together, these results confirm that the residuals meet the necessary assumptions for linear regression, reinforcing the reliability of the model's findings.

Collinearity Diagnostics Analysis

The collinearity diagnostics check how much predictors overlap using condition indices and variance proportions. (see Figure 4.44). This analysis helps ensure the predictors contribute uniquely to explaining variance in the dependent variable WTP.

The condition index measures how much predictors overlap. Values above 15 suggest mild overlap, and those above 30 indicate serious overlap (Hair et al., 2019).

In my model, condition indices range from 1.0 to approximately 20.62. Dimensions with indices exceeding 15 are associated with mild multicollinearity concerns, requiring further exploration of their variance proportions.

Variance proportions show how much each predictor contributes to shared variation. If many predictors show high proportions in the same area, it could mean they overlap too much.

Key observations include:

- Monthly Income which exhibits higher variance proportions in the 2nd and 3rd dimensions (e.g., 0.000985), indicating moderate overlap with other predictors.
- Visit Frequency which shows notable variance proportions in the 2nd dimension (e.g., 0.005903), suggesting shared variance with activity-related variables.
- Ecosystem Service Variables: Maintain consistently low variance proportions (< 0.001) across all dimensions, indicating minimal contribution to multicollinearity.
- Categorical Variables (e.g., Gender, District): Display scattered, small variance proportions, reflecting low multicollinearity.

The relationship between condition indices and variance proportions is illustrated in Figure 4.44. Blue bars represent condition indices for each dimension, with values exceeding 15 (marked by the red dashed line) indicating moderate multicollinearity. The orange line represents the maximum variance proportions for predictors in each dimension. The chart highlights that while certain dimensions show elevated indices and variance proportions, these do not surpass critical thresholds for severe multicollinearity.

Figure 4.44: Condition Indices and Maximum Variance Proportions

The condition index plot highlights the values across dimensions, with a reference line marking the typical threshold of concern (15). These visuals support your interpretation of manageable multicollinearity in the model (Figure 4.45).

Figure 4.45: Condition Index Across Dimensions

The variance proportions heatmap (Figure 4.46) highlights how each predictor contributes to shared variance across model dimensions. Most predictors, such as

Gender and Ecosystem Service variables, consistently show minimal contributions (darker blue), indicating low multicollinearity. However, Monthly Income and Visit Frequency exhibit slightly higher proportions in dimensions with moderate condition indices (around 4–5), suggesting some overlap but within acceptable limits. No dimension shows multiple predictors with high proportions, confirming the model’s stability and minimal multicollinearity.

Figure 4.46: Variance Proportions Heatmap

In conclusion, the collinearity diagnostics suggest manageable levels of multicollinearity in the model. These findings indicate that the predictors do not exhibit severe collinearity, affirming the robustness of the regression model.

Conclusion: Practical Insights from the Regression Analysis

The findings from this regression analysis provide valuable insights into the factors influencing willingness to pay (WTP) for Lake Eymir’s conservation. The model explains a significant portion of the variability in WTP, capturing 38.3% of the

variance, which aligns with expectations for environmental economics studies. This result highlights the utility of the predictors in understanding the economic valuation of environmental resources.

Key predictors such as Monthly Income and Affiliation with METU positively impact WTP, reinforcing the importance of economic capacity and institutional connections in shaping environmental support. Conversely, the negative impact of Sightseeing suggests that individuals engaging passively with the environment may place less monetary value on conservation efforts. These findings underscore the nuanced interplay between demographic, economic, and activity-based factors in environmental valuation, providing a foundation for tailored policy and outreach strategies to enhance conservation funding and public support.

By meeting the assumptions of linear regression and demonstrating manageable multicollinearity levels, the analysis confirms the reliability of the model. Practically, these results can inform decision-makers on prioritizing income-based and community-affiliated engagement to maximize conservation efforts for Lake Eymir.

4.3.1.7 Determinants of the Value Typologies

Building on the investigation of how various determinants relate to WTP, a correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between personal values and willingness to pay. The results revealed weak and negative correlations, suggesting that personal values alone may not directly influence WTP in this dataset (Table 4.27).

Table 4.27 Value Correlations

Value Variable	Variable Name	Correlation
Use value & instrumental value	Value_DirectBenefit_Recode	-0.098
Option value & instrumental value	Value_FutureBenefit_Recode	-0.064
Non-use value, bequest value, & instrumental value	Value_Generations_Recode	-0.103
Non-use value, existence value, intrinsic value	Value_Existence_Recode	-0.093

Recognizing the complexity of value systems and their potential indirect effects, broader analyses were undertaken to explore the relationships between these values and other socio-demographic and attitudinal factors measured in the survey. This approach aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of the underlying drivers of environmental values and their implications for conservation decision-making.

4.3.1.7.1 Regression for Value Typologies, WTP and Socio-Economic Controls

First, a regression model was set (Table 4.28) to include the WTP as the dependent variable and predictors as value variables (direct, future, generational, existence) and socio-economic controls (income, education and age). R-squared value was 0.06 which meant 6.4% of the variance in WTP is explained by the model, while adjusted R-squared was 0.046 and F-statistic was 3.583 ($p = 0.000959$, significant).

Table 4.28 Regression Results: Values and WTP

Variable	Coefficient	p-value	95% confidence interval	Interpretation
Constant	40.66	0.000	[20.02, 61.31]	Baseline WTP when all predictors are zero
Value_DirectBenefit	-2.33	0.163	[-5.61, 0.95]	No significant effect
Value_FutureBenefit	1.34	0.504	[-2.60, 5.28]	No significant effect
Value_Generations	-2.95	0.303	[-8.58, 2.68]	No significant effect.
Value_Existence	1.33	0.605	[-3.73, 6.39]	No significant effect.
Monthly_income	0.0001	0.000	[0.00005, 0.0001]	Significant positive effect: higher income predicts higher WTP.
Education_Recode	-0.033	0.983	[-3.12, 3.05]	No significant effect
Age	0.296	0.164	[-0.12, 0.71]	Positive but not significant

The results showed that none of the personal value variables significantly predicted WTP after controlling for socio-economic factors. This suggests that values like direct benefit or future benefit do not directly drive WTP in this dataset.

Monthly income significantly and positively influenced WTP ($p < 0.001$), confirming its importance as a key predictor. The controls, education and age did not significantly affect WTP.

4.3.1.7.2 Direct Benefit (Use value & Instrumental Value)

Focusing on the values and their possible determinants, the regression analysis was conducted to identify the predictors of the variable Direct Benefit, with a model including the following independent variables: Age, Monthly Income, Education, Employment, and Gender. The model explained 3.4% of the variance in the dependent variable, as indicated by an R-squared value of 0.034. The adjusted R-squared value was slightly lower at 0.021, reflecting the limited explanatory power of the model.

The overall model was statistically significant ($F = 2.616$, $p = 0.0243$), indicating that the included predictors collectively contribute to explaining variations in the value respondents place on direct benefits. Among the predictors, Employment was the only significant variable ($p = 0.006$), showing a positive relationship with the dependent variable. This finding suggests that individuals in higher employment categories tend to place greater importance on direct benefits.

In contrast, the other predictors—Age, Monthly Income, Education, and Gender—did not have a significant influence on Direct Benefit value. These results highlight employment status as a key factor in shaping respondents' valuation of direct benefits, while demographic variables such as age, income, education, and gender appear less relevant in this context.

4.3.1.7.3 Future Benefit (Option value & instrumental value)

The regression analysis examined the predictors of Future Benefit, using Age, Monthly Income, Education, Employment, and Gender as independent variables.

The model explained 2.9% of the variance in the dependent variable, as indicated by an R-squared value of 0.029, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.015, reflecting limited explanatory power.

The overall model approached significance ($F = 2.164$, $p = 0.0575$) but was not statistically significant, suggesting that the predictors collectively had a marginally insignificant impact on explaining variations in the importance respondents place on future benefits. Among the predictors, Age showed a significant negative relationship with the dependent variable, indicating that older respondents tend to assign lower importance to future benefits. This could reflect a shift in focus towards immediate concerns or generational considerations as individuals age.

Employment was marginally significant ($p = 0.064$), suggesting a potential positive relationship with the value placed on future benefits. This may imply that individuals with stable employment or higher employment categories are more likely to prioritize future benefits, possibly due to their capacity for long-term planning.

The remaining predictors—Monthly Income, Education, and Gender—did not significantly influence the prioritization of future benefits. These findings highlight age as a key factor in valuing future benefits, with employment status playing a suggestive but less definitive role. Demographic variables such as income, education, and gender appear to have minimal impact in this context.

4.3.1.7.4 Generational Benefits (Non-use value, bequest value, & instrumental value)

The regression analysis explored the predictors of dependent variable intergenerational value, incorporating Age, Monthly Income, Education, Employment, and Gender as independent variables. The model explained 3.2% of the variance in the dependent variable, as indicated by an R-squared value of 0.032, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.019. These results suggest that the model has modest explanatory power.

The overall model was statistically significant ($F = 2.463$, $p = 0.0326$), indicating that the predictors collectively influence the importance respondents place on generational benefits. Among the predictors, Age showed a significant negative relationship with the dependent variable, suggesting that older respondents are less likely to prioritize generational benefits. This may reflect a focus on immediate concerns or alternative values as individuals age.

Education demonstrated a significant positive relationship with Generational variable, indicating that respondents with higher education levels are more likely to emphasize the importance of generational benefits. This finding aligns with the possibility that higher education fosters greater environmental awareness or altruistic attitudes.

The remaining predictors—Monthly Income, Employment, and Gender—did not significantly influence the prioritization of generational benefits.

In summary, this analysis highlights age and education as key factors in shaping respondents' valuation of generational benefits. Older respondents and those with lower education levels are less likely to assign importance to these values, suggesting demographic and cognitive influences on attitudes toward intergenerational priorities.

4.3.1.7.5 Existence (Non-use value, existence value, intrinsic value)

The regression analysis examined the predictors of existence (variable coded as Value_Existence_Recode in the dataset), using Age, Monthly Income, Education, Employment, and Gender as independent variables. The model explained 3.9% of the variance in the dependent variable, as indicated by an R-squared value of 0.039, with an adjusted R-squared of 0.026, suggesting modest explanatory power.

The overall model was statistically significant ($F = 2.959$, $p = 0.0124$), indicating that the predictors collectively contribute to explaining variations in the importance respondents place on existence values. Among the predictors, Age showed a

significant negative relationship with the dependent variable, suggesting that older respondents are less likely to prioritize existence values. This pattern is consistent with findings from other value variables analyzed, potentially reflecting a shift in focus toward immediate or tangible concerns as individuals age.

Monthly Income also demonstrated a significant negative relationship with existence values, indicating that respondents with higher incomes are less likely to emphasize these intrinsic environmental values. This may reflect a tendency among higher-income individuals to prioritize practical or utilitarian concerns over intrinsic environmental values.

The other predictors—Education, Employment, and Gender—did not significantly influence the importance placed on existence values.

In summary, the analysis identifies age and income as significant factors influencing the prioritization of existence values. Younger respondents and those with lower incomes are more likely to value the intrinsic importance of environmental preservation, highlighting demographic differences in attitudes toward these values.

4.3.1.7.6 Implications from Regression Analysis of the Value Typologies

Summary of regression analysis generated interesting and meaningful results summarized in the following table (Table 4.29).

Table 4.29 Summary of Regression Results

Values	Value variables	Significant Predictors	R-squared (%)
Use value & instrumental value	DirectBenefit	Employment (positive)	3.4
Option value & instrumental value	FutureBenefit	Age (negative)	2.9
Non-use value, bequest value, & instrumental value	Generations	Age (negative), Education (positive)	3.2
Non-use value, existence value, intrinsic value	Existence	Age (negative), Monthly Income (negative)	3.9

For direct benefits, employment emerged as a significant positive predictor of the importance respondents assigned to direct benefits. Those in stable employment categories were more likely to prioritize immediate and utilitarian advantages, suggesting that economic security influences perceptions of direct benefits. This finding aligns with the instrumental value framework, which emphasizes practical considerations and tangible outcomes as dominant factors in decision-making.

As for future benefits, age showed a significant negative relationship with the importance placed on future benefits, indicating that younger respondents were more inclined to emphasize long-term environmental considerations. This generational shift reflects an increasing preference among younger individuals for preserving resources to ensure future utility and flexibility. This trend aligns with the concept of option value, where the preservation of environmental resources safeguards opportunities for future generations.

In terms of generational benefits, both age and education significantly influenced the prioritization of generational benefits. Older respondents were less likely to assign importance to these benefits, while individuals with higher levels of education showed a stronger inclination to value them. This dynamic can be understood through the bequest value framework, which highlights the ethical responsibility to future generations. Education appears to play a critical role in fostering awareness and appreciation of these obligations.

As far as existence values concerned, age and income were significant negative predictors of the importance attributed to existence values. Younger respondents and those with lower incomes demonstrated a greater commitment to intrinsic environmental ethics, valuing nature for its inherent worth rather than its utility to humans. This perspective resonates with eco-centric philosophies, which prioritize the moral value of nature independent of human exploitation or use.

CHAPTER 5

TOTAL ECONOMIC VALUE OF LAKE EYMIR

Lake Eymir serves as a vital urban resource, offering a range of ecological, recreational, and cultural benefits to local communities. This chapter presents an economic valuation of Lake Eymir using survey-based Willingness to Pay (WTP) data and i-Tree Canopy analysis. The valuation encompasses direct use, indirect use, and non-use values, providing a multi-faceted understanding of the lake's economic significance. Rather than aggregating these components into a single Total Economic Value (TEV) figure, this study highlights each dimension independently to avoid potential double counting and maintain methodological clarity.

Like any other ecosystem, Lake Eymir is ultimately invaluable—its ecological, cultural, and emotional significance to people and the environment transcends monetary metrics. This study seeks to highlight and quantify dimensions of value that are often overlooked by neoclassical economics or, for instance, by traditional real estate valuation, both of which typically emphasize market-based, extractive, or utilitarian uses.

Although the terminology suggests a comprehensive figure, the concept of *Total Economic Value* (TEV) in this context should not be misunderstood as representing the market price or sale value of Lake Eymir as a whole. Rather, TEV is an analytical framework in environmental economics designed to capture the broad range of benefits—both use and non-use—that individuals derive from ecosystem services.

This study does not attempt to estimate the lake's full TEV. Instead, it focuses on a limited subset of services, primarily cultural and recreational benefits, as captured through respondents' stated Willingness to Pay (WTP) for conservation, along with biophysical assessments provided by i-Tree Canopy. While the TEV framework is valuable for structuring ecosystem valuation, the results presented here should be

interpreted as a partial and service-specific estimate, not as a measure of the lake's total economic worth.

The findings offer policy-relevant insight into the economic significance of Lake Eymir's ecosystem services, underscoring the reality that natural environments hold substantial value—even when they are not traded in markets. Care should be taken not to interpret these findings as exhaustive, or as an attempt to monetize the lake in its entirety. Therefore, it is crucial to approach the results with the understanding that no valuation method can fully encapsulate the profound and multifaceted worth of natural ecosystems.

5.1 Components of Lake Eymir's TEV

5.1.1 Direct Use Values: Willingness to Pay Analysis

The direct use values of Lake Eymir were assessed through a contingent valuation survey measuring respondents' WTP for its conservation. The mean WTP was calculated as 48.64 TRY, with a median of 50.00 TRY. This close alignment between central tendencies indicates a robust measure of respondents' valuation of the lake's recreational and aesthetic benefits.

Most contingent valuation studies estimate the mean Willingness to Pay (WTP) and stop at the individual level, using this value as a policy-relevant indicator of public support or perceived benefit. This is a widely accepted approach in the environmental valuation literature, particularly when the goal is to highlight non-market values of ecosystem services without necessarily aggregating them. However, in this study, we sought to take the analysis one step further by estimating the potential annual revenue that could be raised through an entry fee, using the mean WTP as a proxy. In the absence of official visitation statistics and given that a large proportion of respondents reported having visited Lake Eymir at least once in the past year, we extrapolated the mean WTP to the population of the most represented

districts as a conservative estimate of possible conservation funding. There are established practices in environmental economics, where individual WTP estimates are scaled to relevant populations to assess total economic value (Birol et al., 2006; Brander, 2023; Carson & Hanemann, 2005; Dahal et al., 2018; Loomis et al., 2000; Milon & Scrogin, 2006). This additional step is intended to provide practical insights for resource management and financing strategies while acknowledging the assumptions involved.

The selected districts—Çankaya, Yenimahalle, Keçiören, and Etimesgut—were chosen for extrapolation based on several key criteria. These districts collectively accounted for over 85% of survey respondents, ensuring that the analysis is representative and grounded in robust data. Their high respondent numbers enhance the reliability of the findings and reduce variability in the Willingness to Pay (WTP) estimates.

Additionally, these districts were selected for their geographic and policy relevance. Located in close proximity to Lake Eymir, their residents are among the primary beneficiaries of the lake's recreational and ecological services. This spatial connection supports the rationale for their inclusion, consistent with established contingent valuation practices, which emphasize surveying populations directly tied to the resource being valued (Loomis et al., 2000). Moreover, these districts represent a substantial portion of the population likely to be affected by any conservation-related interventions. Focusing on them allows the valuation results to offer actionable, locally grounded insights that can inform resource management and funding strategies, ensuring that conservation efforts align with the priorities and well-being of the most impacted communities.

5.1.1.1 Population Data and Extrapolated WTP

Building on the rationale outlined above, the aggregate WTP for each district was estimated using the latest population figures published by the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK), as detailed below:

- **Çankaya (925,828 residents):** $48.64 \times 925,828 = 45,020,000$ TRY
- **Yenimahalle (706,000 residents):** $48.64 \times 706,000 = 34,340,000$ TRY
- **Keçiören (939,000 residents):** $48.64 \times 939,000 = 45,680,000$ TRY
- **Etimesgut (699,000 residents):** $48.64 \times 699,000 = 33,990,000$ TRY

The total aggregated WTP for these districts was estimated at 159,030,000 TRY, reflecting the substantial value that residents assign to the conservation of Lake Eymir. It is important to underscore that this figure represents a potential **annual revenue** that could be generated through entrance fees based on the mean WTP, rather than a definitive market price or comprehensive valuation of the lake itself.

5.1.2 Indirect Use Values: Ecosystem Services

Indirect use values were assessed through i-Tree Canopy analysis, which quantified the annual and cumulative benefits of ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir’s vegetation (Figure 5.1). These services play a critical role in maintaining environmental quality and urban sustainability, encompassing carbon sequestration, air pollution removal, and hydrological regulation.

Figure 5.1: i-Tree Canopy Results Summary

The analysis revealed significant contributions from carbon sequestration and storage. Annually, the lake's vegetation sequesters approximately 267.19 tonnes of carbon, which is equivalent to 979.68 tonnes of CO₂. This sequestration has an estimated economic value of 50,231 USD per year. Over time, the cumulative carbon storage in the lake's ecosystem has reached 10,422.69 tonnes of carbon (or 38,216.52 tonnes of CO₂), valued at an impressive 1,959,465 USD. These results emphasize the long-term role of Lake Eymir as a vital carbon sink, contributing significantly to climate change mitigation.

Air pollution removal represents another critical benefit. Each year, the lake's vegetation removes a total of 12,445.55 kilograms of pollutants, valued at 64,539 USD annually. Among these, the removal of ozone (O₃) provides the highest economic value at 29,519 USD, followed by particulate matter (PM₁₀) at 22,874 USD. These ecosystem services enhance public health and mitigate urban pollution, underscoring the importance of preserving the lake's green cover.

Hydrological benefits were also quantified, demonstrating the lake's role in regulating water resources. The analysis estimates that the vegetation around Lake Eymir prevents 17.59 megaliters of stormwater runoff annually, valued at 41,513 USD. Additional contributions include transpiration (189.84 megaliters) and evaporation (59.56 megaliters), which regulate the microclimate and support water cycling. These findings highlight the lake's function in reducing flood risks, maintaining water quality, and supporting urban resilience.

Collectively, the total annual value of these indirect benefits reinforces the ecological importance of Lake Eymir to Ankara's urban environment. These services provide not only substantial economic value but also significant ecological and social benefits, emphasizing the need for sustained conservation efforts.

5.1.2.1 Non-Use Values: Existence and Bequest

Non-use values were assessed by analyzing survey responses regarding the lake's intrinsic and intergenerational importance. Respondents who strongly agreed with statements about the lake's existence and bequest value demonstrated a mean WTP of 48.64 TRY. These responses highlight the ethical and cultural significance of conserving Lake Eymir, irrespective of direct usage. The third category of Total Economic Value (TEV), alongside non-use and use values, is the option value, which was also assessed in the WTP survey through a question about future benefits.

5.1.3 Integrated Interpretation

The findings from the WTP analysis, i-Tree Canopy results, and non-use valuation collectively demonstrate the multifaceted significance of Lake Eymir. While this study avoids aggregating these components into a single TEV figure to maintain methodological clarity, it emphasizes the substantial direct, indirect, and non-use values associated with the lake. These results provide robust evidence for the importance of Lake Eymir to local communities, informing conservation priorities and policy development. Furthermore, they offer a foundation for designing sustainable financing mechanisms that align with public preferences and ecological needs. Future efforts should aim to integrate ecological, economic, and socio-cultural assessments to ensure that conservation strategies reflect the full spectrum of ecosystem value. In doing so, policymakers can better align environmental protection with public interest, promoting long-term resilience and shared stewardship.

5.1.4 Policy and Management Implications

The valuation of Lake Eymir in this study, provides a structured evidence base supporting its strategic significance within regional conservation and urban

sustainability agendas. The results emphasize the presence of substantial direct use, indirect use, and non-use values, indicating the necessity of an integrated policy approach that reflects both biophysical functions and socio-cultural relevance.

From a resource management perspective, the extrapolated aggregate WTP of 159,030,000 TRY serves as an indicative proxy for the scale of potential annual revenue that could be mobilized through a structured access or user fee mechanism. Although not a TEV estimate per se, this figure supports the economic justification for sustained investment in conservation infrastructure. It may inform the design of cost-recovery schemes, particularly within public finance and environmental fund allocation models. Targeted uses for such funding could include ecosystem restoration, water quality enhancement, and visitor infrastructure improvements, all of which align with adaptive lake management objectives.

The i-Tree Canopy assessment further quantifies key ecosystem service outputs, such as carbon sequestration, pollutant filtration, and stormwater regulation, which represent essential urban environmental assets. These outputs should be embedded in ecosystem accounting frameworks and recognized within urban planning instruments as natural capital inputs contributing to climate resilience, public health, and cost savings in infrastructure maintenance. Their valuation reinforces the relevance of Lake Eymir in broader green infrastructure and ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) strategies.

The identification of strong non-use values, including cultural, existence, and bequest motivations, underscores the need to incorporate ethical and heritage-based perspectives into conservation frameworks. Policymakers should consider mechanisms for public engagement and co-management, including stakeholder consultation processes, environmental education programs, and citizen science initiatives. These approaches align with principles of environmental democracy and can enhance social acceptance and compliance with conservation measures.

In sum, the valuation outcomes presented in this study offer actionable inputs for the formulation of evidence-based, cross-sectoral policies that integrate economic,

ecological, and social dimensions of lake management. Institutional uptake of these findings can enhance the operational effectiveness of environmental governance in Ankara, positioning Lake Eymir as a model for urban ecosystem valuation and sustainable landscape stewardship.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

The valuation of ecosystem services (ES) is a multifaceted endeavor that bridges ecological science, economic principles, and ethical considerations. This thesis systematically explored the theoretical foundations, methodological applications, and practical implications of ES valuation, with a particular focus on Lake Eymir. The findings provide a robust framework for understanding how the interplay of intrinsic and instrumental values can shape sustainable policy and conservation strategies.

This research underscores the necessity of an interdisciplinary perspective in ES valuation. By integrating environmental ethics, economics, and advanced analytical tools such as i-Tree Canopy and contingent valuation, the study bridges the gap between theoretical discourse and practical application. The combined use of the Total Economic Value (TEV) framework and ecosystem service classifications demonstrates how complex ecological benefits can be quantified and effectively communicated to policymakers and stakeholders. Through this dual-method approach, the i-Tree Canopy tool quantified tangible services such as carbon sequestration and air quality regulation, while the Willingness-to-Pay (WTP) survey captured both use and non-use values, including existence and bequest values. This integration ensures that both material and immaterial dimensions of ES are incorporated into conservation strategies.

Beyond its ecological and cultural significance, Lake Eymir can also be classified as a mixed good: it is partially rival, as its use is generally non-rival under normal conditions, but excessive visitation can lead to crowding and reduce the quality of experience for others and it is also partially excludable due to access controls maintained by Middle East Technical University. This economic classification is

especially relevant for understanding the applicability of stated preference methods such as WTP. Unlike pure public goods, where free-rider problems often challenge voluntary contributions, the partial excludability of mixed goods makes individual financial support for conservation more realistic and policy-relevant. Acknowledging this aspect not only reinforces the theoretical coherence of the study but also supports the design of sustainable financing and governance strategies for similar ecosystems.

This study also gains relevance in light of the ongoing transition from orthodox to heterodox economic paradigms, particularly in the context of environmental valuation. Orthodox economics, rooted in market efficiency and individual utility, has long struggled to account for the full value of nature—especially non-market goods and long-term environmental concerns. In contrast, heterodox approaches increasingly emphasize ecological limits, ethical considerations, and the integration of social values into economic decision-making. WTP studies, while expressed in monetary terms, serve as a bridge between these paradigms. By capturing both use and non-use values, they reflect a broader understanding of what people value—not only in terms of consumption, but also in relation to identity, legacy, and intergenerational responsibility.

Supporting WTP research, therefore, is not only about refining valuation techniques—it is also about contributing to a more inclusive and responsive economic narrative. A narrative that acknowledges markets alone cannot reflect the complexity of human–environment relationships, and that public preferences deserve a meaningful role in shaping environmental policy.

In the case of Lake Eymir, this approach has revealed how citizens value the lake not only for its recreational offerings but also for its ecological integrity, symbolic meaning, and future existence. These insights are particularly relevant for countries like Türkiye, where economic and environmental challenges increasingly demand policies that are both socially grounded and ecologically informed. As Türkiye navigates its own shift toward more participatory and sustainability-oriented

governance, tools like WTP can support decision-making processes that better reflect public priorities and long-term ecological goals.

This study offers a partial yet meaningful account of Lake Eymir's value, focusing primarily on cultural and recreational services captured through WTP surveys and biophysical assessments. While these methods provide policy-relevant estimates, they do not—and cannot—fully represent the lake's total worth. The concept of Total Economic Value (TEV) serves here not as a singular monetary figure, but as a framework to structure and communicate the diverse benefits people associate with the lake. By presenting value components separately rather than as an aggregated figure, the study avoids double counting and maintains methodological clarity. More importantly, it acknowledges that Lake Eymir's ecological, cultural, and emotional significance transcends economic metrics. In this respect, the valuation is not an attempt to reduce nature to market logic, but rather to illuminate aspects of value often overlooked by conventional policy and planning processes.

The annual value of ecosystem services—such as carbon sequestration, air pollution removal, and hydrological benefits—was estimated at approximately 156,283 USD. The cumulative carbon storage value reached 1,959,465 USD, underlining the long-term ecological importance of the lake. Meanwhile, the survey revealed a mean WTP of 48.64 TRY and a median of 50.00 TRY. When extrapolated to the broader relevant population, the annual aggregate WTP amounted to 159,030,000 TRY—offering a strong proxy for the potential scale of voluntary or policy-driven conservation funding.

It is important to note that these WTP figures were collected prior to the sharp inflationary period Türkiye experienced following the survey. Although these nominal values may appear modest by today's standards, they reflected substantial public support at the time and signified a meaningful willingness to contribute under the prevailing economic conditions. This underscores the importance of interpreting valuation results within their appropriate temporal and macroeconomic contexts, especially in countries facing economic volatility.

A key contribution of this thesis is its attempt to bridge intrinsic and instrumental dimensions of value within ES valuation. Rather than treating them as opposing paradigms, the research presents them as interconnected ways in which people relate to nature. By employing both biophysical models and contingent valuation, the study captured a wide range of values—from tangible ecosystem functions to ethical, emotional, and cultural attachments. This integrative approach highlights the limitations of purely economic or ecological assessments when used in isolation. While monetary estimates provide policy-relevant data, they gain true significance when interpreted in the broader context of public moral concern and personal connection to nature. The inclusion of qualitative motivations in the WTP survey—such as valuing the lake’s existence independent of human benefit—demonstrates that valuation can and should reflect both ethical principles and practical considerations.

By recognizing both the moral standing of ecosystems and their measurable services, this thesis promotes a more nuanced and holistic understanding of environmental value. This aligns with emerging perspectives in sustainability science, which call for reconciling ecological integrity with social legitimacy in conservation practice.

The findings of this thesis offer significant policy and practical implications. First, they highlight the critical role of urban ecosystems in mitigating challenges such as air pollution, climate change, and water management. Policymakers are encouraged to integrate ES valuation into urban planning frameworks to ensure that natural assets like Lake Eymir are preserved and enhanced for long-term sustainability. Second, the study advocates for a balanced approach that respects ecological boundaries while meeting human needs. By embedding ethical considerations into economic frameworks, decision-makers can design policies that are both equitable and effective—particularly relevant for rapidly urbanizing areas. Third, the WTP survey illustrates the importance of public engagement. Beyond measuring economic contributions, it revealed public values and fostered environmental awareness. Involving communities in valuation processes can lead to more resilient, adaptive, and democratically grounded management strategies.

Building on these insights, the thesis outlines several recommendations for future research. Advancing methodological scope through emerging technologies—such as machine learning—could improve land cover classification and valuation accuracy in tools like i-Tree Canopy. Longitudinal studies would also enable researchers to track changes in ecosystem service values over time and assess the effects of environmental policies or climatic shifts. Extending the methodology to a variety of ecosystems would help assess its generalizability, while comparative studies between urban and rural settings could uncover both shared patterns and context-specific differences. Lastly, integrating climate projections into ES valuation would offer more robust assessments of ecosystem resilience and the long-term economic implications of conservation under climate change scenarios.

In broader reflection, this thesis contributes to the growing literature on ecosystem services by emphasizing their central role in sustainable development. By combining ethical, ecological, and economic dimensions, it offers a replicable model for valuing urban ecosystems in ways that resonate with both policymakers and the public. Lake Eymir, in this context, serves as a microcosm of the broader challenges and opportunities associated with ecosystem-based management in urban areas. Through its case study, this research demonstrates how ES valuation can inform conservation, deepen public engagement, and guide policy toward long-term ecological and societal resilience. The findings aim to support ongoing efforts to protect Lake Eymir and inspire similar initiatives elsewhere—fostering a deeper, more conscious harmony between humanity and nature.

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APPENDICES

A. Survey in English

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR DOCTORAL STUDY ON

“VALUATION OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES: PHILOSOPHY, ECOLOGY AND POLICY”

Funda Yakar, a PhD student at METU is carrying out this survey for her dissertation. Thank you for participating in this survey which is part of a doctoral research exploring the valuation of ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir and the value that the public places on it. Your opinion is valuable even if you have not visited Lake Eymir. Please answer each question to the best of your ability. This survey consists of 15 questions with a combination of multiple-choice, rating scale, and open-ended formats and takes about 7-10 minutes to complete. In this survey, you will not be required to disclose any personal or institutional identification information. Your responses will be kept strictly confidential and will only be used for research purposes. The questionnaire is designed to be non-intrusive, but if any questions cause discomfort or for any reason you feel uncomfortable, you are free to discontinue the survey and withdraw from the study at any point.

Should you need more information regarding the survey, you can contact Funda Yakar at the phone number [REDACTED] or [REDACTED] email address.

I have read the information above and I am participating this survey voluntarily.

I understand and accept that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the survey and that I can withdraw at any stage without any problems.

Lake Eymir, located about 20 kilometers south of Ankara, Turkey, is within the Middle East Technical University campus but is open to public visits, offering various recreational opportunities. The lake and its surroundings feature a substantial flora and fauna, including over 200 bird species, 700 plant species, as well as foxes, badgers, and weasels. The lake's shores are surrounded by a diverse landscape of wetlands, forests, and steppes. The picturesque surroundings boast flourishing reedbeds, almond, black pines, scotch pines, Taurus cedars, and expansive grassy steppes that harbour butterfly and flower species, including endemic ones. The lake itself is a habitat for variety of aquatic plants, planktons, and fish species. The globally significant wetlands extending from Mogan to Eymir are crucial habitats for numerous bird species, especially during migration season. However, these invaluable assets face endangerment due to urban and industrial pressures, pollution, misuse, and climate change.

1. What is your Monthly total net household income? _____ (TRY)
2. Age: _____
3. Gender: Male Female Other Prefer not to disclose
4. District: _____
5. Highest Level of Education:
 Non-literate Primary School Secondary School Primary Education
 High School Some university level courses (not graduated) Associate's Degree
 Bachelor's Degree Master's Degree Doctoral Degree
6. Employment Status:
 Employed Unemployed Retired Student
7. Are you affiliated with METU?
 Student Alumni Academic Staff Administrative Staff
 Relative to any of the above None

8. Have you visited Lake Eymir in the past 12 months?

Yes No (*If no, please leave the questions 9 and 10 blank*)

9. In total, how often did you visit Lake Eymir in the past 12 months?

1 to 3 times 4 to 5 times 6 to 9 times 10 or more times 20 or more times

10. Have you done any of the activities below in the past 12 months at Lake Eymir? Please check all that apply.

(Please note that the items below are listed in alphabetical order and does not indicate any order of importance.)

- Art and cultural activities
- Biking
- Birdwatching or other wildlife and nature observation
- Cycle Boating
- Education/Science
- Fishing
- Foraging for wild edibles (herbs, berries, mushrooms etc.)
- Hiking
- Photography
- Picnic
- Resting/retreat
- Rowing
- Sightseeing
- Socializing
- Special event
- Sports and training
- Visiting restaurants and cafes around the lake
- Other. Please specify: _____

11. Lake Eymir is located within the boundaries of Gölbaşı Municipality, included in the Special Environmental Protection Area (SEPA) declared by the Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation, and Climate Change, and is situated on the Middle East Technical University (METU) campus. The conservation, preservation, and maintenance of Eymir Lake fall under the responsibility of these institutions and are primarily financed by METU. Suppose that funding from these institutions were insufficient, and contributions from individuals were strictly needed; otherwise, the lake would potentially cease to exist. This contribution would take the form of an entry fee for each visit to the lake. Please note that the money from this contribution would directly go to a fund created for Lake Eymir, exclusively used for preserving its wetland, forest, and lake ecosystems, biological diversity, and funding its recreational opportunities.

What is the maximum amount of money, if any, that you would be willing to pay as an entry fee for each visit to Lake Eymir, knowing that it would contribute to its protection? Please consider your monthly income before you answer this question.

- 0 TRY 5 TRY 10 TRY 15 TRY 20 TRY 25 TRY
- 30 TRY 35 TRY 40 TRY 45 TRY 50 TRY 75 TRY
- 80 TRY 85 TRY 90 TRY 95 TRY 100 TRY Above 100 TRY

12. On a scale from 1 to 10, how certain are you in choosing the amount of money you checked above if you actually had to pay? (1=very uncertain, 10=very certain).

Very uncertain	Very certain
1	10
2	9
3	8
4	7
5	6
6	5
7	4
8	3
9	2

13. If you selected 0 TRY for question 11, please tell why (check one **single** most important reason).
(If you did not select 0 TRY for question 10, please skip this question.)

- I cannot afford to pay any amount.
- I don't think protection of Lake Eymir would cost that much.
- Lake Eymir should be funded by the government and with tax money.
- Payments should be made on a voluntary basis and/or with donations.
- Lake Eymir is not worth anything to me.
- Lake Eymir is important to me but I refuse to put a financial value on it.
- Other (please specify): _____

14. An ecosystem is defined as a dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment interacting as a functional unit. Ecosystem services are the direct and indirect benefits that humans obtain from ecosystems.

Lake Eymir provides a wide range of ecosystem services since the area is a composition of wetland, grassland, steppe, water and forest ecosystems. Among the ecosystem services provided by Lake Eymir, please rate the importance of each ecosystem service to you on a scale of 1 to 5.

(1=not at all important, 5=very important)

(Please note that the items below are listed in alphabetical order and does not indicate any order of importance.)

	1	2	3	4	5	No Opinion
Air quality maintenance (e.g. removal of pollutant gases and particles from the atmosphere)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Atmospheric oxygen production (e.g. trees and planktons producing oxygen via photosynthesis)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Carbon storage (e.g. storage of carbon within plants, soil and water as a result of carbon dioxide consumption)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Climate regulation (e.g. mitigating global warming via removal of greenhouse gases from the atmosphere)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cultural heritage	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Education/Science	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Erosion control (e.g. protection of soil by vegetation cover from external impacts such as water and wind erosion)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Food (e.g. fruit, herbs, fish)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fresh water supply	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fuel (e.g. firewood, pine cones, resin)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Natural hazard protection (e.g. storm, flood, landslide)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nutrient cycling (e.g. carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, phosphorus cycles)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Habitat provision and biological diversity	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Inspirational/Aesthetic/Scenic	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pest and disease control (e.g. preventing overpopulation of some harmful species through interspecies competition)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Pollination (a process required for plants to reproduce and ensure the continuation their offspring)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Primary production (photosynthesis & chemosynthesis)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Recreational activities	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social relations	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Soil formation (e.g. by physical, chemical, and biological processes)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Spiritual/Sentimental value (e.g. sense of belonging, memorial, holiness)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Water cycling (Continuous movements of water between the earth and the atmosphere thorough processes such as evaporation and precipitation)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Water purification (e.g. infiltration of surface waters from ground and forming pure ground water)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Water regulation (e.g. regulation of water regime, velocity and direction)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>

15. Please check the box which best describes how you feel about the statements below.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1. It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected because I directly benefit from it.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected, as I might benefit from it in the future, even if I do not currently benefit from it.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected for future generations whether I benefit from it or not.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. It is important to me that Lake Eymir is protected because it should exist, regardless of whether people benefit from it or not.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

B. Survey in Turkish

"EKOSİSTEM SERVİSLERİNİN KIYMETLENDİRİLMESİ: FELSEFE, EKOLOJİ VE POLİTİKA" KONULU DOKTORA ÇALIŞMASI ANKET FORMU

Bu anket çalışması, ODTÜ doktora öğrencisi Funda Yakar tarafından yürütülmektedir. Eymir Gölü'nün sağladığı ekosistem servislerinin değerlendirilmesi ve halkın Eymir Gölü'ne atfettiği değerin ortaya çıkarılmasını araştıran bir doktora tez çalışmasının parçası olan bu ankete katılımınız için teşekkür ederiz. Eymir Gölü'nü ziyaret etmemiş olsanız bile fikirleriniz bizim için önemlidir. Lütfen her bir soruyu elinizden gelen en gerçekçi şekilde yanıtlamaya çalışınız. Bu ankette, çoktan seçmeli, derecelendirme ölçekli ve açık uçlu formatların birleşiminden oluşan 15 soruyu yanıtlamanız beklenmekte ve anketin tamamlanması yaklaşık 7 ila 10 dakika sürmektedir. Anket kapsamında sizden kimlik veya kurum belirleyici hiçbir bilgi istenmeyecektir. Yanıtlarınız kesinlikle gizli tutulacak ve yalnızca araştırma amacıyla kullanılacaktır. Anket, genel olarak kişisel rahatsızlık verecek sorular içermeyecek şekilde tasarlanmıştır. Ancak, katılım sırasında sorulardan ya da başka herhangi bir nedenden ötürü kendinizi rahatsız hissederseniz, herhangi bir anda anketi yarıda bırakıp çalışmadan çekilmekte serbestsiniz.

Anket ile ilgili daha fazla bilgiye ihtiyaç duymanız halinde Funda Yakar'a [] numarasından veya [] elektronik posta adresinden ulaşabilirsiniz.

Yukarıda yer alan bilgileri okudum ve bu ankete gönüllü olarak katılmaktayım.

Anketin bir bölümüne veya tamamına katılmamayı seçebileceğimi ve herhangi bir aşamada bir sorulara karşılansızın ankettten çekilmeyi tercih edebileceğimi anlıyor ve kabul ediyorum.

Ankara şehir merkezinin 20 km güneyinde, Orta Doğu Teknik Üniversitesi kampüsü içerisinde yer alan Eymir Gölü halka açık olup, çeşitli rekreasyonel imkânlar sunmaktadır. Göl ve çevresi, 200'den fazla kuş türü, 700 bitki türünün yanı sıra tilki, porsuk ve gelinciklerin de dâhil olduğu önemli bir flora ve faunaya sahiptir. Gölün kıyıları, sulak alanlar, ormanlar ve bozkırlardan oluşan çok çeşitli peyzajlar ile çevrilidir. Göl çevresinin sunduğu eşsiz manzara; gür sazlıklar, badem, kuşburnu, alıç, karaçam, sarıçam, Toros sediri, kızılçam gibi çok sayıda ağaç türüne ve bazı endemik türler de dâhil olmak üzere çeşitli kelebek ve çiçek türlerinin yaşadığı geniş bozkır ve çayırılara ev sahipliği yapar. Gölün kendisi de çeşitli su bitkileri, planktonlar ve balık türleri için bir yaşam alanı oluşturmaktadır. Mogan'dan Eymir'e kadar uzanan dünya çapında öneme sahip sulak alanlar, özellikle göç mevsiminde pek çok kuş türü için önemli yaşam alanlarıdır. Ne var ki, tüm bu paha biçilemez değerler; kentsel ve endüstriyel baskılar, kirlilik, yanlış kullanım ve iklim değişikliği gibi nedenlerle tehlikeyle karşı karşıyadır.

1. Aylık net hane halkı geliriniz ne kadardır? _____ (TRY)
2. Yaşınız: _____
3. Cinsiyetiniz: Erkek Kadın Diğer Belirtmemeyi tercih ederim
4. İlçe: _____
5. Eğitim Durumunuz / En son Bitirdiğiniz Okul:
 Okur-yazarlığı yok İlkokul Ortaokul İlköğretim Lise
 Üniversite düzeyinde dersler aldım (mezun değil) Önlisans
 Lisans Yüksek Lisans Doktora
6. Çalışma Durumunuz:
 Çalışıyor Çalışmıyor Emekli Öğrenci

Sayfa 1/4

7. ODTÜ ile bir bağlantınız var mı?
 Öğrenci Mezun Akademik Personel İdari Personel
 Yukarıdakilerden herhangi birinin yakını Hiçbiri

8. Son 12 ayda Eymir Gölü'nü ziyaret ettiniz mi?

- Evet Hayır *(Cevabınız hayır ise lütfen 9 ve 10. Soruları boş bırakınız.)*

9. Toplamda, son 12 ayda Eymir Gölü'nü kaç kez ziyaret ettiniz?

- 1-3 kez 4-5 kez 6-9 kez 10 veya daha fazla 20 veya daha fazla

10. Son 12 ayda Eymir Gölü'nde aşağıdaki aktivitelerden herhangi birini yaptınız mı? Lütfen uygun olanların hepsini işaretleyiniz.

(Aşağıdaki seçenekler karışık olarak sıralanmış olup, herhangi bir önem sırasına işaret etmemektedir.)

- Kültür ve sanat etkinlikleri
 Bisiklet sürme
 Kuş gözlemciliği veya diğer yaban hayatı ve tabiat gözlemciliği
 Su bisikleti
 Eğitim/Bilim
 Olta balıkçılığı
 Yenenebilir yabani ürün toplama (bitki, meyve, yemiş, mantar vs.)
 Doğa yürüyüşü
 Fotoğrafçılık
 Piknik
 Dinlenme/kafa dinleme
 Kütrek çekme
 Gezip görme/manzara seyretme
 Sosyalleşme
 Özel bir etkinliğe katılma
 Spor ve antrenman yapma
 Göl çevresindeki restoran ve kafelerde yeme-içme
 Diğer. Lütfen belirtin: _____

11. Eymir Gölü, Çevre, Şehircilik ve İklim Değişikliği Bakanlığı tarafından ilan edilen Özel Çevre Koruma Bölgesi (ÖÇK) kapsamında, Gölbaşı Belediyesi sınırları içerisinde ve Orta Doğu Teknik Üniversitesi (ODTÜ) yerleşkesi üzerinde yer almaktadır. Eymir Gölü'nün korunması, muhafazası ve bakımı bu kurumların sorumluluğunda olup, ağırlıklı olarak ODTÜ tarafından finanse edilmektedir. Varsayalım ki, bu kurumların sağladığı finansman, Eymir Gölü'nü korumakta yetersiz kaldı ve bireylerden gelecek katkılara önemle ihtiyaç duyulmakta, aksi takdirde Göl yok olma tehlikesiyle karşı karşıya kalacaktır. Bireylerden gelecek bu katkının, Göl'e yapılan her ziyarette ödenecek bir giriş ücreti şeklinde olduğunu farz edin. Katkılarından elde edilecek gelirin ise doğrudan Eymir Gölü için oluşturulan ve yalnızca Eymir'e ait sulak alan, orman ve göl ekosistemlerinin, biyolojik çeşitliliğin korunması ve rekreasyon olanaklarının finansmanı için kullanılacak bir fona aktarılacak olduğunu düşünün.

Eymir Gölü'nün korunmasına katkı sağlayacağımı bilerek, her ziyaretinizde giriş ücreti olarak ödemeye istekli olduğunuz azami tutar, eğer varsa, ne kadardır? Lütfen bu soruyu cevaplarken aylık gelirinizi göz önünde bulundurunuz.

- 0 ₺ 5 ₺ 10 ₺ 15 ₺ 20 ₺ 25 ₺
 30 ₺ 35 ₺ 40 ₺ 45 ₺ 50 ₺ 55 ₺
 60 ₺ 65 ₺ 70 ₺ 75 ₺ 80 ₺ 85 ₺
 90 ₺ 95 ₺ 100 ₺ 100 ₺ üzeri

12. 1 ile 10 arasında değerlendirecek olursanız, eğer gerçekten ödemek zorunda olsaydınız, yukarıda işaretlediğiniz miktarı seçmekten ne derece eminsiniz? (1=hiç emin değilim, 10=son derece eminim).

Hiç emin değilim										Son derece eminim
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	

13. Eğer 11. soruyu 0 (sıfır) olarak yanıtladıysanız, lütfen nedenini belirtin (Yalnızca seçiminizi etkileyen en önemli neden olarak gördüğünüz **tek seçeneği** işaretleyiniz).
(Eğer 11. soruya 0 (sıfır) olarak yanıtı vermediyseniz bu soruyu yanıtlamadan geçebilirsiniz.)

- Herhangi bir miktarı ödeme gücüm yok.
- Eymir Gölü'nü korumanın o kadar maliyetli olacağını düşünmüyorum.
- Eymir Gölü, devlet tarafından ve vergilerle finanse edilmeli.
- Ödemeler gönüllülük esasına dayalı olarak ve/veya bağışlar yoluyla yapılmalı.
- Eymir Gölü'nün benim için herhangi bir değeri yok.
- Eymir Gölü benim için önemli, ancak ona finansal bir değer biçmeyi reddediyorum.
- Diğer (Lütfen açıklayınız): _____

14. Ekosistem, bitki, hayvan, ve mikroorganizma topluluklarının ve bunların cansız çevrelerinin işlevsel bir birim olarak etkileşiminden oluşan dinamik kompleks olarak tanımlanır. Ekosistem servisleri, insanların ekosistemlerden elde ettikleri doğrudan ve dolaylı faydaları ifade etmektedir.

Eymir Gölü, sulak alan, çayır, bozkır, su ve orman ekosistemlerinin birleşiminden oluşan bir alan olması nedeniyle çok çeşitli ekosistem hizmetleri sunmaktadır. Lütfen Eymir Gölü'nün sunduğu ekosistem servisleri arasında bulunan ve aşağıda yer verilen ekosistem servislerinden her birinin size göre önem derecesini 1 ile 5 arasında puanlayınız.

(1=hiç önemli değil, 5=çok önemli)

(Aşağıdaki seçenekler karışık olarak sıralanmış olup, herhangi bir önem sırasına işaret etmemektedir.)

	1	2	3	4	5	Fikrim yok
Hava kalitesini koruma (örn. kirlenici gazların ve partiküllerin atmosferden uzaklaştırılması)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Atmosferik oksijen üretimi (örn. ağaçların ve suda yaşayan planktonların fotosentez yoluyla oksijen üretmesi)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Karbon tutma (örn. atmosferik karbondioksitin tüketilmesi sonucu bitkiler, toprak ve su içerisinde karbon olarak depolanması)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
İklim düzenleme (örn. sera gazlarını atmosferden uzaklaştırarak küresel ısınmayı önleme)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Kültürel miras	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Eğitim/Bilimsel faaliyet	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Erozyon kontrolü (örn. bitki örtüsünün, rüzgâr ve su gibi dış etkenlerle toprağın aşındırılmasını ve taşınmasını önlemesi)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Gıda tedariki (meyve, bitki, balık vb.)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Temiz su kaynağı	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yakıt (odun, çıra, kozalak, reçine vb.)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Doğal afet zararlarını önleme (fırtına, sel, toprak kayması vb.)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Besin döngüsü (karbon, azot, oksijen, fosfor gibi döngüler)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Habitat sağlama ve biyolojik çeşitlilik	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>

Sayfa 3 / 4

İlham vericilik/Estetik/Manzara	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Haşere ve hastalık kontrolü (örn. türler arası rekabet sonucu doğal dengeyle bazı zararlı türlerin gereğinden fazla çoğalmasının önlenmesi)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Polinasyon (Tozlaşma) (bitkilerin üreyerek nesillerini devam ettirebilmeleri için gereken süreç)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Birincil üretim (fotosentez ve kemosentez)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rekreasyonel faaliyetler (örn. eğlenme, dinlenme, spor gibi bir kısmı 10. soruda da sayılan faaliyetler)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sosyal İlişkiler	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Toprak oluşumu (örn. fiziksel, kimyasal ve biyolojik süreçlerle)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ruhsal/Manevi değer (aidiyet hissi, anı değeri, kutsiyet vb.)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Su döngüsü (Suyun buharlaşma ve yağış gibi süreçlerle atmosfer ve yeryüzü arasındaki devamlı hareketleri)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Suyun temizlenmesi (örn. yer üstü sulanın topraktan süzülerek temiz yeraltı suyu oluşturması)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
Su düzenleme (örn. suyun akış rejimini, hızını veya yönünü düzenleme)	1	2	3	4	5	<input type="checkbox"/>

15. Lütfen aşağıda yer alan ifadelerin her biri için düşüncelerinizi/duygularınızı en iyi tanımlayan seçeneği işaretleyiniz.

	Kesinlikle katılmıyorum	Katılmıyorum	Notür	Katılıyorum	Kesinlikle katılıyorum
1. Eymir Gölü'nün korunması benim için önemlidir çünkü ondan doğrudan yararlanmaktayım.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Eymir Gölü'nün korunması benim için önemlidir çünkü şu anda yararlanmasam bile gelecekte ondan yararlanabilirim.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Ben yararlısam da yararlanmasam da Eymir Gölü'nün gelecek nesiller için korunması bana göre önemlidir.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Eymir Gölü'nün korunması benim için önemlidir çünkü insanların ondan yararlanıp yararlanmamasından bağımsız olarak Eymir Gölü var olmalıdır.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C. Consent Form

ARAŞTIRMAYA GÖNÜLLÜ KATILIM FORMU

Bu anket çalışması, ODTÜ doktora öğrencisi Funda Yakar tarafından yürütülmektedir. Bu form sizi araştırma koşulları hakkında bilgilendirmek için hazırlanmıştır.

Çalışmanın Amacı Nedir?

Araştırmanın amacı, Eymir Gölü'nün sağladığı ekosistem servislerinin değerlendirilmesi ve Ankara halkının Eymir Gölü'ne atfettiği değerin ortaya çıkarılması maksadıyla bilgi toplamaktır.

Bize Nasıl Yardımcı Olmanızı İsteyeceğiz?

Araştırmaya katılmayı kabul ederseniz, bu ankette, çoktan seçmeli, derecelendirme ölçekli ve açık uçlu formatların birleşiminden oluşan 15 soruyu yanıtlamanız beklenmekte ve anketin tamamlanması yaklaşık 7 ila 10 dakika sürmektedir. Eymir Gölü'nü ziyaret etmemiş olsanız bile fikirleriniz bizim için önemlidir. Lütfen her bir soruyu elinizden gelen en iyi şekilde yanıtlamaya çalışınız.

Sizden Topladığımız Bilgileri Nasıl Kullanacağız?

Anket kapsamında sizden kimlik veya kurum belirleyici hiçbir bilgi istenmeyecektir. Yanıtlarınız kesinlikle gizli tutulacak ve yalnızca araştırma amacıyla kullanılacaktır.

Katılımla İlgili Bilmeniz Gerekenler:

Anket, genel olarak kişisel rahatsızlık verecek sorular içermeyecek şekilde tasarlanmıştır. Ancak, katılım sırasında sorulardan ya da başka herhangi bir nedenden ötürü kendinizi rahatsız hissederseniz, herhangi bir anda anketi yarıda bırakıp çalışmadan çekilmekte serbestsiniz.

Araştırmayla İlgili Daha Fazla Bilgi Almak İsterseniz:

Anket ile ilgili daha fazla bilgiye ihtiyaç duymanız halinde Funda Yakar'a [redacted] numarasından veya [redacted] elektronik posta adresinden ulaşabilirsiniz.

Yukarıda yer alan bilgileri okudum ve bu ankete gönüllü olarak katılmaktayım.

Anketin bir bölümüne veya tamamına katılmamayı seçebileceğimi ve herhangi bir aşamada bir soruyla karşılaşmajsızın anketten çekilmeyi tercih edebileceğimi anlıyor ve kabul ediyorum.

(Formu doldurup imzaladıktan sonra uygulayıcıya geri veriniz).

İsim Soyad

Tarih

İmza

---/---/----

Anket linki için karekod:

D. Ethical Approval

UYGULAMALI ETİK ARAŞTIRMA MERKEZİ
APPLIED ETHICS RESEARCH CENTER

ORTA DOĞU TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
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18 OCAK 2024

Konu: Değerlendirme Sonucu

Gönderen: ODTÜ İnsan Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu (IAEK)

İlgi: İnsan Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu Başvurusu

Sayın Prof.Dr. Ayhan SOL

Danışmanlığınızı yürüttüğünüz **Funda YAKAR**'ın "*Ekosistem Servislerinin Kıymetlendirilmesi: Felsefe, Ekoloji ve Politika*" başlıklı araştırmanız İnsan Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu tarafından uygun görülerek 0037-ODTÜİAEK-2024 protokol numarası ile onaylanmıştır.

Bilgilerinize saygılarımla sunarım.

Prof. Dr. Ş. Halil TURAN
Başkan

Prof.Dr. İ. Semih AKÇOMAK
Üye

Doç. Dr. Ali Emre Turgut
Üye

Doç. Dr. Şerife SEVINÇ
Üye

Doç.Dr. Murat Perit ÇAKIR
Üye

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Süreyya ÖZCAN KABASAKAL
Üye

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Müge GÜNDÜZ
Üye

E. Cluster Analysis Outputs

Final Cluster Centers

	Cluster		
	1	2	3
ZMonthly_income	.269113328216315	.050325435274866	-.160187486320278
ZAge	.289163142412847	.065269449182625	-.184376423065284
ZGender_Recode	.120925929818874	.046191526345227	-.097790199656289
ZDistrict_Recode	.128030251269560	-.122032307107759	.083585681841092
ZEducation_Recode	.271196681707929	.062352450928668	-.174166771683592
ZAffiliation_General	-.185079712345279	.146945641248382	-.088578003645931
ZVisited_Eymir_Recode	.299505035734860	.823638848270861	-1.018582954370473
ZVisit_Frequency_Recode	.189140565310927	.595788348439967	-.726059892141513
ZActivity_Art	.010381472635669	.120368966505454	-.135819147913982
ZActivity_Biking	.060955318294998	.502598222005845	-.573986521174857
ZActivity_Birdwatching	.038398824034447	.167880391247585	-.198770383237140
ZActivity_CycleBoating	.369505671049647	-.042352978251213	-.097941262205930
ZActivity_Edu_Sci	-.120242451184857	.152740410964548	-.120242451184857
ZActivity_Fishing	.213690026631121	.013235305703504	-.097941262205930
ZActivity_Hiking	.231855886427282	.680377871478792	-.835339613773829
ZActivity_Photography	.006675807681680	.316361113217756	-.348919581374410
ZActivity_Picnic	.053422506657780	.338823826009705	-.391765048823722
ZActivity_Resting	.141237311119537	.650440671453614	-.767178619839101
ZActivity_Rowing	.134817293752718	.061746123581413	-.120242451184857
ZActivity_Sightseeing	-.112235500538527	.639262066017748	-.655952302826869
ZActivity_Socializing	.008299213497104	.474036495255201	-.522156803035629
ZActivity_SpecialEvent	.010381472635668	.120368966505455	-.135819147913983
ZActivity_Sports	-.104002861324331	.306060907610534	-.294420586157061
ZActivity_RestaurantCafe	.105009911718020	.507311397826923	-.596350667286211
ZWTP_Recode	.020121462776744	-.138910389671255	.144203583111937
ZCertainty	-.161582399067930	.029828625522775	.030450548028223
ZReason_ZeroBid_Recode	.037715189230359	-.009610820421636	-.004208288231959
ZEcosystemService_AirQuality	-1.415846719480899	.268652346916876	.258847333172289
ZEcosystemService_OxygenProduction	-1.368730939451111	.242846458162414	.268696137536832
ZEcosystemService_CarbonStorage	-1.429857230856303	.236327754372298	.299703802826274
ZEcosystemService_ClimateRegulation	-1.437517481502607	.247169727592286	.290826947786888
ZEcosystemService_CulturalHeritage	-1.564475490520082	.274154864787311	.310868238986241
ZEcosystemService_Edu_Sci	-1.304941430873970	.236665321416693	.250550591571568
ZEcosystemService_ErosionControl	-1.540446451521343	.275203491699587	.300336212047248
ZEcosystemService_Food	-1.001021947689262	.196124016512270	.176239677471725
ZEcosystemService_FreshWater	-1.096789574729348	.147344447894889	.267037805157291
ZEcosystemService_Fuel	-.786285053515474	.151994437035557	.140685459647593
ZEcosystemService_NaturalHazardProtect	-1.514832580624745	.265329632515739	.301141824294797
ZEcosystemService_NutrientCycling	-1.514854119275201	.283100213436294	.281697233055914
ZEcosystemService_Habitat_Biodiversity	-1.508939078774879	.280560048382811	.282167871291836
ZEcosystemService_InspirationAestheticSc	-1.188143194375345	.330493242355731	.102226041378478
ZEcosystemService_PestDisease_Control	-1.516705634773532	.270547491608251	.296161455310808
ZEcosystemService_Pollination	-1.642556420719054	.328855830065057	.281481628434446
ZEcosystemService_PrimaryProduction	-1.578437431643701	.332447761132402	.252509080940769
ZEcosystemService_Recreational	-1.131490975348723	.289634465623763	.124828569423780
ZEcosystemService_SocialRelations	-1.130908021012910	.265125960425611	.151429743834983
ZEcosystemService_SoilFormation	-1.586530807579524	.295355914583156	.296273308298016
ZEcosystemService_Spirit_Senti	-1.211991491636932	.262231190327460	.186264309097377
ZEcosystemService_WaterCycling	-1.658521587278630	.295494377001749	.324236479379088
ZEcosystemService_WaterPurification	-1.551204342471730	.286211203605309	.292487656426947
ZEcosystemService_WaterRegulation	-1.490522869876986	.287773277669378	.267079603805002
ZValue_DirectBenefit_Recode	-.373054296873148	.404575674984819	-.297188853719313
ZValue_FutureBenefit_Recode	-.475198251461155	.192697147429000	-.025360282117928
ZValue_Generations_Recode	-.635685143118839	.168199426988804	.064132103271682
ZValue_Existence_Recode	-.628672408151642	.164342508168614	.065615472939731

Initial Cluster Centers

	Cluster		
	1	2	3
ZMonthly_income	-.263813846388334	-.909701450447483	1.397039992620908
ZAge	.195222095010303	-.057843583706755	-.310909262423813
ZGender_Recode	.403086432729581	.403086432729581	.403086432729581
ZDistrict_Recode	-.640586117093692	-.640586117093692	1.033627754588638
ZEducation_Recode	-.077662755711153	1.841064150093800	-.077662755711153
ZAffiliation_General	-.886205210876808	1.125720132735405	-.886205210876808
ZVisited_Eymir_Recode	.823638848270863	.823638848270863	.823638848270863
ZVisit_Frequency_Recode	.877918346501012	2.561597367187885	.036078836157575
ZActivity_Art	-.171294298488531	5.824006148610048	-.171294298488531
ZActivity_Biking	1.561027604460968	1.561027604460968	-.639078415249122
ZActivity_Birdwatching	5.018952176737787	5.018952176737787	-.198770383237140
ZActivity_CycleBoating	10.185891269416780	-.097941262205931	-.097941262205931
ZActivity_Edu_Sci	-.120242451184857	8.296729131755136	-.120242451184857
ZActivity_Fishing	-.097941262205931	-.097941262205931	10.185891269416780
ZActivity_Hiking	1.114909262501169	1.114909262501169	1.114909262501169
ZActivity_Photography	2.717053726443581	2.717053726443581	-.367169422492376
ZActivity_Picnic	-.391765048823722	2.546472817354194	2.546472817354194
ZActivity_Resting	-.791461913254763	1.260476380368697	-.791461913254763
ZActivity_Rowing	-.120242451184857	-.120242451184857	-.120242451184857
ZActivity_Sightseeing	-.668736524042054	1.491796861324582	-.668736524042054
ZActivity_Socializing	1.860061225038464	1.860061225038464	-.536336672250354
ZActivity_SpecialEvent	5.824006148610050	5.824006148610050	-.171294298488531
ZActivity_Sports	3.166811762933604	-.315023159663552	-.315023159663552
ZActivity_RestaurantCafe	1.636404457605814	1.636404457605814	1.636404457605814
ZWTP_Recode	-.096346298236877	.216128182531375	-.721295259773380
ZCertainty	.611563701117734	-.379264310770690	.611563701117734
ZReason_ZeroBid_Recode	.000000000000000	.000000000000000	.000000000000000
ZEcosystemService_AirQuality	-3.800736577563623	.541407715773200	-.544128357561006
ZEcosystemService_OxygenProduction	-3.628321183581011	.572607157618239	.572607157618239
ZEcosystemService_CarbonStorage	-2.969703479470781	.659934106549062	-.247475289955899
ZEcosystemService_ClimateRegulation	-2.935612413894688	.627424182064853	-.263334966925032
ZEcosystemService_CulturalHeritage	-3.165803004726418	.655581992510710	-3.165803004726418
ZEcosystemService_Edu_Sci	-2.548084974603030	-.038803324486338	-.875230541191902
ZEcosystemService_ErosionCotrol	-2.948891430604950	.696495574082033	-1.126197928261458
ZEcosystemService_Food	-1.572033034832078	-1.572033034832078	-.226078329424011
ZEcosystemService_FreshWater	-2.174264389008391	-1.417739519408212	-.661214649808032
ZEcosystemService_Fuel	-.550062076064473	-1.199675264054725	-1.199675264054725
ZEcosystemService_NaturalHazardProtect	-2.453675285020178	-.039508330860496	-1.648952966966951
ZEcosystemService_NutrientCycling	-2.296924245085327	.680958157037840	-1.304296777710938
ZEcosystemService_Habitat_Biodiversity	-3.791568218490880	.527154837812482	-.552525926263359
ZEcosystemService_InspirationAestheticSc	-2.831485915036578	.689485206583583	-1.071000354226497
ZEcosystemService_PestDisease_Control	-1.759291607433320	.768709581337107	-1.759291607433320
ZEcosystemService_Pollination	-3.236081306491269	.647216261298251	-2.265256914543889
ZEcosystemService_PrimaryProduction	-3.214487135418636	.654095957088353	-1.280195589165142
ZEcosystemService_Recreational	-1.734291338327066	-.045163836935602	-.889727587631334
ZEcosystemService_SocialRelations	-2.459788086934279	-.023507966078438	-2.459788086934279
ZEcosystemService_SoilFormation	-1.853848402610084	.735026468287059	-1.853848402610084
ZEcosystemService_Spirit_Senti	-1.564928071309049	-.012007120751733	-2.341388546587706
ZEcosystemService_WaterCycling	-3.197002639323787	.622133158565789	.622133158565789
ZEcosystemService_WaterPurification	-2.376614725029506	.629181651342634	-.372750474114746
ZEcosystemService_WaterRegulation	-2.884494553777945	.716218035461868	-.183960111848085
ZValue_DirectBenefit_Recode	.339909259853413	.339909259853413	1.137461713140752
ZValue_FutureBenefit_Recode	-.080110050054756	.761045475520158	.761045475520158
ZValue_Generations_Recode	-.405826340228709	.486566659227089	.486566659227089
ZValue_Existence_Recode	-.365708150185613	.502073901102282	.502073901102282

ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
ZMonthly_income	4.792	2	.982	417	4.881	.008
ZAge	6.026	2	.976	417	6.175	.002
ZGender_Recode	1.488	2	.998	417	1.491	.226
ZDistrict_Recode	2.509	2	.993	417	2.527	.081
ZEducation_Recode	5.350	2	.979	417	5.464	.005
ZAffiliation_General	3.791	2	.987	417	3.842	.022
ZVisited_Eymir_Recode	153.380	2	.269	417	569.848	.000
ZVisit_Frequency_Recode	78.560	2	.628	417	125.094	.000
ZActivity_Art	2.903	2	.991	417	2.929	.055
ZActivity_Biking	51.328	2	.759	417	67.660	.000
ZActivity_Birdwatching	5.994	2	.976	417	6.141	.002
ZActivity_CycleBoating	5.482	2	.979	417	5.603	.004
ZActivity_Edu_Sci	3.857	2	.986	417	3.910	.021
ZActivity_Fishing	2.334	2	.994	417	2.349	.097
ZActivity_Hiking	103.557	2	.508	417	203.804	.000
ZActivity_Photography	19.547	2	.911	417	21.455	.000
ZActivity_Picnic	23.682	2	.891	417	26.573	.000
ZActivity_Resting	89.526	2	.575	417	155.585	.000
ZActivity_Rowing	2.174	2	.994	417	2.186	.114
ZActivity_Sightseeing	74.574	2	.647	417	115.240	.000
ZActivity_Socializing	43.827	2	.795	417	55.156	.000
ZActivity_SpecialEvent	2.903	2	.991	417	2.929	.055
ZActivity_Sports	16.346	2	.926	417	17.645	.000
ZActivity_RestaurantCafe	54.221	2	.745	417	72.805	.000
ZWTP_Recode	3.555	2	.988	417	3.600	.028
ZCertainty	1.022	2	.995	417	1.027	.359
ZReason_ZeroBid_Recode	.057	2	.117	417	.486	.615
ZEcosystemService_AirQuality	78.490	2	.578	417	135.800	.000
ZEcosystemService_OxygenProduction	73.379	2	.574	417	127.900	.000
ZEcosystemService_CarbonStorage	80.224	2	.536	417	149.646	.000
ZEcosystemService_ClimateRegulation	80.991	2	.542	417	149.428	.000
ZEcosystemService_CulturalHeritage	95.889	2	.478	417	200.708	.000

ANOVA Continued

	Cluster Mean Square	df	Error Mean Square	df	F	Sig.
ZEcosystemService_Edu_Sci	66.680	2	.608	417	109.627	.000
ZEcosystemService_ErosionCotrol	92.936	2	.478	417	194.620	.000
ZEcosystemService_Food	39.250	2	.730	417	53.751	.000
ZEcosystemService_FreshWater	47.731	2	.682	417	69.952	.000
ZEcosystemService_Fuel	24.211	2	.805	417	30.086	.000
ZEcosystemService_NaturalHazardProtect	89.901	2	.494	417	181.808	.000
ZEcosystemService_NutrientCycling	89.847	2	.476	417	188.930	.000
ZEcosystemService_Habitat_Biodiversity	89.146	2	.489	417	182.488	.000
ZEcosystemService_InspirationAestheticSc.	57.572	2	.640	417	89.964	.000
ZEcosystemService_PestDisease_Control	90.095	2	.467	417	192.854	.000
ZEcosystemService_Pollination	105.732	2	.397	417	266.350	.000
ZEcosystemService_PrimaryProduction	97.829	2	.440	417	222.508	.000
ZEcosystemService_Recreational	51.325	2	.648	417	79.167	.000
ZEcosystemService_SocialRelations	50.645	2	.666	417	76.047	.000
ZEcosystemService_SoilFormation	98.550	2	.415	417	237.683	.000
ZEcosystemService_Spirit_Senti	57.767	2	.651	417	88.736	.000
ZEcosystemService_WaterCycling	107.733	2	.383	417	281.600	.000
ZEcosystemService_WaterPurification	94.212	2	.455	417	207.233	.000
ZEcosystemService_WaterRegulation	87.002	2	.460	417	188.963	.000
ZValue_DirectBenefit_Recode	27.196	2	.874	417	31.104	.000
ZValue_FutureBenefit_Recode	10.941	2	.952	417	11.489	.000
ZValue_Generations_Recode	16.300	2	.927	417	17.590	.000
ZValue_Existence_Recode	15.905	2	.929	417	17.129	.000

Distances between Final Cluster Centers

Cluster	1	2	3
1		8.490	8.633
2	8.490		4.156
3	8.633	4.156	

Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	2	3
1	66		
2	185		
3	169		
Valid	420		
Missing	0		

F. Regression Analysis Outputs

Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Tolerance
(Constant)	-9.959	13.828		-0.720	0.472		
Monthly_income	9.820e-05	0.000	0.166	3.681	0.000	0.829	1.206
Age	0.181	0.211	0.045	0.857	0.392	0.624	1.604
Gender_Recode	1.329	2.405	0.025	0.553	0.581	0.858	1.165
District_Recode	-0.262	0.247	-0.049	-1.062	0.289	0.795	1.259
Education_Recode	0.633	1.612	0.021	0.393	0.695	0.613	1.630
Employment_Recode	1.205	1.831	0.038	0.658	0.511	0.508	1.967
Affiliation_General	7.377	2.986	0.115	2.471	0.014	0.786	1.271
Visit_Frequency_Recode	-0.635	1.727	-0.024	-0.368	0.713	0.412	2.428
Activity_Art	-1.331	9.500	-0.007	-0.140	0.889	0.690	1.450
Activity_Biking	0.988	3.783	0.014	0.261	0.794	0.586	1.707
Activity_Birdwatching	-8.045	8.926	-0.048	-0.901	0.368	0.592	1.690
Activity_CycleBoating	-9.149	15.677	-0.028	-0.584	0.560	0.745	1.342
Activity_Edu_Sci	6.294	14.212	0.023	0.443	0.658	0.608	1.646
Activity_Fishing	3.417	14.338	0.010	0.238	0.812	0.891	1.122
Activity_Hiking	-6.619	3.874	-0.103	-1.709	0.088	0.466	2.145
Activity_Photography	6.480	5.257	0.066	1.233	0.219	0.596	1.677
Activity_Picnic	-2.349	4.482	-0.025	-0.524	0.601	0.744	1.343
Activity_Resting	1.214	4.085	0.018	0.297	0.766	0.437	2.288
Activity_Rowing	8.388	12.810	0.031	0.655	0.513	0.748	1.337
Activity_Sightseeing	-8.481	4.138	-0.123	-2.049	0.041	0.472	2.118
Activity_Socializing	-2.243	3.970	-0.029	-0.565	0.572	0.631	1.584
Activity_SpecialEvent	18.896	9.961	0.098	1.897	0.059	0.628	1.594
Activity_Sports	-9.935	5.654	-0.089	-1.757	0.080	0.657	1.522
Activity_RestaurantCafe	3.930	3.899	0.055	1.008	0.314	0.575	1.740
Certainty	0.124	0.187	0.030	0.662	0.508	0.840	1.191
Reason_ZeroBid_Recode	-0.467	0.045	-0.485	-10.2699	0.000	0.759	1.318
EcosystemService_AirQuality	3.176	2.795	0.095	1.136	0.257	0.243	4.118
EcosystemService_OxygenProd	-1.548	2.707	-0.049	-0.572	0.568	0.234	4.268
EcosystemService_CarbonStora	-0.067	4.012	-0.002	-0.017	0.987	0.080	12.468
EcosystemService_ClimateReg	-2.688	3.874	-0.098	-0.694	0.488	0.084	11.836
EcosystemService_CulturalHeri	-0.649	2.076	-0.022	-0.313	0.755	0.335	2.985
EcosystemService_Edu_Sci	0.244	1.781	0.010	0.137	0.891	0.344	2.910

Coefficients Continued

EcosystemService_ErosionCont	-0.606	2.299	-0.022	-0.263	0.792	0.245	4.084
EcosystemService_Food	0.086	1.721	0.004	0.050	0.960	0.227	4.403
EcosystemService_FreshWater	0.859	1.700	0.038	0.505	0.614	0.305	3.281
EcosystemService_Fuel	1.190	1.239	0.064	0.961	0.337	0.385	2.600
EcosystemService_NaturalHazardProtect	-1.109	2.083	-0.045	-0.532	0.595	0.235	4.254
EcosystemService_NutrientCycling	0.308	2.608	0.010	0.118	0.906	0.218	4.579
EcosystemService_Habitat_Biodiversity	0.440	2.787	0.013	0.158	0.875	0.232	4.307
EcosystemService_InspirationAestheticScenic	-2.168	2.071	-0.081	-1.047	0.296	0.282	3.549
EcosystemService_PestDisease_Control	0.756	1.872	0.030	0.404	0.686	0.308	3.245
EcosystemService_Pollination	3.579	2.741	0.123	1.305	0.193	0.191	5.230
EcosystemService_PrimaryProduction	1.726	2.507	0.059	0.689	0.491	0.228	4.388
EcosystemService_Recreational	0.633	1.795	0.025	0.352	0.725	0.332	3.010
EcosystemService_SocialRelations	0.398	1.898	0.016	0.210	0.834	0.282	3.550
EcosystemService_SoilFormation	2.700	2.074	0.105	1.302	0.194	0.262	3.824
EcosystemService_Spirit_Sentimental	0.621	1.677	0.026	0.370	0.711	0.340	2.940
EcosystemService_WaterCycling	-0.363	2.951	-0.013	-0.123	0.902	0.161	6.227
EcosystemService_WaterPurification	-4.216	2.851	-0.140	-1.479	0.140	0.188	5.315
EcosystemService_WaterRegulation	-2.290	2.386	-0.086	-0.960	0.338	0.212	4.713
Value_DirectBenefit_Recode	-0.051	1.709	-0.002	-0.030	0.976	0.377	2.650
Value_FutureBenefit_Recode	0.078	1.950	0.003	0.040	0.968	0.322	3.101
Value_Generations_Recode	-3.390	2.739	-0.119	-1.238	0.217	0.184	5.438
Value_Existence_Recode	1.298	2.489	0.047	0.521	0.602	0.210	4.751

Variant Proportions

Eigenvalue	Condition Index	(Constant)	Monthly_income	Age	Gender_Recode	District_Recode	Education_Recode	Employment_Recode	Affiliation_General
37.534	1.000	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
3.105	3.477	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.782	4.589	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.353	5.268	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.023	6.056	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.933	6.341	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.831	6.720	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.790	6.894	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04
0.718	7.228	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03
0.696	7.342	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04
0.624	7.753	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.19
0.573	8.097	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07
0.523	8.474	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15
0.478	8.857	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03
0.462	9.010	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.423	9.422	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07
0.375	9.999	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05
0.349	10.371	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.03
0.309	11.028	0.00	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.285	11.470	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.231	12.734	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.211	13.335	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.04
0.183	14.329	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.00	0.00	0.08
0.163	15.174	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.141	16.314	0.00	0.13	0.03	0.06	0.10	0.02	0.03	0.01
0.111	18.363	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.03
0.103	19.099	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.33	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.088	20.623	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.34	0.00	0.08	0.06	0.01
0.062	24.516	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.051	27.147	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.046	28.584	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.05	0.00
0.043	29.487	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.037	32.008	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00
0.034	33.111	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.06	0.00
0.030	35.092	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.00	0.15	0.03	0.00
0.029	35.830	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.17	0.10	0.00
0.028	36.938	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.02	0.00	0.05	0.13	0.00

Variant Proportions Continued

0.025	38.845	0.01	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.13	0.00
0.025	39.035	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.18	0.01
0.021	41.812	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.019	44.052	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01
0.019	44.507	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.02
0.018	46.011	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.016	49.049	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.015	49.788	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.01
0.014	50.885	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.012	56.590	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.01
0.010	59.839	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.009	65.888	0.43	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01
0.009	66.382	0.14	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.00
0.007	71.752	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.007	75.966	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.006	77.600	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01
0.006	82.093	0.22	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.00
0.003	115.891	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Variant Proportions Continued

Visit_Frequency_Recode	Activity_Art	Activity_Biking	Activity_Birdwatching	Activity_CycleBoating	Activity_Edu_Sci	Activity_Fishing	Activity_Hiking	Activity_Photography	Activity_Picnic
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01
0.00	0.07	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.14	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.74	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.28	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.05	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.17
0.00	0.10	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.22	0.12
0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.06	0.18
0.02	0.22	0.14	0.00	0.10	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
0.01	0.08	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.02	0.00	0.22	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.03
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03
0.00	0.11	0.10	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.06
0.01	0.15	0.00	0.30	0.08	0.12	0.00	0.02	0.06	0.00
0.03	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.20	0.02	0.00	0.17	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.16	0.02	0.07
0.02	0.07	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.02
0.02	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.03	0.03	0.12	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00
0.45	0.00	0.18	0.02	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.02	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.39	0.03	0.01
0.10	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.05	0.01
0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.00
0.03	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01

Variant Proportions Continued

0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01
0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Variant Proportions Continued

Activity_Resting	Activity_Rowing	Activity_Sightseeing	Activity_Socializing	Activity_SpecialEvent	Activity_Sports	Activity_RestaurantCafe	Certainty	Reason_ZeroBid_Record	EcosystemService_AirQuality
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.19	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.13	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.28	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.08	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.10	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.18	0.02	0.02	0.11	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.09	0.02	0.21	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.21	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.18	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.13	0.00	0.00
0.07	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.10	0.00	0.18	0.06	0.00	0.00
0.02	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.27	0.09	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.23	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.09	0.04	0.01	0.00
0.20	0.01	0.18	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.41	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.06	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.08	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00
0.05	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.12	0.00
0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.46	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.16	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00

Variant Proportions Continued

0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.04
0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.03
0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.17
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.35
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Variant Proportions Contined

0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.01	0.03	0.14
0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.30
0.00	0.00	0.02	0.08	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.03
0.00	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.06	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.02
0.03	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.03
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.03	0.00	0.09	0.09	0.00	0.03
0.05	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.00	0.07	0.02
0.00	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.01	0.00	0.11	0.01	0.05	0.21	0.44	0.05	0.08
0.07	0.01	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.06	0.27	0.00
0.11	0.02	0.31	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.09	0.13
0.03	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.11	0.01	0.05	0.17	0.02
0.01	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.01	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.08	0.01
0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
0.16	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.03	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.47	0.39	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
0.05	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01
0.28	0.59	0.00	0.06	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.03
0.02	0.03	0.11	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.00	0.00
0.09	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00

Variant Proportions Continued

0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.11	0.00	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.01	0.02	0.15	0.19	0.00	0.01
0.01	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.31	0.00	0.03
0.01	0.02	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.02	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.01	0.01
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.07	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00
0.08	0.27	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00
0.00	0.03	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.12	0.02
0.03	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.13	0.25	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03
0.05	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00
0.08	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.67	0.70
0.45	0.28	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.05
0.01	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.00

CURRICULUM VITAE

Surname, Name: Yakar, Funda

EDUCATION

Degree	Institution	Year of Graduation
PhD	Middle East Technical University	2025
MS	King's College London	2014
BS	Middle East Technical University	2007

FOREIGN LANGUAGES

English, German

PUBLICATIONS

1. Sol, A., & Yakar, F. (2023). Çevre Etiği Normlarının Araçsal (Epistemik) Gerekçelendirilmesi: Ekosistem Hizmetleri Örneği. In E. Y. Şahin & M. Özer (Eds.), *Çağdaş Epistemolojide Temel Problemler* (pp. 37–61). Sentez Nesriyat.